

“The Economics and Environmental Effects of Plastic Ban and Deysho Production in Bhutan”

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Submitted by Tim Bodt (Registration Number 790620-077-130), January 2001.

Made under Supervision of Prof. Dr. E.C. van Ierland,
Environmental Economics and Natural Resources Group,
Department of Social Sciences,
Wageningen University, The Netherlands.

WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT
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Preface and acknowledgements

An old Bhutanese proverb says:

མཚམས་ཚོད་ཤེས་ན་མཁམ་པའི་རྟགས།

(Tsham tshö shên khäbi ‘མཚམས་ཚོད་ཤེས་ན་མཁམ་པའི་རྟགས།), or roughly translated: “to know ones’ limitations is the hallmark of a wise person”. With this proverb in mind I started on this research, knowing that being only second years’ Environmental Economics students at the Wageningen University my thesis research should not attempt to reach to the sky. If an attempt to do this was made, both feet might have lost touch with the earth, resulting in a probably painful downfall.

It is inept to scientific research though that to some degree one has to explore ones’ limitations in order to achieve something. My seven months in Bhutan involved a lot of exactly that, and not only in the field of studies. It was a very enjoyable time, a very instructive time as well. I made many new friends, saw many new places and learnt many new things. The research took me to the remote corners of Eastern Bhutan, where Trashi Yangtse district is the traditional home base of deysho production. Travelling by public transport, be it bus, truck or lifting, was an unforgettable experience.

I am obliged to thank countless people for all their help and support. I can’t mention all of them here though so will just mention the main persons. Firstly, Prof. Dr. Ekko Van Ierland, my supervisor, for whom a Bhutanese proverb is rightly applicable:

གོང་མའི་བཀའ་རྒྱུ་འདི། བགན་རི་བ་ཅི། མོན་གསེར་བ་འཕང།

(Gongmai kâ ‘ja di, gän ri wa ci, wön ser wa phang), or: “The best of a superior if carried is heavier than a mountain, if ignored its loss proves more precious than gold”. Under his supervision I had my tough times in writing this report, but I duly understand that his comments and advise were invaluable in being able to write the report that currently lies before you. Secondly, my parents and granddad for their continuous trust in me and the goodwill they have constantly shown towards me, despite the fact that I was gone for such a long time. Thirdly, Lyonpo Yeshey Zimba, Finance Minister of Bhutan and Mr. Nim Dorji and Mr. Dorji Wangdi of the Sustainable Development Secretariat, Thimphu, for enabling my coming to and supporting my stay in Bhutan. Furthermore my thanks go to my two host families in Thimphu, Ap Sangay Wangdi and Am Mindu, and Ap Mindu Dukpa and Am Kunzang Choden. And last but not least, I am eternally grateful to all my friends all over Bhutan who made my stay so enjoyable for all these months. Without them all it wouldn’t have been even half the same.

གནམ་མེད་ས་མེད་བཀའ་དྲིན་ཆེ།

(Name same kadrinche)
Thank you very much!

1 Introduction

1.1 Bhutan

The Kingdom of Bhutan, or Dru Ü, the Land of the Thunder Dragon as it is called by the inhabitants, is a small landlocked country in the Eastern Himalayas in Asia. In the North it is bordered by Chinese-occupied Tibet, in the East by the Indian state of Arunachal Pradesh, in the South by the Indian states of Assam and West Bengal, and in the West by the Indian state of Sikkim. The cultural identity and social organisation of the country are based upon a system of norms and values finding its' origins in a unique absorption of the traditional animist beliefs (referred to as Bön) by the Tantrayana Buddhism introduced from Tibet in the 8th century AD by the Indian Saint Guru Padmasambhava. Greatly influenced by this system the people of Bhutan have always kept a way of life that remains closely connected to the natural environment they live in, resulting in an almost virgin natural environment with one of the highest biodiversities in the world. This system has also preserved a rich cultural and religious heritage (National Environment Secretariat, 1992).

It is this natural and cultural variety that the country has cherished and fiercely defended over the centuries. For long the country remained isolated from developments taking place in other parts of the world. The 20th century however has seen great changes in the political, economical and social situation of the country. Despite the developments that have taken place and that have changed the country so much, a quote from the present King Jigme Singye Wangchuck has been the guideline for all development policies over the years: "We will not sacrifice our Gross National Happiness for a higher Gross National Product" (Kinga et al., 1999). Development was deemed not to go at the expense of the natural resources and cultural richness (National Environment Commission, 1999a). This is a very courageous stand, especially when taken by an underdeveloped country. In practice this implies that all developments activities, whether in the economic, technical, medical or scientific field, are only executed if they comply with the preservation of Bhutan's cultural identity, the preservation of the natural environment and the continuation along the path of sustainable development, as described in the environmental document called "The Middle Path" (National Environment Commission, 1999a). The policies of the Royal Government of Bhutan (RGOB) in the past few decades have assured that, despite a growing population and mounting pressure on the natural environment, this pressure has not resulted in a dramatic decrease in its' quality or quantity (National Environment Commission, 1998). At the same time, development policies have been aimed at raising the welfare of the people. Great achievements in health and education have been accomplished and especially in comparison to neighbouring countries such as India and Nepal the living standards are much higher and equally distributed. Bhutan has a total GDP of Nu. 18,202 million at current prices which equals US\$ 396,990,185/-¹ and a GDP per capita of Nu. 28,606.3/- which is equivalent to US\$ 624/- (Kuensel, 2000c). Bhutan is ranked the 125th position on the Human Development Index (HDI) according to latest data, well ahead of neighbouring countries like India and Bangladesh (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2000). Even though Bhutan is classified as Low Income Food Deficit Country, poverty and hunger are virtually unknown and apart from food grains Bhutan is almost self sufficient (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2000). Thus Bhutan has become one of the few countries where a sustainable development has been successfully implemented over the years.

¹ US\$=Nu.45.85 (Kuensel, 2000g)

Map 1: Geographical position of the kingdom of Bhutan (Planning Commission, 1992):

1.1.1 History, Politics and Policies and Society

Bhutan has been a sovereign country at least since the 8th century AD. Internal strifes divided the country however for many centuries. The advent of Zhabdrung Ngawang Namgyel in 1616 AD from Tibet unified the country to a large extent and strengthened its position. The protection of the natural and cultural bounty of the country however had led to a self-imposed isolation for many centuries. As a result the country remained closed to foreign powers, with as only exception the age-old religious, economic and cultural ties with Tibet and the trade with Indian states to the South. In 1865, after a border war, Bhutan established diplomatic relations with British India. This did not lead to a significantly more open international policy. Only after the hostile invasion and take-over of Tibet by the Chinese in 1951 the Bhutanese realised that opening up was the only way to maintain its sovereignty. As counter balance to big neighbour China Bhutan strengthened ties with India. Till date the relation between the two countries has remained very close (Department of Education, 1991).

On December 17th, 1907, the first hereditary monarch of Bhutan, Sir Ugyen Wangchuck, ascended the throne. A process of careful internal stabilisation, nation building and development started that continues till date. Until the reign of the third King, Jigme Dorji Wangchuck, the country remained in a situation comparable to that of feudal Europe during the Middle Ages. It can be attributed to this far-sighted ruler, and his son the present King Jigme Singye Wangchuck, that Bhutan started to thread the path of modernisation. They realised that, for Bhutan to maintain its sovereignty, a strong government and strong international ties were needed (Wangchuk, 1997). In 1971 Bhutan became a full member state

of the United Nations. Other international organisations were joined as well, and since then Bhutan has played a quiet but at times unique role in the international developments (Tshering, 1999).

In due course of time political reforms were put through, such as the establishment of the National Assembly with representatives of the monastic body, the government and the people in 1953. In 1959 a written codified set of laws, the Thrimzhung Chhenmo was introduced (Tshering, 1999). It was followed by a process of decentralisation of the governmental responsibilities towards the districts (dzongkhags) and further to village level, the establishment of an independent judicial system, and finally the limitation of the power of the King in favour of the National Assembly and the Council of Ministers in 1998, with the possibility of a vote of confidence being posed in the King. Although in the western sense of the word Bhutan can not be considered a democracy, in practice it functions more like it than many a democracy elsewhere.

The 781,800 people (World Bank Group, 2000) of Bhutan can be roughly divided into three ethnic groups, the Ngalong (Ngalop), of Tibeto-Mongol origin, in the Western and Central parts of the country, the Sharchop of Tibeto-Burman origin in the East and the Lhotshampa (Nepali), of Indo-Aryan origin in the South. Besides the distinct features and customs of these three broad groups they themselves can again be divided into some 20 different groups, mostly based upon the valley they live in and their means of livelihood. All these groups have separate though interrelated languages and their own cultural features (Driem, Van, 1992). With the current urbanisation trends (6.9% of the population lives in the urban centres, World Bank Group, 2000), increased mobility, decreased attachment to the places of birth and other side effects that come with development these differences are rapidly disappearing as the groups mix up through marriage. Still, cultural diversity will always remain a feature of Bhutan just as well as natural variety. The Buddhist religion (and Hinduism prevalent among the Lhotshampa) plays an important role in the daily life of the people. It comprises respect for other humans and all living creatures and acting according to generally accepted behavioural patterns (Drieglum Namzha). In general Bhutaneese are an easy-going and fun-loving people well adapted to their natural environment.

In the social field many reforms have taken place since the hereditary monarchy was established. They are an integral part of the Five Year Plans (FYPs). The abolishment of slavery, the introduction of Dzongkha as written and spoken national language and the modernisation of army and police are examples of this. Moreover the educational and health systems are undergoing continuous development, being made free of costs to all citizens, raising life expectancy from 47 in the 1960s to 66 in the 1990s and quickly reducing illiteracy, with an adult literacy rate of 46% (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2000). An equal distribution of the modernisation across the country is one of the main targets, thus raising the living standards of the entire population and curbing the urbanisation trends (Tshering, 1999, Department of Education, 1991)

1.1.2 Economy

Besides the political reforms the economy was developed as well. Agriculture, being the main source of income for the majority of the population (around 85%, Food and Agriculture Organization, 2000), has always had a high priority in the FYPs that were started in 1961. The agriculture sector contributes to nearly 50% of GDP in 1995 (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2000). The FYPs provide a five-year layout of the development plans. In the consecutive FYPs (currently the 8th) the agricultural, livestock and natural resource sectors were modernised, a national airport and roads were built connecting Bhutan with the outside world as well as connecting different valleys, providing the infrastructure for accelerated development. Moreover the nation's potential for the generation of hydropower electricity was developed, providing the means for development in other sectors as well as generating income through the export of excess energy to India. Another important source of foreign revenue is the tourism sector. Through the principle of 'low numbers high revenues' the flux of tourists is limited to a mere 6,000 well-off foreigners per year. The manufacturing and industrial sector, which are mainly natural resource-based have remained relatively small. Privatisation policies and the introduction of clean technologies are the ways the development of these sectors is stimulated. In the services sector, the Royal Government is still the largest employer (Ministry of Planning, 1996), with 13,500 civil servants (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2000).

Notwithstanding all these developments, including a growing GDP of 5.8% in 1998, (Central Statistical Organisation, 1999) and 5.9% in 1999 (Kuensel 2000c) and an increasing self-sufficiency, foreign aid remains the main means of closing the gap between government expenditures and revenues (+/- US\$ 53 million, Central Statistical Organisation, 1999). India has by far remained the main contributor to the development process, but other countries and international organisations provided technical and financial support as well.

1.1.3 Environment

Bhutan's natural environment varies from the high Himalayan ranges in the North, reaching up to 7500 meters, to the Southern foothills bordering India at about 300 meters above sea level. Between the mountain ranges are 7 main valleys following the southbound rivers. Due to the enormous geographical variety the biodiversity is impressively high, and Bhutan is considered one of the biodiversity hotspots in the world (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2000). Various factors have contributed to the preservation of this natural environment over the ages. Firstly, a deep reverence for nature and all living creatures taught by the Buddha and the local animist beliefs is the first one (National Environment Commission, 1999a). Secondly, the population of Bhutan has always remained small thus pressure on the environment was low. Thirdly, the geography of the country does not permit expansion of the agricultural area beyond 8%. The forests also provide an important back up to food security and are the main source of domestic fuel. Fourthly, the self-imposed isolation during the ages led to a way of life unaffected by the developments taking place in other countries. Lastly, the policies of the Royal Government in the past few decades have assured that, despite a growing population and mounting pressure on the natural environment, this pressure has not resulted in a dramatic decrease in its' quality or quantity (National Environmental Secretariat, 1992). As a result of these developments about 72% of the total area is currently under forest cover, with the RGOB having pledged to preserve a forest cover of at least 60% at all times.

In the global environmental field, Bhutan has played a leading role as far as taking strict measures to protect the environment are concerned. The UNCED² recommendations and those of subsequent COPs³ have resulted in an environmental document called "The Middle Path" and in the implementation of the Greenhouse Gases project. In many fields, such as sustainable energy, preservation of existing and increase of the forest cover, creating environmental awareness amongst the population and clean technologies great efforts have been made (Kucnsel, 1998a/b, 1999a/b). The results of these efforts look bright and a sustainable development of the nation is on the right track. As said before, Bhutan's path of modernisation has been, and will continue to be, very cautious. Government policies that find their roots in the system based on the rich past will, mixed with the most advantageous of the global developments, provide the guidelines for the changes seen in Bhutan (Ministry of Planning, 1996).

1.1.4 The history and Importance of Deyzo

The art of traditional papermaking is known in Bhutan as 'deyzo' (Dz. 'aDal-bZo, འདེའོ་བཟོ།

). The craft has a long history. The tsharsho production method with fine reed screens has only been recorded from Bhutan and nowhere else in the Himalayan region. This method has been in use with bamboo screens in China, Japan, northeastern India and Burma (Konishi, 1982). The cotton cloth production method is common in other parts of the Himalayan region as well and was believed to have been introduced from either Tibet or the Tawang region of Arunachal Pradesh, India, many centuries ago. The exact date of introduction and the person who introduced it have however gone lost in time. The biography of Guru Rinpoche (Guru Padmasambhava) mentions that during the eighth century AD Bhutan exported deysho to Tibet. Earlier reports, most of which have gone lost in history, indicate that small-scale production of deysho for local use can be traced back to the sixth century AD. In Tibet, not Daphne and Edgeworthia but the root of *Stella chamaejasme* (Tib. Ra-lug-ris-brgyag) was used, and the Bhutanese paper was called dugsho, 'poisonous paper', on account of the bark of Daphne containing a poison (actually an aldehyde chemical) which prevents insect attacks (Mueller and Rauig, 1982). When the British Samuel Turner visited Bhutan in 1783 AD he recorded that deysho making was a well-established tradition in Bhutan and he described deysho as the strongest paper he had ever seen (Turner, 1800).

In the past, the central government of Bhutan was the main demander for traditional paper. It was used at central and district level for printing religious texts, making statues, wrapping, and writing important documents. Beside the national demand, the deysho was also exported to Tibet. The suppliers were mostly farmers, collecting the raw material and producing the paper as a kind of taxation. Every eleven gung of every village had to pay twenty-one jama of bark as annual tax to the king in Wangduechholing, Bumthang, in case they couldn't pay twelve bctang as land tax. This way it played an important role as supplement for other elements of tax (Dorji and Zangpo, 1999).

For centuries deysho making remained a small-scale family business. After the abolishment of this kind of taxation and the development of the country deysho production has started to become a commercial venture undergoing rapid modernisation. However, small-scale production still takes place.

² United Nations Conference on Environment and Development

³ Conference of Parties

Till date the art is considered to be one of the 'zorig chusum' () or thirteen traditional crafts of Bhutan and it is for this reason that preservation of the art as part of Bhutan's cultural heritage has been given a certain importance. Especially after the developmental plans started and cheap paper was imported from India the need for active preservation and promotion of the art became apparent. As Dorji and Zangpo (1999) phrase it: *"The cosmopolitan and metropolitan outlook and behaviour of our people are posing a great threat to our culture and tradition. The technological development and industrialisation have surpassed the indigenous industries' ways of producing goods and commodities. However, an old Bhutanese saying goes that 'every Lama has his own teaching, every country has its own language and customs'. Therefore, it is our unique culture and identity that upholds the sovereign independent status of our country. Deysho making is one of those important and unique traditions that have to be saved from the clutches of westernisation, at present as well as in the future"*.

1.1.5 The Plastic Ban

In April 1999 the Minister of Trade and Industry, Royal Government of Bhutan, circulated a notification to the Heads of Ministries, Dzongkhags, Thrimkhangs, the President of the Bhutan Chamber of Commerce and Industry, the Editor of Kuensel, the Executive Director of BBS, the Thrompon of the Thimphu and Phucntsholing City Corporations, and autonomous bodies/corporations in which the plastic ban was officially announced. The ban coincided with the 25th Enthronement Anniversary of His Majesty the King.

The notification clearly expressed the reasons for the introduction of the plastic ban. With Bhutan quickly joining the rest of the world in many ways since the development programs started plastic bags became available at very low costs and because of their light and easy use they quickly replaced the traditional, easily degradable bags. Indiscriminate discarding instead of traditional and local environmentally friendly beliefs became a part of peoples' attitude resulting in environmental pollution. The following reasons were cited for the ban (Wangchuck, 1999):

- a) Pollution or disturbance of the key ecological sites considered to be the abodes of the deities could result in death, disease or famine.
- b) Plastic bags are non-biodegradable and will persist in the environment over a long period of time; bringing serious health related problems to all living beings, including humans.
- c) Discarded plastic bags seriously damage the esthetical value of the pristine environment of Bhutan.

The plastic ban was initiated by the Ministry of Trade and Industry in conjunction with the Ministry of Health and Education, the Ministry of Communications, the National Environment Commission and the Bhutan Chamber of Commerce and Industry. The ban is very specific as with regard to what is exactly banned: the use and sale of plastic carry bags, plastic doma (betelnut) wrappers and home made ice cream (popularly known as Pepsi) pouches. The ban became effective from June 2nd 1999. Traders are subject to the following penalties: a fine of Nu. 500.00 for the first offence, a fine of Nu. 1,000.00 for the second offence, and cancellation of the trade license on subsequent violation (Wangchuk, 1999). Enforcement of the ban takes place by inspectors of the Ministry of Trade and Industry.

1.2 Rationale of the Research

"The plastic ban has given hope to the manufacturers of traditional Deysho to increase their sales in the local market (Jungshi formerly sold only 10% on the local market, whereas most sheets were exported to Japan, Hong Kong, United Kingdom, Austria and the USA). They consider that paper shopping bags could replace the ousted plastic bags. For that to happen the price has to drop. Currently, sheets sell at about Nu. 8.00 to Nu. 10.00 a sheet depending on quality. If produced in large quantities the price could drop to Nu. 5.00 a sheet. Competition to the deysho paper comes from cheap and easily available paper bags and sheets from India. For many potential customers price makes the difference (Kuensel, 1999d)."

It was this quote that triggered the interest in the research subject. The ultimate aim was to find out whether, and to what extent, the substitution of the ousted plastic bags by the traditional paper had taken place, and moreover whether this actually had a positive impact on the environment. This thesis therefore intends to provide an insight in the relation between the plastic ban and deysho production, as well as their environmental and economic impacts.

During the seven-month stay in Bhutan, data were collected regarding different aspects of this issue. These data were later analysed and the results of this are provided in this report. Soon after the research was started, it became clear that the initial hopes of the deysho producers that demand for their products would increase had not materialised. This was however no major setback, as the reasons behind the fact that demand for deysho bags had not increased could now be explored. Beside this there has been little research into the actual situation of deysho production in Bhutan neither has any attempt been made to explore the effects of the plastic ban. Due to the absence of a clear link between plastic ban and deysho production, the research did more or less split into two parts: that on the plastic ban, and that on deysho production and consumption.

1.3 The Research Questions

With this research rationale taken as departure point, four research questions were formulated each referring to a distinctive part of the overall research objective. These research questions and the sub-issues that have been given specific attention in answering them are:

1. *What is the effect of the plastic ban on the environment?*
 - a) Evaluation of the plastic ban, taking ecological, economical and social criteria into account.
 - b) Estimations of the plastic use prior to and after the ban, more specifically the demand of plastics by consumers and the supply of plastics by shopkeepers.
 - c) Listing of the substitutes that have taken the place of these plastics and their percentage wise use.
 - d) What is the impact of the plastic ban on the use of deysho bags, more specifically, did the ban lead to the expected increase of the use of deysho bags?

2. *What are the environmental effects of the different deysho production methods and the paper recycling in Bhutan?*

- a) Achieving an in-depth understanding of the production processes: what machines are used, what happens in each part of the production process (see diagram I, II and III).
- b) Quantifying the amounts of inputs and outputs of the production.
- c) Look into the environmental consequences of wastewater disposal and determine where improvements can be made.
- d) Comparison between the mechanised paper production and the paper recycling on the use of raw materials and the waste resulting from the production processes.

3. *What are the effects of deysho production on the resource-base?*

- a) Estimate a growth-function for Daphne and Edgeworthia trees.
- b) Describe the effects of deysho production on the resource-base, the current situation and future prospects.
- c) Come up with recommendations regarding optimal harvest methods and conservation policies.
- d) See whether commercial plantations of Daphne and Edgeworthia are an alternative to harvesting from the wild.
- e) List other alternatives to reduce the pressure on the natural resources.
- f) Describe the effects of fuel wood consumption.
- g) Describe the effects of water consumption.

4. *What is the current situation of the deysho production in Bhutan, and what are the future prospects regarding the economic viability and sustainability?*

- a) List the producers of deysho and estimate their in-and outputs.
- b) How does consumers' reaction to the plastic ban affect the consumption of deysho, i.e. how is the current and expected future development of national demand for deysho?
- c) How is the current export position of deysho and how can it be improved?
- d) How is the situation of the rural household producers, what is the importance of their production and how can the income it generates be raised?

1.4 Short Description of the Methodology

To obtain the answers to the research questions in the preceding paragraph, several methods were used. To obtain the data, a literature review, a survey among consumers and shopkeepers, and personal communication were carried out. For analysis of the data thus acquired, several methods were used depending on the purpose of the analysis.

For the evaluation of the plastic ban, use was made of Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA). To estimate the supply of and demand for plastic before and after the introduction of the ban the data from the survey were statistically analysed and by making use of regression analysis the demand and supply functions were estimated. The use of substitutes was asked in the survey and these data were used to make an overview of their use. To analyse why deysho bags had not conquered their expected market share several reasons were explored first being the price. The price of deysho bags in the market was compared to the Willingness To Pay of the Bhutancese for these bags. This WTP was obtained through regression analysis.

The existing literature in combination with personal communication with and visits to the deysho production units and the paper recycling plant resulted in data which made an

analysis of the various deysho production methods possible. It also facilitated input-output analysis of some production processes and the environmental impacts of the production. Various investment criteria were used to judge a number of investment decisions in the paper recycling plant.

Relevant information regarding the supply of raw materials for deysho production was obtained from the work of Hadorn and Wangda (1999). Additional information on the effects on the resource base resulted from interviews with deysho producers and other concerned parties.

The research done by Hadorn and Wangda (1999) also revealed relevant data on the production in deysho units and the returns. These data were updated with information from later sources and with information provided by the deysho producers themselves. Regression analysis was used to obtain a demand function for deysho sheets. Finally, the importance of deysho production for the rural household producers was analysed by means of a profit-and-loss account.

1.5 Structure of the Text.

The remaining part of the thesis is structured as follows: Chapter 2 provides a literature review of the information regarding plastics and plastic pollution control policies from selected sources. After that the supply and demand for raw materials for deysho production are described relying heavily on the work done by Hadorn and Wangda (1999). Chapter 3 presents the methods of obtaining the data and generating the results. First the locations of study are described, followed by the means of data collection, and the methods by which these data were analysed. Chapter 4 presents the results of the analysis. It starts with the impact of the plastic ban on the environment in Bhutan; firstly the MCA of the ban, secondly its' effectiveness, thirdly the attitudes of the people regarding the ban, and lastly the substitution of plastic by other items. After this presentation follow results on the economics and environmental effects of deysho production; starting with a description of the production processes, then the supply and demand sides of deysho production, the attitudes towards deysho, the paper recycling project in Bhutan and its' prospects and finally raw material, fuel wood and water consumption and pollution in the deysho industry. Chapter 5 then discusses the results in combination with the information from other sources and comes up with recommendations. Finally, in Chapter 6 the general conclusions and recommendations of the research are given.

2 Literature Review on Plastics and Raw Material Supply and Demand

In the following paragraphs information on plastic and deysho from selected sources will be presented. Paragraph 2.1 summarises different views on plastic, its' usage, disposal, recycling, reuse and reduction and plastic pollution control measures. Paragraph 2.2 presents the results of a study on the supply of the raw materials for deysho production in Bhutan (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999). Paragraph 2.3 presents results from that same study combined with that of various others on the demand for the raw materials for deysho and the production units.

2.1 Plastics

Advantages of plastics: Together with the increased environmental awareness over the past few decades, doubts have arisen over the use of plastics. In the early days of plastic use, only the advantages were observed. During their use plastics clearly have a lot of advantages over other packaging materials. They are light, versatile and durable (American Plastics Council, 1999). Moreover they allow for hygienic packing of a wide range of products, including food products. Plastics often help product manufacturers do more with less material - which is known as resource efficiency or source reduction. Source reduction is the process by which a package or product is made using fewer resources, creating less pollution and utilising fewer potentially toxic ingredients, thus increasing the functionality and durability of a product. Resource conservation is the planned management of natural resources to optimise their utility (Cunningham and Saigo, 1997). Plastic products employ all elements of resource conservation, efficient usage in their original application, reuse, and recycling, through their entire life cycle. Plastics are derived from natural resources - typically oil and natural gas. And yet, because plastics are so efficient, their application often conserves other resources during a product's life cycle when compared to the alternatives (American Plastics Council, 1999). Effective resource conservation includes making and choosing products that minimise the energy consumed and environmental impact during production, through the life of a product, until its disposal.

Disadvantages of plastics: And it is in this disposal that plastics pose a threat to environmental quality and quantity, human and animal health and others, because they deteriorate but never decompose completely (Perman et al., 1996). This makes plastics a stock pollutant: the environment has little or no absorptive capacity and they accumulate over time as emissions enter the environment (Tietenberg 1994). The damages from the pollutant are a function of the stock of the pollutant in the environmental system at any given point in time. Thus it poses a detrimental externality to both current and future generations. Plastic pollution of the environment is an example of a classic externality: the welfare of an individual agent not only depends on his own activities, but also on activities under the control of some other agent (James, 1994). As a result of this, markets will generally produce in excess of the efficient amount of it. This implies higher than efficient damages and lower than efficient control costs (Tietenberg 1994). In an efficient situation however, the net benefit of the pollution would be maximised, in which the net benefit of the pollution is equal to the benefit of the output with which the pollution is associated minus the damages resulting from the pollution (Perman et al., 1996). Because of plastics being a stock pollutant, this net benefit has to be maximised over some relevant time horizon. Also, the way in which damages enter the problem is more complex. Summarised, equation 1.1 presents the function that has to be maximised to calculate the efficient path of pollution flows (i.e. the choice of sequence of pollution flows $Y(t)$ from $t = 0$ to infinite) over time:

$$\int_{t=0}^{t=\infty} \{B[\Psi_t] - D[\Psi_t] - D^A[Q_t]\} e^{-rt} dt \text{ subject to the constraint } dQ_t/dt = \Psi_t - \theta Q_t \quad (\text{Eq. 1.1})$$

In which $B[\Psi_t]$ is the gross benefit as a function of the flow level of pollution at a given point in time, $D[\Psi_t]$ is the damage that arises from the level of the pollution flow at a given point in time, $D^A[Q_t]$ is the damage that arises from the size of the pollution stock at a given point in time, r is the social consumption discount rate applied, and θ is the fixed proportion of the pollution stock which decays in each period. More detailed information on the economics of pollution can be found in Perman et al. (1996), Chapter 8.

Plastic disposal methods: there are various ways to dispose plastics after they have been used (Cunningham and Saigo, 1997). The first one is open dumping in a certain place together with other solid wastes collected. The second one is ocean dumping. The third one is disposal in regulated and controlled landfills. The fourth and last one is incineration. All these options have very large adverse environmental impacts, due to the difficult decomposing nature of plastics (on average plastics take 10 to 30 years to decompose, Randall Curlee, 1986). Moreover plastics can release heavy metals such as cadmium and lead into soil and groundwater (Randall Curlee, 1986). Even incineration is very harmful since upon burning they release dioxins, nitric oxides, hydrogen chloride and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs). It has to be noted however that the opinions on the environmental impact of plastic disposal vary greatly (Randall Curlee, 1986). But it would not be senseless to look at other means to limit the discard of plastics into the environment.

The three R's and plastics: The classical answer to pollution is the three R's: recycling, reuse and reduce (Cunningham and Saigo, 1997). Plastic *recycling* involves the reprocessing of discarded plastics into new, useful products (Tietenberg, 1994). Currently, technology has improved to the extent that recycling of plastics in a wide variety of products has become possible. Applications for recycled plastics are growing every day. Recycled plastics can be blended with virgin plastic (plastic that has not been processed before) without sacrificing properties in many applications. Recycled plastics are used to make polymeric timbers for use in picnic tables, fences, and outdoor toys, thus saving natural lumber. An option for plastics that are not recycled, especially those that are soiled, such as used microwave food wrap or diapers, can be a waste-to-energy system (WTE). The controlled combustion of polymers produces heat energy. The heat energy produced by the burning plastics not only can be converted to electrical energy but helps burn the wet trash that is present (American Plastics Council, 1999). However, according to Curlee (1986), the potential environmental problems resulting from plastic disposal can not be completely negated by recycling. Repeated recycling of plastics is only limited and ultimately the plastic will have to be disposed of after all, and recycling of plastic involves complicated production processes all using energy and other resources

A better alternative is cleaning and *reusing* of plastics. Plastic durability allows many products and packaging to be reused over and over again, thus saving the cost and energy of making them into something else (Cunningham and Saigo, 1997). In this case, the plastics need to have a considerable strength, size and durability, which allows their reuse.

The best option for any kind of solid waste pollution is therefore *reducing* the amount of waste generated in the first place. For example, marketing of a product is the primary reason for packing of products (Cunningham and Saigo, 1997), even before other reasons such as ease and hygiene. If consumers' reduce their use of fancy packaged products, the manufacturers will be forced to change their packaging using less plastic.

Pollution control policies: After concluding that reduction of plastic use is the best option, than how can this reduction be achieved? The market would not provide an automatic pollution reduction response, as it would do in the case of scarcity of natural resources. Whilst the cost of controlling their pollution will have to be met by the firms or households, the benefits of abatement would not be received by them but by society at large. Thus the bargaining solutions presented in the Coase Theorem will not lead to an effective outcome in the case of many externalities. Therefore some kind of government intervention is strong in the case of pollution control (Tietenberg, 1994), either to fully control the pollution behaviour of agents in the economy or to encourage internalisation of externalities in that behaviour through other means, such as for example pollution taxes and pollution abatement policies (Pernan et al., 1997)

In the search for optimal regulatory policies, a number of logic steps are generally undertaken. First the problem is identified in terms of how markets are failing. Next, an assessment of alternative mechanisms for correcting the problem is made, based on criteria such as efficiency, cost-effectiveness, flexibility and public acceptance. The alternative mechanisms may include command and control regulations such as standards or other market instruments (taxes, marketable permits). The final step would be to determine the appropriate measures for identifying conditions that would indicate when the market failure has been corrected (Haener and Luckert, 1998). According to Wehrmeyer and Mulugetta (1999) government intervention should include three fundamental principles: the *precautionary* principle, the *polluter pays* principle and the *user pays* principle. The first principle dictates that governments undertake more extensive risk assessments before authorising activity and that the acceptable risk margin be narrowed. The second and third principle mainly refer to the incorporation of environmental concerns in public decisions whereby the costs of environmental measures are internalised and reflected in the prices paid by producers for inputs and by consumers for final goods and services.

Social pressures and the limitations of information have led to a situation in which not only economic criteria such as *economic efficiency* (marginal cost-of pollution abatement equalling marginal damage of the pollutant) or *cost-effectiveness* (whichever abatement level selected should be achieved at minimum cost) should determine whether, and if so, which government policy tool should be implemented. Other criteria are (Pernan et al., 1996): *dependability* (the extent to which the instrument can be relied upon to achieve the target), *information requirements* (the amount and costs of acquiring the information), *enforceability* (the amount of monitoring required for the instrument to be effective, and the enforcement of compliance), *long-run effects* (whether the influence of the instrument changes over time), *dynamic efficiency* (the creation of continuous incentives to improve products/production processes in ways that reduce the extent of pollution for given output levels), *flexibility* (the capability of the instrument to adapt quickly and cheaply with new information, changing conditions or alteration of targets) and finally *equity* (the welfare distribution implications of a tool, i.e. income and wealth distributions among groups in society and the possibility of compensation). The weights attached to these criteria differ per type of pollution and on who judges them. This determines in turn the outcome of the instrument chosen.

For stock pollutants other criteria emerge from their nature and acute uncertainty. Pollution control programmes should be designed in such a way that stocks and flows attain steady state, sustainable outcomes. The flow of pollution into relevant environmental media should therefore be equal to the flow of pollution stock decay (Pernan et al., 1996).

Now to come to the different pollution control instruments that a government can use, there is a distinction between direct (command-and-control) instruments, and indirect, market-oriented instruments. Most strict command-and-control instrument to be used with a stock pollutant is total prohibition, supported by an effective monitoring regime and very large

penalties for non-compliance. To reduce the cost of adjustment, a gradually increasing restriction programme with at the final stage total prohibition is advocated (Perman et al., 1996). Most widely used direct control program is *emission quota* (allocation of permitted emission licenses to individual pollution sources based on their portion of the total emission in such a way that an aggregate target of pollution reduction, i.e. the steady state pollution flow level, is met). These programs have to be supported by effective pollution monitoring systems and sufficiently harsh penalties for non-compliance to assure their effectiveness and dependability. The costs and difficulties associated with gathering information on individual emissions and abatement costs are another weakness of this instrument. It results in economic inefficiency and has very weak incentives to promote dynamic efficiency.

Indirect pollution control mechanisms create economic incentives through the modification of relative prices and thus internalise the marginal damage of pollution. They include *taxes* on certain input levels, or the level of pollution discharges, and *subsidies* paid for pollution abatement. They eliminate the wedge between the private and socially efficient prices by adding an amount equal to the monetary value of the marginal pollution damage at the optimal level of pollution on each unit of pollution emitted. In the case of stock pollutants, an efficient tax rate should consist of two components: one pricing the pollution flow externality, the other the pollution stock externality. However, considering the high-risk nature of stock pollutants, certainty and dependability of the chosen control instrument become very important attributes. In that case, taxes and subsidies may be less appropriate than quantity controls (Perman et al., 1996).

2.2 Supply of Raw Materials for Deysho Production

As raw material for deysho mainly two plant species are used in Bhutan. They are collectively known as 'paper trees' (Dzalakha 'shokhu', Sh., Dz. Shoku-shing, ཤོག་ཀོ་ཤིང།).

Firstly there is Daphne (Dz. Deynâp, འདལ་ནག་ཤོ། or "black Daphne"); secondly there is

Edgeworthia (Dz. Deykâp, འདལ་དཀར་ཤོ། or "white Daphne"). Both species belong to the family Thymeleaceae. This family mainly consists of small to medium sized trees and shrubs of both temperate and tropical regions.

Photo 1: Bush of Daphne snreil (Deynâp) in Rangbikhar, Trashigang (July 2000).

The distribution of Daphne and Edgeworthia: Bhutan has five known species of Daphne and one of Edgeworthia (Table 1.1). All six species are found throughout the country, but their distribution and frequency varies- a constraint in providing a continuous supply of raw materials. Moreover there is little, if any, documentation of the species in Bhutan.

Table 1.1: Potential distribution of Daphne and Edgeworthia species in Bhutan (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999, Grierson and Long, 1991)

Botanical name	Size	Forest type	Altitude	Reported distribution
<i>Daphne bholua</i> D. Don	1-3.5m	Evergreen oak, spruce, hemlock, fir and blue pine forests	1,980-3,400m,	Chukha, Samdrup Jongkhar, Haa, Thimphu, Punakha, Trongsa
<i>Daphne sureil</i> W.W. Smith & Cave	1-2m	Warm broadleaf and evergreen oak forests	1,220-2,130m	Chukha, Samdrup Jongkhar, Pemagatshel, Punakha, Trongsa, Trashi Yangtse, Trashigang
<i>Daphne involucrata</i> Wall.	2-6m	Mixed broadleaf forests	1,200-2,000m	Chukha
<i>Daphne retusa</i> Hemsley	30-60cm	Rocky hillsides and wet ravines	3,700-4,200m	Thimphu, Bumthang
<i>Daphne ludlowii</i> Long & Rae	20-30cm	Mixed rhododendron, hemlock and spruce forests	3,350-3,580m	Endemic in Bumthang
<i>Edgeworthia gardneri</i> Wall.	2-4m	Cool laurel-dominated and evergreen oak forests	1,670-2,400m	Chukha, Trongsa, Zhemgang

Based on the available information regarding the altitude and reported districts the Geographic Information System (GIS) unit of RNR-RC Yusipang has produced a map of the potential distribution of Daphne and Edgeworthia (see Annex 1). This map shows the distribution of Daphne and Edgeworthia based on the information of height and district-wise distribution given in Table 1.1 in dark shaded and aligned area as well as the distribution based on height only in light shaded and aligned area. Numbers I to VIII give the areas where currently most exploitation takes place, namely (I) Merak-Sakten, (II) Southern Yangtse, (III) Northern Yangtse, (IV) Wamrong/Thrimshing, (V) Korila, (VI) Kheng Buli, (VII) Gedu/Takti, (VIII) Dochula. However this map cannot show the exact distribution of the examined species because of two reasons. Firstly altitude is not the only ecological condition that limits Daphne and Edgeworthia growth. Other factors such as forest type, slope location, soil condition and moisture have not been taken into account. Secondly the information is

taken from a single source and Daphne is reported to grow in other districts as well (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999).

Yield equations for Daphne and Edgeworthia were deemed necessary to be able to estimate the volume of raw materials in the field. This is important as forest resource planners and managers have to take informed decisions in issuing permits for the collection of the bark according to the Forest and Nature Conservation Act of 1995 (Kuensel, 1999f). An indication of the availability of the raw material can be obtained from information gathered during surveys by the FSD. The Forestry Services Department (FSD) issues permits and collects royalty (Nu. 0.60 per kg) for harvesting the bark and these surveys are conducted when an entrepreneur wants to establish a papermaking unit in a particular area. It gives an estimate of the availability of the raw material in that area by establishing a figure of the number of acres and by multiplying that by 20 kg of raw material per acre.

To determine the actual effect of deysho production on the Daphne and Edgeworthia resource base, following paragraphs present the results of the research conducted by the Renewable Natural Resource Research Centre (RNR-RC) Yusipang (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999). This research came up with a growth function for these plants to estimate the supply of this resource. Their work did not specifically mention the standard deviations of the parameter estimated so they could not be mentioned here either. The following method was used:

In four sites, one each in southern, western, central and eastern part of Bhutan separate samples of trees (i.e. the most commonly used and predominant of the six species, namely Edgeworthia gardneri, Daphne bholua and Daphne sureil) were collected. Predictor variables were measured and the bark was harvested. Then the bark was taken to the laboratory for dry weight determination. On the basis of the measured values and of the dry weight a bark yield equation was created. The four sites from which samples were taken are:

- Southern region: Gedu, Chukha dzongkhag, for Edgeworthia
- Western region: Dochula, Thimphu dzongkhag, for Daphne bholua
- Central region: Korila, Mongar dzongkhag, for Daphne sureil
- Eastern region: Shingchenmo, Yongphula, Trashigang dzongkhag, for Daphne sureil.

The samples all consisted of 60 randomly chosen trees but equally distributed over 10 predetermined diameter classes, so 6 in each class. For each tree/shrub the following parameters were determined: Height (h), Diameter at 10cm above ground level (D10), Diameter at 30cm above ground level (D30), number of stems (Ns) and distance to the next tree/shrub (d). Further information regarding the particular site was taken as well: the altitude, slope and aspect of slope, forest type, density of the stand for tree and shrub canopy.

Every tree within the sample was harvested by cutting the stem at 10cm above ground level and by stripping of all the bark from stems and branches thicker than 1cm. The bark of every tree was brought to the laboratory and the green weight was taken as soon as possible. It was then placed in an oven until constant weight was obtained. Then the total dry weight was measured.

After this measurements the raw data were entered in an Excel file for further processing. With the statistics software Genstat 5 different regression models were tested with the dry weight (Wd) as response variate and with explanatory variables. In total 182 different models were tested, both simple as well as multiple linear regression and both with as well as without log10 (lg) transformation of the response variate and the variables. After comparison of the different results, especially the coefficients of determination (R^2), the simple linear regression with lg(D10) as explanatory variable and lg(Wd) as response variate over the total sample was chosen:

$$\text{Log}_{10}(Wd) = -1.5918 + 2.2722 * \text{Log}_{10}(D10) \quad (\text{Eq.1.2})$$

with an R^2 of 0.952.

Which is equivalent to

$$Wd = 0.02559 * D10^{2.27221} \quad (\text{Eq.1.3})$$

Choosing different regressions for each sample would theoretically have led to a slightly more appropriate estimation of the bark yield. However it would be more difficult to define the exact regions of validity for the different equations and only one model for the whole of Bhutan would be much easier to work with in an inventory. The regression had quite good characteristics, a very narrow 95% confidence interval, and highly significant coefficients with a small standard error. Based on the yield equation a yield table was computed as well showing the estimated total dry weight depending on the diameter of the stem at 10cm above ground level in mm.

Useable bark: the amount of waste bark depends very much on the required paper quality. For high quality white paper more bark has to be removed than for lesser quality. The waste bark content also depends on the way of working of the harvesters and paper manufacturers. Therefore the yield equation chosen above only estimates the total dry bark yield of *Daphne* and *Edgeworthia*. However it is necessary to have a rough idea about how much bark can be finally used for paper production. There is a weak trend towards a bigger amount of usable bark with increasing diameter. Rough estimates suggest that in the field 25% waste bark is removed with another 25% being removed upon arrival at the producer.

Growth analysis: in order to estimate the bark yield in relation to the age the diameter with bark (D_{ab}) is required. From each sample tree a stem disc was taken at 10 cm above ground level. By measuring the growth rings the diameter without bark (D_{wb}) in relation to the age can be determined. The diameter without bark (measured on the stem disc) and the diameter with bark (measured in the field and used for the yield equation) are strongly linear correlated ($r = 0.995$). The best estimation of D_{ab} based on D_{wb} entered in mm is given by equation 1.4:

$$D_{ab} = 3.634 + 1.1406 * D_{wb} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.4})$$

Hence, the diameter with bark in relation to the age can be estimated. Applying the yield equation this will lead to an equation of bark yield and of the annual increment in relation to age. For trees a logistic growth can be assumed, but only a few *Daphne* and *Edgeworthia* trees reach the age where the growth rate begins to decrease. Because the variance in diameter of the sample trees becomes bigger with increasing age, the data (age and D_{ab}) have to be log₁₀ transformed, making variance constant and a linear regression applicable. Unlike with bark yield the rates of growth for *Daphne* and *Edgeworthia* differ a lot which makes a different examination of the growth functions necessary.

The growth of *Daphne bholua* and *Daphne surcil* depends a lot on the ecological conditions, mainly altitude, more than on the species. Therefore one single growth equation for all *Daphne* stands on north facing slopes at an altitude between 2300 and 2700m has been computed. The equations for the diameter in relation to the age are as follows:

For Edgeworthia:

$$\text{Log}_{10}(D10) = 1.1231 + 0.9609 * \text{Log}_{10}(\text{age}) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.5})$$

with an R^2 of 0.802.

For Daphne:

$$\text{Log}_{10}(D10) = 0.7742 + 0.9592 * \text{Log}_{10}(\text{age}) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.6})$$

with an R^2 of 0.894.

It can be concluded from tables and graphics computed after transforming the equations back is that Edgeworthia is much faster growing than Daphne, with a more than double growth rate. Secondly growth is nearly linear and hence the growth rate is nearly constant, decreasing only little with age. Thirdly typical sigmoid (logistical function) aspects can not be observed. Lastly the coefficient of determination for the growth function is lower than for the yield equation, due to the higher variance.

Entering the yield equation into the diameter growth functions leads to the equations for the growth of bark yield in relation to the age:

Edgeworthia:

$$\text{Log}_{10}(Wd) = 0.9616 + 2.1882 * \text{Log}_{10}(\text{age}) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.7})$$

or

$$Wd = 9.1542 * \text{age}^{2.1882} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.8})$$

Daphne:

$$\text{Log}_{10}(Wd) = 0.1712 + 2.1843 * \text{Log}_{10}(\text{age}) \quad (\text{Eq. 1.9})$$

or

$$Wd = 1.4832 * \text{age}^{2.1843} \quad (\text{Eq. 1.10})$$

Analogous to the growth of diameter, the dry bark weight of Edgeworthia is again much faster growing than of Daphne. Both species though show a big increase of the annual growth rate from year to year. The growth functions of the bark yield are useful in the future after a detailed survey has been carried out at the places where Daphne and Edgeworthia are available to establish a figure on the total resource stock on base of which harvest decisions can be taken.

2.3 Demand for Raw Materials for Deysho Production

The actual demand for the raw materials is difficult to estimate. Mainly because not all the paper manufacturers around the country are known, but also because the cottage industries do not produce the paper year round. Only a few larger units operate on a continuous basis and many factories of temporary nature are either being established or shut down. The number of temporary units may vary from year to year and the amounts produced may also vary depending on the size and number of workers available. The RNR-RC Yusipang survey among paper producers revealed their raw material consumption (table 1.2 and 1.3).

Table 1.2: Daily and annual raw material consumption for seasonal and permanent rural household production units (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999).

Production Unit (proprietor and location)	Raw material consumption per day (kg)	Raw material consumption per year (kg)
Sangay Wangdi (T/Yangtse)	10	2,600
Tashi (T/Yangtse)	11	2,860
Sonam Choda (T/Yangtse)	10	2,600
Pema (T/Yangtse)	10	2,600
Kotangla (T/Yangtse)	14	3,640
Gempo Dorji (T/Yangtse)	23	5,980
Mancla (T/Yangtse)	11	2,860
Shogpola (T/Yangtse)	10	2,600
Ugyen, Khaling (T/Gang)	30	7,800
Namgay, Yongphula, Kanglung (T/Gang)	22	5,720
Temporary units in Bomdeling (14)	56	8,400
Temporary units in Yangtse (12)	48	7,200
Total	255	54,860

Table 1.3: Daily and annual raw material consumption for the semi-mechanised units (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999).

Unit	Raw material requirement per day (kg)	Raw material requirement per year (kg)
Jungshi Paper Manufacturing Company	90	30,000
Mangala Handmade Paper House	50	15,000
Total	140	45,000

This brings the total demand from the mentioned producers on an approximate 395 kilo daily or 99,860 kilo (nearly 100 tons) yearly. Out of this 70% is made up by Daphne and the remaining 30% by Edgeworthia. In Trashhi Yangtse and Trashigang Daphne is the common raw material. The manufacturers in Thimphu use about 30% Daphne and 70% Edgeworthia.

3 Methods of Obtaining Data and Generating Results

3.1 Location of Study

A consumer and supplier survey on plastic ban and deysho was conducted in several places all over Bhutan. These are Thimphu, Phuentsholing and the Eastern part of Bhutan. These places were chosen because of their differences in history, population, means of living and attitudes towards traditional values and modern influences. Short descriptions of the three locations are provided in following paragraphs. Map 2 shows the locations of the study.

Map 2: Bhutan.

3.1.1 Thimphu

Thimphu, the capital of Bhutan, is located in the Western part of the country. It is situated in the Thimphu (or Wang) valley. Until as recent as the 1960s the fertile valley bottom near the Thim (or Wang) Chu consisted of a Dzong (Tashichhoe Dzong) and a number of small villages. After that the seat of government, until that time shared between Thimphu in summer and Punakha in winter, completely shifted to Thimphu. The town saw a fast development but thanks to careful planning the city never became a typical Third World city with all its problems. Rural-urban migration and an expanse in the civil service sector have lead to a population of between 40,000 and 45,000 divided over a total of 6,245 households (Policy and Planning Division, 1995). For a capital that is not much, but in the Bhutanese context it is by far the largest concentration of people. Most people in Thimphu have a

definite urban attitude and lifestyle, especially the younger generations, although they have never completely lost the links with the ancestral villages in their native parts of the country. These ties are gradually disappearing with every generation though, a considerable part of the current students at Thimphu schools never having been back to their home villages.

Still most people working in Thimphu are civil servants. The private sector however is experiencing a rapid expansion. The traditional large families of rural Bhutan continue to exist in Thimphu as well, although modernisation has changed the family life considerably. Couples moving out at relatively young age instead of staying with the family combined with rural influx have led to housing shortages and soaring rents. The town largely depends on imports from India for its food and fuel needs. The government provides electricity and sanitation. The capital has the largest hospital of Bhutan, the Jigme Dorji Wangchuk National Referral Hospital, and a large number of schools to cater for the education of the younger generations.

Thimphu is very much a modern city although the flavours of the past still resound in architecture and ways of living. There are a large number of shops, mainly grocery/general shops, and imported articles from India, Bangladesh, China and Thailand can be bought in a great variety. Every Friday night, Saturday and Sunday there is a 'Sabji Bazar' or vegetable market where beside vegetables all kinds of foods and other items can be bought, both local produce as well as Indian imports. The relatively large population and cheap and abundant availability of plastic from India together with low internalised environmental awareness led to many problems associated with indiscriminate discarding of plastic.

3.1.2 Phuentsholing

Phuentsholing is located in the southern dzongkhags of Chukha, approximately a six-hour drive from Thimphu. It is a town directly bordering the Indian city of Jaigaon in Jalpaiguri district, West Bengal. Phuentsholing is the main economic centre of Bhutan with major industries being located in or near the town. Moreover it is an important distribution centre from where products imported from India are sent all over the country including to Thimphu. It has a population of around 26,000, spread over some 4,000 households and consisting of people from all over Bhutan. Of all places in Bhutan, Phuentsholing together with the other border towns like Samtse, Gelephu, Sarphang and Samdrup Jongkhar have the largest foreign (mainly Indian) influence. Apart from Bhutanese in national dress and names of shops in Dzongkha there are few indications one is in Bhutan and not in India. The large non-national population of the town accentuates this, with many Indians mostly of Bengali and Nepali origin. This strong foreign influence has led to much looser ties with the home villages of most people.

Cheap availability of plastic, both from Phuentsholing as from Jaigaon, and a porous border makes the ban difficult to implement here. Degradation of the traditional value system under the influence from abroad has probably significantly reduced deysho consumption among the Bhutanese population.

3.1.3 Eastern Bhutan

Eastern Bhutan consists of 8 dzongkhags: Bumthang (sometimes together with Trongsa referred to as Central Bhutan), Lhuentse, Mongar, Zhemgang, Trashigang, Trashigang, Pemagatshel and Samdrup Jongkhar. Average travelling time by public transport from Thimphu ranges between one day (Bumthang) and four days (Trashigang and Pemagatshel). Especially Trashigang and Pemagatshel have always been relatively densely

populated districts and they still remain the parts of Bhutan with the highest population. The people in eastern Bhutan are mainly of Tibeto-Burman ancestry as opposed to the Tibeto-Mongols of western Bhutan. They speak a variety of languages and every part has its distinct cultural and historical pattern. Despite this the eastern dzongkhags have always been an integral part of Bhutan.

Life in Eastern Bhutan is still very traditional and basic. The developments that have taken place in Western Bhutan, whether the urban centres like Thimphu and Phuentsholing or the rural areas, have been much slower here. The main part of the population lives in rural areas living of subsistence farming with cash crop sale and handicraft production as major income generators. Although primary health care, education and sanitation targets have been achieved, general development levels are still considerably lower than in the West. The commission of the Kurichu Hydro Electric Project in 2002 is expected to give an impulse to the development. The past few decennia have seen a large rural-urban migration, both to local dzongkhag headquarters where small towns developed, such as Jakar (Bumthang), Mongar and Trashigang, and to Thimphu. This was fuelled by an urge to escape from harsh conditions in the rural areas facilitated by raised educational levels after which many people joined government service. People living in the small eastern towns however still have very strong links to their home villages, and even the towns themselves have a largely rural atmosphere.

Plastic comes mainly with imported products which mainly enter the market through the southeastern border town of Samdrup Jongkhar. Availability and demand for plastics have been less here than in Thimphu and Phuentsholing. Deysho is traditionally produced in many places in the East, with Trashy Yangtse being the home base of deysho production in the old fashioned way.

3.2 Data Collection

A major problem that occurred was the almost complete absence of data. On deysho some previous research was done, focusing on supply and demand (results of which are presented in Chapter 2.2 and 2.3) and on production processes and economics of deysho production in Trashy Yangtse. Regarding the plastic ban however no previous research had been done except for a few basic surveys by the Royal Society for the Protection of Nature. Thus, two different methods were adopted to get this information: a consumer and supplier survey, and personal communication with people involved.

3.2.1 Consumer and Supplier Survey

The main part of the research consisted of a survey that was done in collaboration with the Royal Society for the Protection of Nature and with the assistance of the Society's Nature Club Youth Members at various schools. The 'Survey on plastic ban and deysho' was conducted in Thimphu with a total number of 6,245 households (Policy and Planning Division, 1995) by students of Changangkha Junior High School and Yangchenphug High School, in Phuentsholing with a total number of around 3,800 households (Policy and Planning Division, 1995) in collaboration with students of the Phuentsholing Junior High School and in the East by the students of Jakar High School in Jakar town with a population of around 500 households (Policy and Planning Division, 1995), Bumthang, Trashy Yangtse Junior High School in the proposed town of Chorten Kora with a population of around 400 households (Policy and Planning Division, 1995) and in Trashigang town, population around 1,000 households (Policy and Planning Division, 1995) by students of Trashigang Junior High School.

The questions asked are included in annex. It has to be noted that because the survey questions had to be translated from English to local languages by the students and therefore the questions are very easily formulated. Moreover, because the questions were also asked to villagers a certain way of formulating the questions and possible answers had to be taken into account to achieve the required type of answers. However, personal interviews by students were preferred as a personal interview will yield the most reliable data (Peiman, 1996). High costs and time consumption were avoided by execution of the survey by students. For these reasons a standard format of making a survey form could not be used, although some widely accepted rules were applied. The survey was clearly divided in three parts: questions regarding the plastic ban including questions that would give indications on environmental awareness, questions on deysho, questions on substitution of plastics and willingness to pay for deysho bags, and personal data of the interviewed such as age and income which were asked at last. Questions that were also used by the RSPN in previous surveys were adapted and included. Questions were almost all structured instead of open-ended to obtain reliable responses. The questions are included in Annex 3.

3.2.2 Personal Communication

The lack of available data on issues related to deysho production and the plastic ban had to be compensated by a lot of personal communication with people involved as well as personal observations and ideas by the Bhutanese population.

Regarding the plastic ban information was obtained from Mr. Miraj Pradhan, Communications Officer of the Royal Society for Protection of Nature, Mr. Tshering Phuntsho, Town Planner of the Thimphu City Corporation, Mr. Karma C. Nyedrup, Head of the Environmental Impact Assessment Division of the National Environment Commission, and Mr. Chhimi Dorji, Industries Officer, Industries Licensing and Implementation Sector of the Ministry of Trade and Industry.

In Thimphu there are two deysho producers who mainly produce for the export market and who produce a great variety of products. Jungshi Handmade Paper (JHP) factory is by far the largest in the country and works according to a semi-mechanised production process, whereas Mangala Handmade Paper House follows a slightly more traditional production method. On a 45-minute drive from Thimphu, in the industrial estate in Bjemina village, the paper recycling plant that is owned by Jungshi Handmade Paper factory is located. These three units were visited and the owners and operators of the units (Mr. Norbu Tenzin of JHP and the recycling plant and Mrs. Kesang Eudon) were questioned.

In Trashigang and Yongphula (Trashigang) deysho producers were visited and interviewed despite the fact that the production was stopped during the agricultural high season. More information and a few reports on the household level production in the East were obtained from two Sherubtse College ex-students, Mr. Tshering Dorji (currently employed at Bhutan Broadcasting Service) and Mr. Sherab (currently working in Nature Conservation Division, Ministry of Agriculture). The previous sites of deysho production in Dekiling, Bumthang, and Kuri Zampa, Mongar, were visited and the producers were interviewed and asked for the reasons why they had suspended production. Mr. Pema Wangda, Regional Natural Resource-Research Centre, Yusipang gave information and a detailed report on supply and demand for the Daphne and Edgeworthia. The project manager of the new deysho project in Zhemgang funded by Save the Children USA/Stichting Nederlandse Vrijwilligers (SNV) Bhutan, Mr. Dorji Wangdi, was interviewed by phone. The Secretary of the National Women's Association of Bhutan (NWAB) Dasho (Mrs.) Dawa Dem was interviewed regarding the restart of the Kuri Zampa deysho unit in Gyelpozhing, Mongar. Finally, friends from different walks of life contributed their valuable opinions.

3.3 Analytical Methods

3.3.1 Evaluation of the Plastic Ban as Environmental Policy Measure

To analyse the effects of the plastic ban, first the decision to actually implement the plastic ban has to be reviewed. Although the ban was a decision by the RGOB that has already taken place, it would be useful to see whether other options wouldn't have provided a better alternative. The reader has to keep in mind however that this is an ex-post review.

Environmental impacts of human activities for as far as they are negatively valued (in themselves, or in their consequences) are said to lead to environmental damage or loss of environmental quality. Environmental policies aim to prevent and reduce such damage by improving environmental quality relative to the situation without such policy, and thereby leads to environmental benefits (Kuik et al., 1992).

The economic benefit of an environmental policy measure is the value of improvements to natural and man-made environments resulting from this measure. Ideally, this value is the sum of the values assigned to improvements by all individuals directly or indirectly affected. If expressed in monetary terms, they are referred to as Willingness To Pay (WTP), or the amount of money a person would be willing to give up to obtain an improvement and still be as well off as with his previous entitlement or alternatively Willingness To Accept (WTA), the monetary compensation required to induce people to voluntarily refrain from an improvement or accept a deterioration. However, three problems were occurred when trying to evaluate an environmental policy measure. These problems are linked to the nature of environmental problems: environmental costs are not adequately priced, the problems appear at a distance in both time and place, and they occur in systems that are insufficiently understood (Janssen, 1991).

The purpose of benefit assessment ultimately lies in the evaluation of alternative policies, programmes, regulations or projects. The assessment models of the different alternatives includes the following functions (Kuik et al., 1992):

- To order and structure the information with respect to the alternatives
- To reduce the number of alternatives
- To rank the alternatives
- To establish the net gain in social welfare of the alternatives if the pros and cons to the alternatives can be measured in money terms

For the first three functions, the effects can be measured qualitatively or quantitatively in physical units. Ideally, *Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA)* is used to rank the alternatives and calculate each alternative's net gains to social welfare. This implies however that the pros and cons of the alternatives can be measured in money terms. Valuing the impact of a certain environmental policy measure is often unreliable and not meaningful. In this particular case, no information is available regarding the valuation of the negative and positive impact of the plastic ban. Within the limited timeframe of the study neither was it possible to establish these. Therefore another method had to be applied to evaluate the ban: *Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA)*.

Multi-Criteria methods are characterised by the fact that different, explicit criteria are used to evaluate the alternatives. The method also takes into account that some criteria may weigh more heavily on the decision than others. Explicit weights must be given to the various criteria. The weights can express the preferences of any person or group involved in the process. Therefore the ranking of the alternatives is conditional upon the preferences of the

person or group from whom the weights have been derived (Kuik et al., 1992). A *Multi-Objective Decision Support System (MODDS)* was used to weigh the advantages and disadvantages of the plastic ban and other alternatives and thus try to come to a judgement as to whether this was a good choice of policy tool or not. It consists of two modules: a prediction module and an evaluation module. The first module aims to predict results of an environmental policy measure, and the second to evaluate the possible alternatives and to recommend certain actions (Beinat, 1992).

The first phase of the prediction module is to offer a description of the environmental pollution, its intrinsic characters and the quantitative and qualitative effects on environment, society and economics. Beside that, a selection of potentially suitable alternatives is made in order to concentrate on feasible remedial actions. The main step of the prediction module consists of predicting the results of a policy tool. These results are included in a table called *Effects Table*. In the Effects Table, remedial activities are evaluated according to a set of criteria selected in order to represent the performances of every alternative. Feasible alternatives are evaluated according to these criteria and the prediction module provides data to fill in the Effects Table (Janssen, 1991, Beinat, 1992).

This Table is the starting point for the evaluation module, which results in the selection or recommendation of the remedial technique. To compare the alternatives it is necessary to consider all the performances in a way that consist of several parts, the aggregate of which will give a total picture of the results of each chosen alternative. In this phase, it is very useful to separate monetary and non-monetary aspects of each alternative. This can be achieved by defining two indices: the *effectiveness index* and the *efficiency index* (Beinat, 1992). Effectiveness combines in a single value all the non-monetary aspects of each alternative. The best alternative is given the highest effectiveness score, which is measured on a scale from 0 to 100. Efficiency is, for each alternative, the ratio between the effectiveness index and the cost of the alternative. To calculate the effectiveness index, a unified unit of measure is needed. A solution to this is the normalisation of the effects in a common scale. Therefore, for all non-monetary effects a function called the *value function* is required, which translates the scores of the Effects Table (physical data) into other scores, called *value scores*. In general, for every criterion in the Effects Table it is necessary to know the relative value function (Beinat, 1992). In the Effects Table, a single alternative corresponds to a column of criteria scores.

Multicriteria value theory is based on the assumption that there exists a multicriteria value function $v(\cdot)$ which translates all the scores of alternative A_i (i.e. a column of criteria scores x_i for each criteria X_i , or (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) , with x_i^* being the best score and x_i^* being the worst score, which define criterion ranges R_i such that $R_i = [x_i^*, x_i^*]$ and $x_i \in R_i, i=1, \dots, n$) into real numbers representing the preference of the alternative. The multicriteria value function is then defined as $v(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in [0, 100]$. The value $v=0$ is given to the worst score combination, $v(x_i^*, \dots, x_i^*)=0$ being the worst alternative. Likewise, the value $v=100$ to the best score combination, with $v(x_i^*, \dots, x_i^*)=100$ being the best possible alternative considered (Beinat, 1992). Every criterion score is thus translated into a value included in the range between 0 and 100. However, this scale is common to every criterion, regardless of their priority.

In reality, not all the evaluation criteria are equally important and this has to be considered in aggregating the performances of the alternatives (Janssen, 1991). Therefore, priorities are represented in *criterion weights* (w_i) that have a specific value for different individuals. With this set of weights certain criteria can be emphasised and the alternative performing best in this criteria will score the highest effectiveness index. This effectiveness index is calculated by aggregating value scores, mostly by using a weighed summation, although Janssen (1991) described other solutions as well.

This aggregation is represented as:

$v(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{i=1, \dots, n} w_i * v_i(x_i)$. This way the alternatives can be ranked according to their aggregate effectiveness indices.

In the particular case of evaluating the plastic ban, the situation with immediate total plastic ban was compared to a situation without plastic ban, a ban on single-use plastics, a gradual introduction of a total plastic ban, a plastic disposal system and a recycling scheme for plastics as the alternatives. Different criteria, economic, social, and environmental, were defined. Due to lack of data, there were no monetary criteria. Thus only an effectiveness index could be calculated. Because there were no quantitative data either, it proved impossible to establish value functions. The criteria of each alternative were therefore ranked on an ordinal scale from 0 to 100 on basis of expected value. The alternative expected to score worst on the criterion was given value 0, and the alternative expected to score best on the criterion was given value 100. The other alternatives were assigned score values between this 0 and 100. The criterion weights were chosen as per personal preference. Then the effectiveness index was calculated for each alternative.

3.3.2 Bid Curves for Deysho Bags

In order to evaluate the deysho producers' initial expectation of being able to sell more deysho bags to replace the ousted plastic bags, the maximum WTP of both consumers and producers was asked for starting to use deysho bags and bidcurves for these bags were established.

The WTP for a marketable good is the total area under the demand curve of the good. It consists of the monetary transaction volume and the consumer surplus at a given equilibrium price. In this study the WTP is not defined exactly similar as the WTP used in studies for valuing environmental goods. Here it is the maximum amount that people are willing to pay for deysho bags, i.e. the maximum amount of money that deysho bags may cost such that people will start their use. However, due to the similarities with the WTP of environmental valuation methods the same theoretical background and method was applied here. Of the various valuation methods the Contingent Valuation Method was chosen. The method was executed according to Hanley and Spash (1993).

The hypothetical market, with consumers and shopkeepers from three different regions of Bhutan, was discussed in paragraph 3.1. The maximum WTP was asked as an open-ended question. Firstly the respondents were given the choice whether or not they would be willing to use deysho bags. If they were not willing to do this, a maximum WTP of Nu. 0/- was noted. If they answered yes, they were asked which amount they were maximally WTP, with as lower boundary Nu. 1/- and as upper boundary Nu. 50/-. After the survey was conducted, three bidcurves were estimated with single-equation multiple linear regression modelling in SPSS 9.0, one for consumers, one for shopkeepers, and one for the total. In these bidcurves, the WTP was related to different independent variables that were asked in the survey. The total function combined the two separate ones and therefore certain variables that were used in those separate functions (i.e. HHS, INS and STY) were omitted in the total bidcurves. In each model tested, a number of 'outlying' observations with a standard deviation larger than twice the mean were removed to account for possible wrong observations due to the way the questions were formulated, and possible protest bids and outlying bids. With respect to the variables, DDB, HHS, INC, INS and AGE were quantitative data on a nominal scale. OPD, EDU and PLA were qualitative data that were transformed quantitatively to an ordinal scale by ranking them (OPD and PLA from high to low, EDU from low to high). PSS contained qualitative data on an ordinal scale.

In the single-equation multiple regression class of models the variable under study is explained by a single, linear or non-linear function of a number of independent explanatory variables. In mathematical form this model is written as:

$$Y_i = \beta_1 + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \beta_3 X_{3i} + \dots + \beta_k X_{ki} + \varepsilon_i \quad (\text{Eq. 2.1})$$

Where Y is the dependent variable, the X's are the independent variables, and ε is the error term. β_1 is the constant term or intercept of the equation. The assumptions underlying the multiple regression model are the following:

1. The relationship between Y and X is linear as given in Eq. 2.1;
2. The X's are nonstochastic variables. In addition, no exact linear relationship exists between two or more independent variables
3. The error has zero expected value for all observations
4. The error term has constant variance for all observations
5. Errors corresponding to different observations are independent and therefore uncorrelated
6. The error term is normally distributed.

SPSS version 9.0 was used to estimate the parameters which minimise the error sum of squares through the least-squares procedure, or:

$$ESS = \sum \varepsilon_i^2 = \sum (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2 \text{ where } \hat{Y}_i = \beta_1 + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \beta_3 X_{3i} + \dots + \beta_k X_{ki} \quad (\text{Eq. 2.2})$$

SPSS then came up with values of $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_k$ minimising ESS. These coefficients measure the change in Y associated with a unit change in their accompanying X's on the assumption that the other X variables are held constant. R^2 measures the proportion of variation in Y explained by the multiple regression equation. R^2_{adj} accounts for the degrees of freedom of the model. The higher the R^2 the better the model estimates the reality. The F statistic tests $H_0 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = \dots = \beta_k = 0$, or all of the coefficients are equal to 0 which makes the model useless. It takes the degrees of freedom into account, or the total number of observation minus the number of independent variables. If $F_{model} > F_{(N, n-k)}$ from the table then H_0 is rejected. The t-statistic tests $H_0 = \beta_k = 0$. If $t_{model} > t_{(N, \alpha)}$ from the table then H_0 is rejected and the coefficient is significant. In all cases a 95% confidence interval was applied ($\alpha = 0.05$). For further elaboration on the mathematical background of single-equation multiple regression models reader is referred to Pindyck and Rubinfeld (1998) Chapter 2 and 4.

Independent variables with a t-statistic highly insignificant were removed until the model had the highest possible R^2 with as many significant variables as possible. This resulted in the best fitting curves. Means and medians were calculated. This resulted in indications of the factors that influence people's bid for deysho bags. Moreover it provided with an indication of at which price deysho bags should be sold for the Bhutanese public to start using them.

After this, attempts were made to aggregate the mean bids to the national level. This proved to be impossible however. Ideally, one would use national values obtained from a nation-wide survey done for other purposes and enter the relevant variables into the estimated bid curve. This would lead to an estimated population mean bid, μ , which could be multiplied by N to get the national aggregate (Hanley and Spash, 1993). However, national means regarding data like educational level, opinion on deysho and price of substitutes are unavailable in Bhutan. Therefore this option was not possible, and as second best option the means which resulted from running the regression with the available data were used.

3.3.3 National Demand for Deysho

The method described in paragraph 3.3.2 was also used to establish a demand curve for deysho. In this case, the relevant population consisted of the consumers of deysho. They were asked which deysho products they use and in what amounts. A conversion factor was applied to transform the deysho products to rough sheets. Thus DDE became a quantitative dataset on a nominal scale. The same holds for INC, HHS and AGE. OPD, EDU and PLA were qualitative data that were transformed to an ordinal scale by ranking them (OPD and PLA from high to low, EDU from low to high). PDE contained quantitative data on an ordinal scale.

An expected bidcurve was established with different independent variables thought to influence the demand for deysho. SPSS 9.0 was used to estimate the bidcurve. The applied method and interpretation of the result are similar as described under paragraph 3.3.2. Again, population values for the relevant variables were not available. However, to get a mere indication of total national demand for deysho, the mean was multiplied by the number of households in Thimphu, Phucntsholing, Jakar, Chorten Kora and Trashigang. This method of aggregation was considered superior over multiplying by the total number of households in Bhutan, since these towns are some of the main deysho consumers in Bhutan. Moreover the surveyed area did not include the other regions of Bhutan. However the resulting figure is just a mere indication of demand for deysho. Religious institutions and the RGOB, other consumers of deysho, have not been included in the survey.

3.3.4 Supply and Demand Curves for Plastic Bags

The method of obtaining parameter estimates and a regression curve as described in paragraph 3.3.2 was also applied to another set of data that had been obtained through the survey. Least-square estimation was used to estimate the demand and supply curves of plastics in Bhutan prior to and after the introduction of the ban. Using the same method and statistical interpretation as described in 3.3.2, two demand and two supply curves were estimated. The data obtained from shopkeepers on their daily distribution of plastics was used to estimate the supply curves, whereas data obtained from consumers were used to estimate the demand curves. Population values for the relevant variables were not available. However, to get a mere indication of total national demand for plastic, the mean was multiplied by the total number of households in Thimphu, Phucntsholing, Jakar, Chorten Kora and Trashigang. This method of aggregation was considered superior over multiplying by the total number of households in Bhutan, since these towns are some of the main plastic consumers in Bhutan, with village households consuming much less. Moreover the surveyed area did not include the other regions of Bhutan. However the resulting figure is just a mere indication of plastic demand. The mean of the estimated supply curve for plastic was multiplied by the total number of shops in Bhutan to estimate the total supply of plastics, since the total number of shops in the different regions was unavailable.

Regarding the variables, INS, AGE, INT and HHS were quantitative data on a nominal scale. SPL, SPLI, DPL and DPLI were quantitative data on a classified ordinal scale. These data were transformed by taking the mean of each class as this would facilitate their use and increase their meaningfulness. ENV, KNB and EFB were qualitative data on a binary scale for which dummy's were introduced. EDU, OPB, STY, PLA, were qualitative data that were transformed to an ordinal scale by ranking them (OPD, STY and PLA from high to low, EDU from low to high). PSS and PPL contained quantitative data on an ordinal scale.

In a proper demand and supply model for a certain good or service demand and supply would have been equalled to obtain the estimated regression curve. However, in this case the demand could not be set equal to the supply unless difficult transformations and assumptions were made. For example, how to treat reuse of plastics, direct import from abroad, etc.

3.3.5 Input-Output Analysis and Environmental Impact of Deysho Production Processes

An input-output analysis of the deysho production processes provided a better insight and overview of the total use of raw materials and waste. Diagrams were constructed showing the different steps in the production process and the in- and outputs per step. Where ever possible these in- and outputs were quantified as well. After this recommendations could be formulated to decrease the raw material usage and decrease wastage.

Currently, Bhutan has no environmental assessment procedures specifically aimed at the deysho production units. The deysho production is largely small-scale production with consequently small environmental effects. Focus of environmental assessment has been on others sectors such as new and existing industries (cement manufacturing, food processing, textile industries, distilleries, fibre board production and electric arc furnaces, National Environment Commission, 1999e), hydropower, power transmission lines, highways and roads, mining and mineral processing (National Environment Commission, 1999a) and forestry (National Environment Commission, 1999c). However, especially the larger scale semi-mechanised production has considerable impacts on the environment, both from raw material use (bark and firewood) and waste water discharge. Even in the small-scale rural household production the implications of raw material use are considerable.

By reviewing the in-and outputs of deysho production and comparing them with the standards from other sectors the environmental impact of deysho production has been analysed and recommendations have been put up.

3.3.6 Financial Analysis of a Rural Household Producer

Information regarding in and output of deysho producers was very difficult to obtain. The rural household producers hardly keep any track of their inputs and output. Moreover their production is highly variable over the years and seasons. Production levels and prices might vary from location to location and from season to season. But even the larger-scale producers in Thimphu produce such a wide variety of products mostly on order. They hardly keep track of their costs and benefits. However with the available information and assumptions regarding the others a cost-benefit analysis of a rural household producer in Trashigang was made.

For the financial analyses, a categorical profit and loss account was constructed on basis of the model in Epe and Koetzler (1996) which in turn was derived from legal Dutch requirements to accounting. This was done in absence of detailed information on a Bhutanese system. The model is however an internationally much applied one. In a categorical profit and loss account the revenues and costs are represented on basis of production.

3.3.7 Investment Decision in the Paper Recycling Plant

The Paper Recycling Plant in Bjemina, owned by Mr. Norbu Tenzin of Jungshi Handmade Paper, is currently not operating as paper recycling plant. Raw materials are made into deysho sheets in a mechanised process that was supposed to be the paper recycling process. According to the owner, the lack of demand for the recycled paper has caused the recycling operations to cease. He is of the opinion however, that a number of investments could bring the process back on track. These investments would both increase production as well as reduce production costs. Beside this, he has also plans of making the production more environmentally friendly by additional investments. Since a proper analysis has not been executed by the owner and therefore this report will provide a brief look into the decision.

Capital budgeting is a means to establish whether an investment is economically viable and if so, which investment has the preference based on expected profits. Firstly, the investment amount has to be established clearly, taking investments in fixed assets as well as additional investments in liquid assets into account. Secondly, the expected benefits of the production resulting from the investment have to be estimated as realistically as possible. After the costs and benefits of the investment have been established, there are several criteria on basis of which the investment can be judged (Blommaert et al., 1993, Bruins and Pinske, 1996):

- The *payback period*, defined as the initial investment divided by the expected net benefits per year,
- The *average return on investment*, defined as the average yearly net benefits minus the yearly depreciation of the investment (which is equal to the total investment divided by the expected economic operating life of the investment); or average net profits; divided by half of the total amount of the investment (average invested amount).
- The *net present value method*, in which the present values of the future net cash flows are deducted from the invested amount. This method requires a discount rate. A positive net present value at a certain discount rate means that the investment can be economically accepted.
- The *internal rate of return*, defined as the discount rate at which the net present value of the project is nil. The discount rate in cases of long-term investments can be taken as the reciprocal of the payback period.

All four criteria were used making assumptions on the expected benefits of the investments. For the production capacity increasing investments assumptions were made on increased sheet production and decreased costs per sheet for recycled paper. For the environmentally friendlier investments reduction in water and fuel wood costs were taken as main investment benefits. These investments have social benefits as well, such as cleaner water and less usage of wood.

4 Results

4.1 The Impact of the Plastic Ban on the Environment in Bhutan

4.1.1 Multi Criteria Analysis of the Plastic Ban

Although the plastic ban was a decision by the RGOB that came into effect as per June 2nd 1999, it would be useful to see whether other options wouldn't have provided a better alternative to reduce the harmful effects of plastic use in Bhutan. To this end an effects table was constructed in which various alternative policy measures were evaluated. The effects table was based on the MODDS method described in Paragraph 3.3.1. A total of 6 different alternatives were formulated:

- **A1: no plastic ban or other measures** (the initial situation). This option changes nothing to a situation in which plastics are used and discarded after use.
- **A2: a total immediate plastic ban** (the current situation). This alternative is best from environmental point of view. However, fines have to be high and enforcement has to be strict enough to enforce compliance. The costs and problems associated with finding alternatives for plastic are high in this option.
- **A3: a gradual implementation of total plastic ban**, this alternative is equal to A2, with as major difference that the ban would be gradually implemented over a certain time-span to allow for adjustments to be made in consumer behaviour. It would allow time for awareness campaigns and give the public sufficient time to find substitutes. A time-span of 3 to 5 years would probably suffice. A step-wise reduction in plastic use, e.g. first the banning of thin, single-use plastics and in a later stage banning of lasting, reusable plastics has to take place and be enforced.
- **A4: a ban on the use of thin, single-use plastics**. Considering that thin, single-use plastics constitute the major part of plastic waste due to their short durability and small reuse properties, a ban of these plastics would mean a considerable decrease in plastic waste. At the same time, lasting, re-usable plastics would be allowed for convenience of the public.
- **A5: a deposit system on plastics**. This system will imply that consumers pay a surcharge on plastics they obtain from shopkeepers, which will be returned when they hand the plastics back to shopkeepers. Systems of this kind are in use in many developed countries with plastic and glass bottles and other durable packaging materials. The surcharge has to be high enough for people to be stimulated to return the plastics. Awareness campaigns have to be focused at informing the public on the advantages of the system and the financial benefits of returning plastics. The plastics have to be cleaned and returned or cleaned after return to make them suitable for re-use. In this system, the thin, single-use plastics will be difficult to reuse and therefore it is questionable whether this is feasible. Many other practical difficulties exist. Moreover, the system will be income-sensitive: consumers with high incomes will be easily tempted to discard the plastics as they can more easily afford to pay the surcharge whereas low-income consumers might have to use plastic substitutes to avoid the surcharge.
- **A6: the introduction of plastic recycling schemes**. This alternative is currently not possible in Bhutan since no plastic recycling plants exist. Due to the high costs of such a plant compared to the (economical) benefits its' establishment is doubtful. Consequently, the plastics have to be collected and transported to India, where the Jan Seva Ashram, a Non-Governmental Organisation (NGO) in Himachal Pradesh recycles plastics (RSPN, 1999). This implies very high transportation costs. High costs will also be associated with plastic

separation and collection. It is questionable whether the majority of the plastics can be thus collected or whether they will end up being dumped after all (Curlcc, 1986). Being an end-of-pipe solution, it is not preferable as compared to the source-reduction alternatives A1 to A6.

After defining the alternatives a set of criteria was established as comprehensively as possible. Consequently, every criteria was given a weight and every criteria was given a value from 0 to 100 for each alternative keeping the characteristics of the alternative as mentioned above in mind. Finally, the total effectiveness index for each alternative was calculated by using an Excel 5.0 Spreadsheet. Regarding the assignment of values to the different criteria, following arguments determined these criterion values per alternative:

1a/b, 2d, 3d/e) A total ban will result in a total stop of plastics ending up in the natural environment and thus decrease the pollution of the water and soil and health risks in animals in humans. Therefore the decrease in medical costs associated to these health risks will also show the highest decrease. A gradual implementation of a total ban will see a slower decrease, as the plastic flow into the environment will remain for some time. The ban on thin, single use plastics will stop these plastics from ending up in the environment but other plastic items will still be available and cause pollution and health risks. The effect of the deposit system and the recycling schemes is estimated to be ambiguous since it is doubtful whether they can be easily implemented, the pollution associated with cleaning the returned plastics and recycling and pollution resulting from transportation. Lastly no measures will change nothing to the current situation and therefore lead to no decrease in these criteria at all.

2a) In case of a total ban, there will be no need to buy (and thus import) plastics if the ban is adhered to, and thus the reduction in costs of plastics will be maximal. In case of gradual implementation of the ban, the costs will finally be minimal but only after some time. Since thin, single use plastics are the cheapest kind, the reduction in the cost of plastics will be less in the case of a ban on these plastics since the more expensive strong plastics will still be bought. In the case of a deposit system, not all plastics will be returned. Mainly thin, single use plastics will be discarded and bought anew thus the reduction in plastic costs will be ambiguous. If a recycling scheme were implemented, plastics would continue to be bought new. If no measures were taken, the reduction in costs of plastics would be minimal.

2b) With a total ban the costs associated with innovating, making, using and buying plastic substitutes would be maximal since plastics would no longer be allowed. In the case of a gradual implementation there would be a certain time to do this. In case of a thin, single use ban only substitutes replacing this kind of plastics have to be used reducing the costs. In case of a deposit system these costs are considered to be even lower and in case of recycling schemes all kinds of plastics can still be used and only limited substitutes have to be found. With no measures the costs associated with plastic substitutes will be least.

2c) With a total ban no plastics have to be disposed. In case of gradual implementation the disposal costs will lower to 0 in a certain time span. If recycling schemes are implemented only very few plastics will have to be disposed, as the majority will be recycled. Similarly, in case of a deposit system most plastics will be reused although there is an end to reuse after which the plastics will be disposed anyhow. With a thin, single use ban only the stronger plastics, constituting smallest part of the total plastic volume, will have to be disposed thus at lower costs. In case of no ban there will be no reduction in the volume of plastics disposed and thus the costs.

2e) In case of total ban there would be no plastic litter. There would be somewhat more in the first period of a gradual implementation but this would decrease with time. If people adhere to recycling schemes they will also lead to considerable less littering. With a deposit system there would probably a bit more littering since not all plastics can be reused

neither can they be reused till infinity. Although thin, single use plastics would be banned the durable ones would still be littered. In case of no measures, the plastic littering would be maximal.

2f) If there would be a total ban there would be no costs associated with transportation of plastics. With a gradual implementation these costs would gradually decrease to 0. With a deposit system the plastics would only have to be collected and transported to the reuse centre and back to the shops. The transportation from consumer to supplier would be done by consumers themselves. In case of thin, single use ban only the reusable plastics have to be transported to the disposal site. Due to the fact that there is no plastic recycling centre in Bhutan itself the plastics would have to be transported to India with high costs associated with it. In case of no measures plastics have to be transported from the collection point to the disposal site.

2g) This criteria has same scores as criteria 2f) with as only difference that the costs associated with collecting the plastics in case of no measures would be maximal.

2h) In case of no measures, total ban, gradual implementation of total ban and thin, single use ban there would be no costs of reuse or recycling. The costs of reuse would be a bit higher whereas the costs of recycling would be maximal.

2i) If no measures are taken there would be no costs of enforcement. The costs with a total ban would be maximal since it is most difficult to check. The costs with a gradual implementation would be slightly lower and expected to be equal to the enforcement costs in case of a thin, single use ban. A deposit system would require some kind of enforcement to make sure people follow the system. Recycling schemes would imply low enforcement costs as the plastics could be separated from the other waste at any time.

2j) A total ban and gradual implementation of total ban would mean high costs associated with creating awareness among the people, for example why it is introduced, what are the fines, and what is banned. The deposit system would also require a lot of awareness campaigns to explain how it works. The thin, single use ban would imply lower costs, and in case of no measures and recycling schemes the costs would be minimal.

3a) In case of total ban no plastics can be used for shopping implying highest reduction of utility. In case of gradual implementation there would be a certain time span in which plastics can still be used. With a thin, single use ban the thicker plastics can still be used. With a deposit system all plastics can still be used but they might be dirty or otherwise unfit for use. In case of recycling schemes and no measures all kinds of plastics would still be available and there would be no reduction in shopping utility.

3b) The deposit system would be associated with high trouble for having to return the plastics to their source. In the other alternatives this would not be the case.

3c) In case of total ban former plastic users will be forced to look for alternatives. In case of gradual implementation of the ban there would be time to do this. With a thin, single use ban only substitutes for the thin, single use plastics have to be thought of. With a deposit system in some cases plastics would no longer suffice but in general there would be little need for alternatives. In case of recycling schemes and no measures all plastics could still be used.

Regarding the criteria weights, most importance was given to economic criteria since they constitute most different criteria. The criteria 2a and b) were given most weight since they imply costs for the people whereas the other criteria imply costs for the government. The reduction of existing costs was valued less than the introduction of new costs with a certain alternative. The social effects were valued quite high individually because of Bhutan's importance given to the society. There were only two environmental effect criteria and they were also valued high. When summing over the different environmental, social and economic criteria, decreased health risks and costs and pollution/decreased esthetical value of

the landscape were valued high with 0.25 and 0.13. Decreased costs of substitutes and searching for them also scored high with 0.16.

Table 2.1: Effects Table

Criterion	Weight	A1: no measures	A2: total ban	A3: gradual total ban	A4: ban on thin plastics	A5: deposit system	A6: recycling schemes
1. Environmental effect criteria	0.18						
a) Decreased health risks in humans, livestock and wildlife	0.10	0	100	90	70	50	50
b) Decreased pollution of water and soil	0.08	0	100	90	70	50	50
2. Economic effect criteria	0.49						
a) Reduced costs of plastics	0.08	0	100	90	40	50	10
b) Reduced costs of plastic substitutes	0.10	100	0	10	40	60	90
c) Reduced disposal costs	0.03	0	100	90	70	80	90
d) Reduced medical costs of adverse health effects in humans and livestock	0.05	0	100	90	70	50	50
e) Reduced costs of collecting litter	0.03	0	100	90	50	80	90
f) Reduced costs of plastic transportation	0.03	70	100	90	60	90	10
g) Reduced costs of collecting plastics	0.03	0	100	90	60	90	10
h) Reduced costs of reuse/recycling	0.05	100	100	100	100	30	0
i) Reduced costs of enforcement	0.06	100	0	20	20	40	90
j) Reduced introduction- and awareness costs	0.03	100	0	0	80	20	100
3. Social effects	0.33						
a) Reduced shopping utility and convenience	0.10	100	10	20	40	70	100
b) Reduced trouble of returning used plastics	0.02	100	100	100	100	0	100
c) Decreased searching for substitutes	0.06	100	0	30	70	80	100
d) Decreased esthetical value of landscape	0.05	0	100	90	70	50	50
e) Decreased health risks	0.10	0	100	90	70	50	50
4. Effectiveness index		44.1	66.0	65.2	59.8	55.5	59.4

From this effects table the total ranking $A2 > A3 > A4 > A6 > A5 > A1$ results on basis of the effectiveness indices. With the chosen criteria scores and weights the plastic ban as initiated by the RGOB turns out to be the best policy measure, closely followed by a gradual implementation of the ban. Another high score is obtained by the banning of thin, single-use plastics only. Plastic recycling schemes have a surprising 4th position. This alternative is unfortunately in practice difficult to realise. The absence of a ban scores worst as could be expected in this example.

It should be clear however that with different preferences of decision-makers' and more detailed information on the actual value scores of each criterion under the various alternatives, the result could change completely. If it is, merely for exercise of the above, assumed that before introduction of the ban the RGOB had only considered the reasons as mentioned in the notification. Then criteria 1a, 1b, 2d, 3d, and 3c were the only criteria that would have been given a weight. Let's assume that criteria 1a, 1b and 3d would weigh 0.25 each and 2d and 3c would weigh 0.125 each. Keeping the value scores constant, the effectiveness indices would become 0/100/90/70/50/50, in other words, the choice made by the RGOB under the considered preferences would uniformly point to a complete and immediate ban of plastics, with a strong second position for the gradual implementation of the ban.

Similarly, any given preference could be entered for the criteria by adjusting the weights thus obtaining entirely different outcomes. In fact, any of the alternatives can be ranked first under a certain set of value weights. A sensitivity analysis could shed some light on to what extent the choice of alternative is dependent on the values of the individual criteria value scores and criteria weights. However, with the value scores being mere biased estimations of their real values it would not be useful to explore all options. And considering the fact that the ban is already in place, trying to obtain more realistic value scores would be a waste of resources. Instead, it would be more useful to see whether the ban is effective, and in which way its' effectiveness can be improved.

4.1.2 Effectiveness of the Ban

Unfortunately no detailed information as with regard to plastic use before the ban became effective is available. Plastic waste was collected together with all other waste by the Thimphu City Corporation and dumped in the Mimalakha landfill or burned at the place of collection. Plastic was however already being considered an environmental problem mainly by the RSPN. In 1998 and 1999 they conducted several short studies regarding the plastic use in Bhutan. A mere indication for the plastic use is given by a inter-school plastic collection competition in Thimphu organised by the RSPN in 1998. 1,254 collection bags full, or 3,210 KGs of plastic were collected that time (Pradhan, 2000).

A phone survey conducted by the RSPN prior to the ban among consumers in Thimphu revealed that 70% of the people were in favour of the introduction of a ban or restriction on the use of plastics in Thimphu. 10% were against it because of the inconvenience it would bring along, whereas 10% who were in favour of the ban also stated it would cause some inconvenience, and 20% had no opinion. However, the results from the survey are probably not very reliable because it was mentioned that the survey was conducted by the *Royal Society for the Protection of Nature*, possibly leading to politically correct answers (RSPN, 1999).

After the introduction of the plastic ban in the southern dzongkhag of Samdrup Jongkhar and before the nation-wide ban, the RSPN also conducted a more comprehensive sample survey among 35 shopkeepers in Thimphu. It revealed that 80% of the shops used or distributed plastic bags, and 20% didn't. An average monthly plastic distribution of 1.91 KGs

appeared. 60% of the shopkeepers stated that customers explicitly ask for plastics whereas 22.86% said that customers do not ask for plastics and 17.14% said that customers only sometimes ask for plastics. Only 8.56% of the shopkeepers said that customers usually bring their own bags with 71.42% stating that customers sometimes bring their own bags, and 17.14% said that customers never bring their own bags. 51.42% of the shopkeepers would support the extension of the Samdrup Jongkhar plastic ban to Thimphu and nation-wide, whereas 14.28% was against the imposition of a ban. An impressive 34.28% did not care either way.

From the survey conducted in 2000, Table 2.2 summarises the results regarding the use of plastic before the introduction of the ban.

Table 2.2: Percentages plastic use before the ban

Number of plastics obtained per day	% of consumer obtaining this number	Number of plastic distributed per day	% of shopkeepers distributing this number
≤ 3	35.3	0	5.8
3 to 5	41.1	≤ 5	27.1
5 to 10	15.8	5 to 10	21.8
10 to 20	5.7	10 to 20	16.0
≥ 20	2.2	20 to 30	13.7
		30 to 50	13.7
		> 50	1.9

To make these data more tangible and moreover to come to a nation-wide demand and supply of plastics before the ban, the during the survey collected data were used to estimate the supply and demand functions for plastics. SPSS version 9.0 was used for this purpose.

Different linear, non-linear and logistic models for SPL with different explanatory variables, were run, all having equation 3.1 as their base:

$$SPL = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INS + \beta_2 ENV + \beta_3 EDU + \beta_4 STY + \beta_5 AGE + \beta_6 INT + \beta_7 PLA + \epsilon_0 \quad (\text{Eq. 3.1})$$

In which:

SPL = supply of plastics per day before the ban, no = 0, ≤ 5 = 2.5, 5 to 10 = 7.5, 10 to 20 = 15, 20 to 30 = 25, 30 to 50 = 40, ≥ 50 = 50, as from question 5.

INS = income from the shop, as from question 15.

ENV = dummy variable environmental awareness, if 'yes' then 1, if 'no' then 0, as from question 1.

EDU = educational background, no education = 1, non-formal education = 2, primary education = 3, class X = 4, class XII = 5, diploma course = 6, BSc = 7, MSc = 8, as from question 19.

AGE = age, as from question 17.

STY = type of shop, 1 = grocery/general, 2 = pan, 3 = clothing, 4 = hardware, 5 = electronics, 6 = stationary, 7 = restaurant/bar/hotel, as from question 18.

INT = total monthly income, as from question 16.

PLA = place, 1=Phuentsholing, 2=Thimphu, 3=East.

The assumptions regarding the variables were:

- When income from shop rises the shopkeeper can afford to use more expensive packaging material to give to his consumers. The plastics are relatively cheap and therefore supply of plastics will decrease with increasing INS.
- With increasing ENV the amount of plastics supplied will decrease.
- With rising levels of EDU the supply of plastics will probably decrease as increased EDU often implies higher environmental awareness.
- With rising AGE environmental awareness will increase due to higher education and supply of plastics will thus decrease.
- In general, type 1 and 5 shops (grocery/general and pan) will provide most plastics for packing of their sales, followed by clothing, hardware, stationary and electronics. Type 7 shops (restaurants, bars, and hotels) have most customers consume the products inside and not take them out, therefore as STY increases the supply of plastics decrease.
- Increase in INT often goes together with higher environmental awareness/educational levels and therefore reduced supply of plastics. Moreover when income rises the shopkeeper can afford to use more expensive packaging material to give to his consumers. The plastics are relatively cheap and therefore supply of plastics will decrease with increasing INT.
- Shopkeepers in Phuentsholing will provide most plastics due to closeness to the border, followed by Thimphu, and lastly by east. Increasing PLA will therefore lead to decreasing supply of plastics.

The result after the testing of 17 models was the model presented in equation 3.2. The standard deviations are given in parentheses:

$$SPL = 48.128 - 0.270 * AGE - 9.622 * PLA - 0.0001 * INT \quad (\text{Eq. 3.2})$$

(6025) (0.092) (1720) (0.000)

with an R^2 of 0.344.

The low R^2 and high value of the intercept are reason for doubts regarding the validity of the model. It is probably the data that have caused the fact that only a small number of explanatory variables prove to be significant at the 5% significance level. Looking at the standardised coefficients PLA is the most influential independent variable in the explanation of SPL with a value of -0.568, followed by INC and AGE with a value of both around -0.25 to -0.30. The significance of PLA and INT are more or less expectable. The fact that AGE, instead of e.g. ENV or STY is significant in explaining SPL is a surprising outcome. After entering the means of the independent variables (AGE = 35.89, PLA = 2.49, INT = Nu. 16,160.00/-) an average number of 12.80 plastics distributed per day results. Multiplied by the approximate total number of shops in the surveyed regions, 1,850, this results in an average daily distribution of 23,680 plastics before the initiation of the ban

General characteristics of the model are given in table 2.3:

Table 2.3: ANOVA Table of the model in equation 3.2:

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3638.118	3	1212.706	12.436	.000 ^a
	Residual	6923.882	71	97.519		
	Total	10562.000	74			

a. Predictors: (Constant), INC, AGE, PLA

b. Dependent Variable: SPLA

Secondly the demand for plastics before the ban was estimated by running 22 different models taking the model of equation 3.3 as basic model:

$$DPL = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INC + \beta_2 ENV + \beta_3 EDU + \beta_4 HHS + \beta_5 AGE + \beta_6 PLA + \varepsilon_0 \quad (\text{Eq. 3.3})$$

In which:

DPL = demand for plastic per day, no =0, $\leq 5 = 2.5$, 5 to 10 = 7.5, 10 to 20 = 15, $\geq 20 = 20$, as from question 5.

INC = average income per month, as from question 15.

ENV = dummy variable environmental awareness, if 'yes' then 1, if 'no' then 0, as from question 1.

EDU = educational background, no education = 1, non-formal education = 2, class X = 3, class XII = 4, diploma course = 5, BSc = 6, MSc = 7, as from question 17.

HHS = household size, as from question 14.

AGE = age, as from question 16.

PLA = place, 1 = Phuentsholing, 2 = Thimphu, 3 = East.

The assumptions regarding the variables were:

- The influence of *INC* will probably be ambiguous. With rising income, general expenditure will increase, thus amount of things bought, and therefore the amount of plastics acquired per day. However, higher income might also go together with higher environmental awareness and thus lower amounts of plastic wanted.
- The influence of *ENV* will be that higher environmental awareness regarding the harmfulness of plastics will result in a lower amount of plastics used.
- With higher *EDU* levels the environmental awareness will increase and thus the amount of plastic acquired will decrease.
- As *HHS* increases, more shoppings have to be done and thus more plastics will probably be obtained to carry these shoppings.
- With decreasing *AGE*, environmental awareness will increase through education and thus the amount of plastics will be less. Moreover, at higher age people will often have larger families to sustain and therefore more shopping as to be done and the amount of plastics acquired will be higher.
- Regarding *PLA*, due to close proximity to the border, consumers in Phuentsholing will probably use most plastics, followed by Thimphu, the largest town in Bhutan, and in last position the consumers from the relatively underdeveloped towns in eastern Bhutan.

Running the model resulted in the model of equation 3.4, standard deviations are given between parentheses:

$$DPL = 9.983 - 0.000611 * INC \quad (\text{Eq. 3.4})$$

(1.221) (0.000)

with an R^2 of 0.122.

The R^2 of this model is extremely low. Moreover only one variable, INC seems to help in explaining DPL. Major part of the dependant variable is explained by the intercept. The validity of this model is therefore highly questionable. It is probably due to the low number of observations ($N = 45$) that the model is fitting so poorly. After substituting INC with its mean, Nu. 3800.54/- a daily demand for 7.66 plastics per household resulted before the ban. Multiplied by the total number of households in the surveyed regions, 11,245 (Policy and Planning Division, 1995), a total daily demand of 86,137 plastics per day results.

General characteristics of the model are given in table 2.4:

Table 2.4: ANOVA Table of the model in equation 3.4:

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	171.454	1	171.454	6.116	.017 ^a
	Residual	1233.573	44	28.036		
	Total	1405.027	45			

a. Predictors: (Constant), INC

b. Dependent Variable: DPLA

There is a discrepancy between the supply and demand for plastics before the ban of 62,457 plastics. The explanation for this is given after equation 3.8.

Many people in Bhutan are of the opinion that the plastic ban has greatly reduced the amount of plastic used and littered. As compared to the situation before the ban, the streets of Thimphu are much cleaner with regard to the banned items. Now and then it is still possible to get the banned items, especially doma wrappers, showing that there is a lack in enforcement. More seriously, during the authors' stay and increase in the availability of especially plastic shopping bags was observed. After asking specifically for a packaging material most shopkeepers, especially those selling doma, fruits, and vegetables, rapidly provided single use, thin plastic bags which tear and have to be discarded fast. However, 65.5% of the people considers the ban an effective means to curb the use plastic and its' negative impacts even though other things are still packed in plastic. This means though that 34.5% of the people doubts its effectiveness, which is quite a high figure.

Table 2.5 gives the summarised results of the questions asked regarding plastic use after introduction of the ban. First two columns give the use of plastics by consumers. The second two give the provision of plastics by shopkeepers. The increase in the number of consumers no longer obtaining plastics is less than the comparable situation of shopkeepers no longer distributing plastics. This is probably due to the fining mechanism that does target shopkeepers but does not target consumers.

Table 2.5: Percentage plastic use after the ban:

Number of plastics obtained per day	% of consumers obtaining this number	Number of plastics distributed per day	% of shopkeepers distributing this number
0	57.5	0	90.6
≤ 5	38.4	≤ 5	4.2
5 to 10	4.1	5 to 10	1.9
10 to 20	0.0	10 to 20	1.9
≥ 20	0.0	20 to 30	1.4

Combining the prior to the ban and after the ban data, table 2.6 reveals the decrease in plastic use and supply. All categories show a decrease except for the category 'no plastics' as can be seen in table 2.6:

Table 2.6: Percentage change in plastic use:

Number of plastics obtained per day	% in- or decrease in % of consumers obtaining this number after introduction of the ban	Number of plastics distributed per day	% decrease in % of shopkeepers distributing this number after introduction of the ban
0	+ 57.7	0	+84.8
≤ 5	- 38.0	≤ 5	- 22.9
5 to 10	-11.7	5 to 10	- 19.9
10 to 20	- 5.7	10 to 20	- 14.1
≥ 20	- 2.2	20 to 30	- 12.3
		30 to 50	- 13.7
		≥ 50	- 1.9

Combining the results from the shopkeeper survey in Thimphu conducted by RSPN in 1999 and the new results of the 2000 survey, the distribution of different kinds of plastic are given in table 2.7. The distribution of thin, single use plastics has reduced to a small extent and instead the distribution of good quality, lasting reusable plastics has increased. Although the total plastic distribution has decreased thin, single use plastics still constitute the main part of plastic distribution.

Table 2.7: Kinds of plastics distributed:

Kind of plastic bags	Distribution before the ban	Distribution after the ban
Thin, single use plastics	75%	64%
Thicker plastics	7%	12%
Good quality, lasting, reusable plastics	7%	24%
Combination	11%	-

Same surveys were used to compose the following tables 2.8 and 2.9 giving the percentage of shopkeepers listing the reasons for distributing plastics and their plastic bag sources before and after the ban. The perceived business necessity as driving force behind plastic distribution has decreased and instead consumer demand has become the most important factor of plastic distribution. An increase is noticed in the products themselves as source of plastics. In contrary India and the border towns and the local agents, in effect the buying of plastics, has seen a significant decrease.

Table 2.8: Reasons for plastic distribution:

Reason	Before the ban	After the ban
Business necessity	60.7%	40.2%
Cheaply available/for free with products	7.1%	12.0%
Consumer demand	28.6%	47.8%
Combination business necessity & consumer demand	3.6%	-

Table 2.9: Sources of plastics:

Source of plastic bags	Before the ban	After the ban
India/border towns	67.9%	51.8%
Local agent	17.9%	12.0%
For free with products	3.6%	36.1%
Combination India/border towns & local agents	3.6%	-
Elsewhere	7.2%	-

To establish supply functions for plastics before and after the ban the survey data were transformed by SPSS 9.0 using Probit modelling. Again different models were tested with the equation 3.5 as starting point:

$$SPL_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INS_i + \beta_2 ENV_i + \beta_3 EDU_i + \beta_4 INT_i + \beta_5 AGE_i + \beta_6 STY_i + \beta_7 EFB + \beta_8 OPB + \beta_9 PSS + \beta_{10} PPL + \beta_{11} KNB + \beta_{12} PLA_i + e_0 \quad (\text{Eq. 3.5})$$

In which:

SPL_i = variable supply of plastics per day after the ban, no = 0, $\leq 5 = 2.5$, 5 to 10 = 7.5, 10 to 20 = 15, 20 to 30 = 25, 30 to 50 = 40, $\geq 50 = 50$, as from question 6.

INS_i = Income from the shop, as from question 15.

ENV_i = dummy variable environmental awareness, if 'yes' then 1, if 'no' then 0, as from question 1.

EDU_i = educational background, no education = 1, non-formal education = 2, primary education = 3, class X = 4, class XII = 5, diploma course = 6, BSc = 7, MSc = 8, as from question 19.

AGE_i = age, as from question 17.

STY_i = type of shop, 1 = grocery/general, 2 = pan, 3 = clothing, 4 = hardware, 5 = electronics, 6 = stationary, 7 = restaurant/bar/hotel, as from question 18.

INT_i = total monthly income, as from question 16.

PLA_i = place, 1 = Phucnsholing, 2 = East, 3 = Thimphu.

KNB = dummy variable knowledge of the ban, if yes then 1, if no then 0, as from question 2.

EFB = dummy variable effectiveness of the ban, if yes then 1, if no then 0, as from question 3.

OPB = opinion on the ban, 'very good' = 1, 'good' = 2, 'neutral' = 3, 'bad' = 4, 'very bad' = 5, as from question 4.

PSS = weighted average price of substitutes for plastic: hereby all the average prices of the

substitutes are multiplied by their average use percentage by suppliers in the different places (Thimphu, Phuentsholing and East), with the price if the substitutes taken as equal:

Thimphu: $0.308*0 + 0.359*0.02 + 0.026*10 + 0.154*0 + 0.051*45 + 0.051*9 = \text{Nu. } 3.02/-$.

Phuentsholing: $0.375*0.02 + 0.168*0 + 0.126*0 + 0.126*45 + 0.084*9 + 0.042*225 + 0.042*400 + 0.042*0 = \text{Nu. } 32.68/-$,

East: $0.235*0 + 0.177*400 + 0.165*0 + 0.094*625 + 0.094*9 + 0.024*225 + 0.024*0 + 0.012*45 + 0.012*10 = \text{Nu. } 136.46/-$.

PPL = average price of plastics, in which the price in Thimphu comes down to Nu. 65/- per Kg, in Phuentsholing Nu. 50/- per kg and in the east Nu. 75/- per kg.

As for assumptions regarding PLA_1 , $INSI$, INT_1 , STY_1 , AGE_1 , EDU_1 , ENV_1 same counts as in equation 3.1. For the remaining variables, following are the assumptions regarding their influence on *SPL*:

- When *KNB* is positive and people know about the existence of the ban, they will probably supply fewer plastics (unless they knowingly violate it).
- If *EFB* is positive and people think the ban is effective, they will probably give fewer plastics. Other wise said, if *EFB* is negative, with people doubting the effectiveness, they might have the 'when others don't then why should we adhere to it'-attitude which results in higher plastic supply.
- If $\bullet PB$ is more positive people will be more likely to adhere to the ban and thus supply fewer plastics.
- As for *PSS*, when the average price of plastic substitutes increases shopkeepers will have an incentive to use more of the cheaper alternative, i.e. plastics. Plastic supply will then increase.
- When *PPL* increases shopkeepers have an economic incentive to turn to other alternatives, i.e. plastic substitutes. Supply of plastics will therefore decrease.

After 34 models were tested the model in equation 3.6 was the best fitting model with standard errors between parentheses:

$$SPL_t = 0.552 - 0.607*ENV_t + 0.000011*INT_t \quad (\text{Eq. 3.6})$$

(0.252)(0.259) (0.000)

with an R^2 of 0.309.

Again the low R^2 is cause for concern. One of the explanations is that the number of explanatory variables has decreased by one as compared to equation 3.2. Instead of *PLA* and *AGE* in the model of equation 3.2 *ENV* has become an explanatory variable. *INT* is now the most important explanatory variable when comparing the standardised coefficients. After entering the means for *ENV* (0.9518) and *INT* (Nu. 15,759/-) an average daily supply of 0.1508 plastics per shopkeeper results. This is a considerable decrease of 99% compared to the situation before the ban. Multiplied by the estimated total number of shops in the surveyed regions, 1,850, this results in a total daily distribution of 279 plastics per day.

Characteristics of the regression are given in table 2.10:

Table 2.10: ANOVA Table of the model in equation 3.6:

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.063	2	4.531	17.854	.000 ^a
	Residual	20.305	80	.254		
	Total	29.367	82			

a. Predictors: (Constant), INT, ENV

b. Dependent Variable: SPLA1

For the demand for plastics after the ban equation 3.7 expresses the relationship between the demand and a number of observed independent variables:

$$DPL_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INC_t + \beta_2 ENV_t + \beta_3 EDU_t + \beta_4 HHS_t + \beta_5 AGE_t + \beta_6 KNB + \beta_7 EFB + \beta_8 OPB + \beta_9 PSS + \beta_{10} PLA_t + \varepsilon_0 \quad (\text{Eq. 3.7})$$

In which:

DPL_t = demand for plastic per day, no = 0, $\leq 5 = 2.5$, 5 to 10 = 7.5, 10 to 20 = 15, $\geq 20 = 20$, as from question 5.

INC_t = average income per month, as from question 15.

ENV_t = dummy variable environmental awareness, if 'yca' then 1, if 'no' then 0, as from question 1.

EDU_t = educational background, no education = 1, non-formal education = 2, class X = 3, class XII = 4, diploma course = 5, BSc = 6, MSc = 7, as from question 17.

HHS_t = household size, as from question 14.

AGE_t = age, as from question 16.

KNB = dummy variable knowledge of the ban, if yes then 1, if no then 0, as from question 2.

EFB = dummy variable effectiveness of the ban, if yes then 1, if no then 0, as from question 3.

OPB = opinion on the ban, 'very good' = 1, 'good' = 2, 'neutral' = 3, 'bad' = 4, as from question 4.

PSS = weighted average price of substitutes for plastic: hereby all the average prices of the substitutes are multiplied by their average use percentage by consumers:

Thimphu: $0.266*15 + 0.20*225 + 0.20*45 + 0.066*0 + 0.1*400 + 0.133*0 + 0.033*0 = \text{Nu. } 98.0/-$,

Phuentsholing: $0.20*0 + 0.15*225 + 0.16*650 + 0.12*15 + 0.08*0 + 0.08*45 + 0.08*0 + 0.08*0 = \text{Nu. } 143.15/-$,

East: $0.303*15 + 0.182*400 + 0.121*225 + 0.121*0 + 0.091*650 + 0.061*45 + 0.061*0 + 0.030*0 + 0.030*0 = \text{Nu. } 166.47/-$.

PLA_t = place, 1 = Phuentsholing, 2 = Thimphu, 3 = East.

For assumptions regarding INC_t , ENV_t , EDU_t , HHS_t , PLA_t and AGE_t same assumptions hold as mentioned below equation 3.3. Moreover it is assumed that:

- If KNB is positive and people know about the existence of the ban, they will probably use fewer plastics (unless they knowingly violate it).
- If EFB is positive and people think the ban is effective, they will probably take fewer plastics. Other wise said, if EFB is negative, with people doubting the effectiveness, they might have the 'when others don't then why should we adhere to it'-attitude which results in higher plastic use.
- If OPB is more positive people will be more likely to adhere to the ban and thus use fewer plastics.
- If PSS increases, consumers will be less likely to use these substitutes and prefer to get the free plastics from shopkeepers. It has to be kept in mind however that this weighted average only includes the substitutes for which consumers have to pay, and that there are several others (glued paper bags, old paper, re-used plastic bags and Indian-made paper bags, amounting to 27.1% of the total substitute use) which they get for free as well.

After running 29 models, equation 3.8 expresses the best relationship between DPL_1 and the independent variables, with standard errors between parentheses:

$$DPL_1 = 7.500 - 6.591 * ENV \quad (\text{Eq. 3.8})$$

(0.850) (0.869)

with an R^2 of 0.566.

The R^2 of this model is considerably higher than the one of the previous models. However, in this case too only one independent variable is responsible for the explanation of the demand for plastic and a considerable part is explained by the intercept. The fact that only ENV is responsible for explaining the demand for plastic is surprising too. After adding the mean of ENV, 0.9565 into the equation an average demand for plastics after the ban of 1.20 per day results. The decrease in the demand for plastics is not as much as the decrease in the supply. Multiplied by the total number of households in the surveyed regions, 11,245 (Policy and Planning Division, 1995), a total daily demand of 13,494 plastics per day results. Compared to the situation before the plastic ban, this is a decrease of 84%. General characteristics of the model are given in table 2.11.

Table 2.11: ANOVA Table of the model of equation 3.8:

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	83.103	1	83.103	57.460	.000 ^a
	Residual	63.636	44	1.446		
	Total	146.739	45			

a. Predictors: (Constant), ENV1

b. Dependent Variable: DPLA1

Again there is a discrepancy between the demanded and the supplied amount of plastics, this time of 13,215 plastics or 98%. This discrepancy can be explained by different factors. Firstly the plastics demanded and used by the consumers do not necessarily have the shops as source, with many plastics being imported directly from abroad. Secondly the functions do not account for reuse of plastics by either shopkeepers or consumers. Thirdly, not the whole of Bhutan was included in the survey.

4.1.3 Attitudes towards the Ban

The conducted survey revealed the attitudes of the Bhutanese people regarding the plastic ban. Nation-wide 94.9% of the people think that plastic is bad for the environment. This leaves 5.1% which thinks plastic is not harmful to the environment. Before the ban, 45% thought plastics were harmful to the environment, 39.3% considered them to be useful or even a necessity, and 15.7% had no opinion (RSPN, 1999). It can thus be concluded that after the inception of the plastic ban the environmental awareness regarding the harmfulness of plastics has considerably increased. Of the surveyed people, 85.0% was aware of the plastic ban, but still a considerable 15.0% was not. 65.5% of the people considers ban an effective means to curb the use plastic and its' negative impacts even though other things are still packed in plastic. This means that 34.5% of the people doubts its effectiveness, which is quite a high figure. 35.4% considers the ban as 'very good', 37.8% as 'good', 17.8% has a neutral opinion, 5.9% thinks the ban is a 'bad' development, and 3.1% thinks it's 'very bad'. A majority of 70% of the people discloses a positive attitude towards the ban, whereas 18% is neutral and only 9% has a negative attitude. These opinions on the ban are further given in graph 1.

Graph 1: Opinions on the plastic ban.

4.1.4 Substitutes for Plastic

From observation in Thimphu as well as other parts of Bhutan the use of several different substitutes for plastic bags has been observed. Some of them were in use before the ban; others have come up after the ban as inventive reactions of both prior suppliers as well as users of plastic bags. From the government side no substitute was supplied and therefore it depended upon the previous users to come up with them. The observed substitutes are as follows:

- Traditional woven bags: these bags are mostly woven by women, mainly from Eastern Bhutan. The bags are made by settlers from there in Thimphu or brought from the East itself. Their price is dependant on size, materials used (cotton or silk thread) and the patterns that are woven, the more intricately the pattern the more expensive the bag. On average they will cost around Nu. 400/-. Because they are mainly used by rural people most of the population in the towns considers them old-fashioned and does not make much use of these bags.
- Imported nylon bags: these are mainly duplicate brand bags (Nike, Reebok, and Adidas) imported from Thailand, Bangladesh or China. Their price is dependent on size; quality is mostly similar (poor!). Still they find a ready market and have a lot of appeal especially among the youth. Price is around Nu. 650/- on average.
- Indian-made paper bags: shopkeepers, mainly of the bigger shops like Tashi Stores import these bags from India. They are relatively cheap but not strong and should not be filled too heavy or they'll tear.
- Hand woven plastic-string baskets: these baskets are made at home, mainly in Thimphu. The plastic strings are bought in different colours and woven into bags of different sizes and shapes. They are very popular for vegetable shoppings. On average they will cost Nu. 225/-.
- Glued paper bags: used paper, like notebooks used by schoolchildren, old books and other waste paper are glued together.
- Old paper: old paper, mainly newspapers, are bought from stationary shops or collected and used to wrap products in.
- Re-stitched cement bags: plastic-thread bags in which the cement producers of Bhutan sell their cement are cleaned after used and re-stitched into bags of different size, with prices ranging from Nu. 3/- to Nu. 30/-.
- Re-used plastic bags: plastic bags which come from abroad, which are still kept and used by people after one year of ban, plastic bags which were illegally given and are re-used, and the plastics formerly wrapped around imported products like instant noodles are re-used.
- Jute bags: these big bags are mainly used for bulk transportation of vegetables by road.
- Deysho bags: these bags are manufactured from rough deysho sheets, which are glued together and onto which a rope handle is made. The bags are strong, durable and decorative but they are destroyed by water.

In table 2.1 these substitutes are listed as well as their most common use. The average price and approximate share in the total use of substitutes are given as well subdivided by consumers (upper row) and shopkeepers (lower row).

Table 2.12: Substitution of plastic.

Substitute Item	Use	Average price (Nu.)	Share (%)
Traditional woven bags	Grocery shopping	Nu. 400/-	12.7%
		Nu. 400/-	12.5%
Imported nylon bags	Travelling, to office, vegetable and grocery shopping	Nu. 650/-	7.4%
		Nu. 625/-	8.2%
Indian-made paper bags	Grocery shopping	-	12.1%
		Nu. 0.02	24.5%
Hand woven plastic-string baskets	Vegetable shopping, pack lunch	Nu. 225/-	16.0%
		Nu. 225/-	2.1%
Glued paper bags	Grocery shopping, clothing	-	7.9%
		-	15.6%
Old paper	Doma, snacks, meat, grocery shopping and clothing	-	3.1%
		-	24.2%
Re-stitched cement bags	Vegetable and fruit shopping	Nu. 12.50/-	0%
		Nu. 10/-	1.3%
Re-used plastic bags	Doma, fruits, vegetables, grocery shopping, clothing	-	4.6%
		-	3.4%
Jute bags	Vegetables, clothes, grocery items in bulk	Nu. 45/-	11.7%
		Nu. 45/-	2.0%
Deysho bags	Souvenirs, bread, expensive clothing and footwear	Nu. 15/-	24.6%
		Nu. 9/-	6.3%

Graph 2 shows the percentual use of the different plastic substitutes nation wide and average over both shopkeepers as well as suppliers.

Graph 2: Plastic substitute use in Bhutan.

The consumer survey conducted by the RSPN in 1998 revealed that 50% of the consumers supported the opinion of the deysho producers by indicating that they would start using deysho bags as an alternative. 40% had no opinion, and 10% stated that the deysho bags would be too expensive for shopkeepers. The shopkeeper survey conducted by the RSPN in Thimphu in 1999 revealed that 48.6% of the shopkeepers would be willing to use paper bags as an alternative. 20% was unwilling to use paper bags as an alternative. 31.4% said that this depended on other factors (RSPN, 1999).

The arrival at Paro Airport bore a promising feature: when being something from the small Duty Free Shop the commodities are given in a deysho bag bearing Druk Air's logo. But after leaving the airport, a completely different picture exists. When roaming around in Thimphu or any other place in Bhutan these days, one will hardly see any people using deysho paper bags. In fact, one is more likely to see people carry plastic bags! The survey revealed a rather high percentage of people saying they use deysho bags. But the fact that they considered this, intentionally or unintentionally, the 'right' answers to give might have biased their answers. Currently Druk Air Corporation distributes deysho bags, as duty free bags at Paro Airport, Jichu Drake bakery in Thimphu, and some clothing shops in Thimphu town. Most of the bags produced find their way to markets outside Bhutan. Even the Handicrafts Emporium in Thimphu, considered the stronghold of Bhutan's cultural produce, presents the bought items in a foreign-made paper bag. Even the producers themselves admit the internal market for their deysho bags has not improved after the introduction of the ban.

Why is it that the paper producers' hopes and expectations did not materialise? To examine this question, firstly the WTP for deysho bags and the forces that determine it were examined by using regression analysis. To this end three models were tested with information from both shopkeepers as well as consumers as to how much they are willing to pay for deysho bags. These models establish a bid function for deysho bags dependant on various variables.

The first model, for consumers only, includes HHS as one of the independent variables, or:

$$DDB_{cons} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INC + \beta_2 OPD + \beta_3 EDU + \beta_4 AGE + \beta_5 PSS + \beta_6 PLA + \beta_7 HHS + \varepsilon_0 \quad (\text{Eq. 3.9})$$

The second model, for shopkeepers, includes STY and INS as independent variables, or:

$$DDB_{shop} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INC + \beta_2 OPD + \beta_3 EDU + \beta_4 AGE + \beta_5 PSS + \beta_6 PLA + \beta_7 STY + \beta_8 INS + \varepsilon_0 \quad (\text{Eq. 3.10})$$

The third uses observations from both consumers and shopkeepers. This model is represented as:

$$DDB_{tot} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INC + \beta_2 OPD + \beta_3 EDU + \beta_4 AGE + \beta_5 PSS + \beta_6 PLA + \beta_7 INS + \beta_8 HHS + \beta_9 STY + \varepsilon_0 \quad (\text{Eq. 3.11})$$

In which following are the variables, (s) refers to shopkeepers, (c) refers to consumers:

DDB = the maximum willingness to pay per deysho bag, as from question 13(c)/14(s).

INC = average income per month, as from question 15(c)/16(s).

OPD = opinion on deysho, 'very good' = 1, 'good' = 2, 'neutral' = 3, 'bad' = 4, as from question 11(c)/12(s).

EDU = educational background, no education = 1, non-formal education = 2, primary education = 3, class X = 4, class XII = 5, diploma course = 6, BSc = 7, MSc = 8, as from question 17(c)/19(s).

STY = type of shop, 1 = grocery/general, 2 = pan, 3 = clothing, 4 = hardware, 5 = electronics, 6 = stationary, 7 = restaurant/bar/hotel, as from question 18 (s)

INS = income from the shop, as from question 15 (s).

INT = total monthly income, as from question 16 (s).

AGE = age, as from question 16(c)/17(s).

PSS = the weighted average price of substitutes for deysho for consumers and producers from the different regions, for consumers: Thimphu: Nu. 98.0/-, Phuentsholing: Nu. 143.15/-, East: Nu. 166.47/-, for suppliers: Thimphu: Nu. 3.02/-, Phuentsholing: Nu. 32.68/-, East: Nu. 136.46/-.

HHS = household size, as from question 14 (c).

PLA = place, 1=Phuentsholing, 2=Thimphu, 3=East.

- The influence of *INC/INT/INS* will be positive. With rising income, people will have more to offer for the relatively expensive deysho bags. When income from shop rises the shopkeeper can afford to use more expensive packaging material to give to his consumers.
- When *OPD* is more positive, the *WTP* will probably be higher. People who have a positive attitude towards are more likely to spend money on it as well.
- With higher *EDU* levels people might be more aware of the importance of the deysho craft for Bhutan, and the importance of the production mainly for the small-scale producers' livelihood. Moreover, higher education often goes together with higher income.
- As *HHS* increases, the *WTP* for deysho bags will decrease as disposable income decreases due to larger expenses on other items.
- With decreasing *AGE*, consumers might have less interest in deysho (and the traditional crafts in general).
- Regarding *PLA*, people in the traditional deysho producing eastern dzongkhags will probably offer more for deysho bags than people in the westernised towns.
- As for *PSS*, if the average price of substitutes increases people are probably prepared to offer more for deysho bags to offset this increase in price.
- In general, type 1 and 2 shops (grocery/general and pan) will provide most packings for their sales and therefore have the greatest need for deysho bags and thus offer more, followed by clothing, hardware, stationary and electronics. Type 7 shops (restaurants, bars, and hotels) have most customers consume the products inside and not take them out; therefore as *STY* increases the *WTP* for deysho bags will decrease.

Equation 3.9 was run with 44 different models. The mean of the dataset was 7.659 with a median of 5.000. Finally, the model of equation 3.12 was deemed to fit the data best. Under the coefficients their standard deviations are mentioned:

$$DDB_{cons} = 9.016 + 0.001134*INC - 1.707*OPD - 0.205*AGE + 0.647*HHS \quad (\text{Eq. 3.12})$$

(2.505) (0.000) (0.757) (0.069) (0.210)

with an R^2 of 0.549.

Table 2.13: ANOVA table corresponding to equation 3.12.

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	870.203	4	167.551	10.947	.000 ^a
	Residual	551.017	36	15.306		
	Total	1221.220	40			

a. Predictors: (Constant), HHS, OPD, AGE, INC

b. Dependent Variable: DDBCONS

The values of the standardised coefficients show that INC has relatively the largest influence on DDB_{cons} . After substituting INC, OPD, AGE and HHS with their national means for consumers (INC = Nu. 3,617.68/-, OPD = 1.732, AGE = 30.317, HHS = 5.756) a WTP of Nu. 7.67/- per deysho bag emerged.

Equation 3.10 was run with 45 different models. The mean of the dataset was 9.877 with a median of 8.000. The model given by equation 3.13 was the best fitting one. Below between parentheses the standard deviations.

$$DDB_{supp} = 0.777 + 0.0001214 * INC - 0.0273 * PSS + 2.818 * PLA - 0.386 * STY + 0.0006209 * INS$$

(2.707)
(0.000)
(0.016)
(1.415)
(0.229)
(0.000)

(Eq. 3.13)

with an R^2 of 0.759.

Table 2.14: ANOVA Table of the model in equation 3.13:

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3553.091	5	712.618	42.298	.000 ^a
	Residual	1128.799	67	16.848		
	Total	4681.890	72			

a. Predictors: (Constant), STY, PSS, INT, INS, PLA

b. Dependent Variable: DDBSUPP

The correlation between INC and INS was, as could be expected, rather high (-0.597). Even larger was the correlation between PLA and PSS, which is understandable due to the way the value if the two were fixed, the price of dcysho being dependant on the place where the shop was situated. Due to the high significance of the variables in this model and the low improvement of the model if one of the two was left out, it was deemed better to include them both. It is noted from the coefficients after standardisation that the absolute values of most standardised coefficients are more or less in the same order except for INS and STY. STY has a rather lower influence on DDB_{supp} whereas INS has the largest influence. An increase in

income earned from the shop has relatively the largest influence on the change (increase) in the WTP for deysho bags.

After substituting the national means for INC (Nu. 11,678.77/-), INS (Nu. 6,244.25/-), STY (2.343), PLA (2.507), and PSS (Nu. 86.29/-) a WTP of Nu. 9.88/- per bag emerged.

Equation 3.11 was run with 9 different models after which the model of equation 3.14 turned out to have the best results. The mean of the dataset was 8.778 with a median of 8.000. The standard deviations of the coefficients are in parentheses:

$$DDB_{tot} = 8.548 + 0.000695 * INC - 1.404 * OPD - 0.0769 * AGE \quad (\text{Eq. 3.14})$$

(1.355) (0.000) (0.007) (0.008)

with an R^2 of 0.767.

Table 2.15: ANOVA table of the model in equation 3.14:

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4105.459	5	821.092	54.625	.000 ^b
	Residual	1533.208	102	15.031		
	Total	5638.667	107			

a. Predictors: (Constant), INS, OPD, HHS, PSS, INT

b. Dependent Variable: DDBTOT

The standardised coefficients once more show that relatively the greatest influence on DDB_{tot} comes from INC. The standardised coefficients of OPD and AGE are almost equal. After substituting the mean values of INC (Nu. 6,890.93/-), OPD (1.72) and AGE (34.28) an average WTP of Nu. 8.29/- appears for the combined equation.

PSS and INS, variables which do occur in the shopkeeper model but not in the consumer model, and HHS and OPD for which the opposite holds all appear in the combined function as well. INC, HHS and INS are the only variables which are significant in all three the models (although HHS does not appear in equation 5.16 and INS does not appear in equation 5.15 this is simply because these variables have not been measured for shopkeepers and consumers respectively). Compared to INC and INS, HHS has a considerably lower standardised value of the coefficient and therefore relatively less influences on the WTP. It can therefore be expected that in a model based on a better set of data, and in fact in reality as well, the WTP for deysho bags is purely dependant on income. For a developing country this is not strange, as here the preferences of individuals are mainly dependent on their income. Income restraints influence the buying preferences of individuals, and preferences based on an attribute of the individual other than income, such as environmental concern, age or education, develop only with raising incomes (Cunningham and Saigo, 1997). Since the WTP and the maximum stated amount people are prepared to offer for deysho bags, is a stated preference of the individuals, it can be expected to depend directly and only on their income. The re-appearance of INS, which is highly related to INC, supports that presumption. Despite this, income is also influenced by the price of substitutes and one would therefore expect PSS to be significant as well. The fact that the average price of substitutes as it is linked to the

region instead of the consumption package of substitutes of the concerned individual multiplied by the average price of those substitutes (i.e. a separate average price of substitutes for each observation) was taken might have caused the absence of PSS in the consumer model and the low standardised coefficient values.

Concluding, the WTP for deysho bags ranges between Nu. 7.67/- for consumers and Nu. 9.88/- for shopkeepers with a national average of Nu. 8.29/-. Therefore, the current price of Nu. 5/- (Tenzin, 2000) should effectively increase the sale of the deysho bags and encourage its wider use. But this is assuming that price is the only determinant for deysho demand. However, without proper marketing methods to increase the popularity of the deysho bags among the population a price drop will not be effective. Moreover, substitution between plastic bags and deysho bags is difficult. Deysho bags have only a very limited use, which is more of a decorative than of a utility character. Their propensity to disassemble when becoming wet makes them useless for most purposes. Other substitutes have taken over the role of plastics and deysho bags have not been able to secure their position firmly. The fact that almost 25% of the consumers indicated using deysho bags as substitute is clearly not supported by the general observation and has to be discarded as 'an answer in the line of the survey', people answering this because they think they are expected to answer it.

4.2 The Economics and Environmental Effects of Deysho Production in Bhutan

4.2.1 Classification of Deysho and its Production Methods

Broadly, paper factories operate at two different levels, which can be distinguished on the basis of production capacity, technology sophistication and nature of operation (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999).

The *household level paper production* is concentrated in Trashigang dzongkhag and is a unique tradition of the local communities. Its main activities include collection of raw material and fuel wood and cooking and drying the products. Due to the use of simple tools and crude method of processing the paper quality is poorer compared to that of the larger units. This method of production of traditional paper is a very labour-intensive process that can be carried out with little initial investment and infrastructure.

The *semi-mechanised or enterprise level production* is concentrated in Thimphu. It is defined as a production exceeding 100,000 sheets annually, more than 10 employees permanently employed, having the ability to value add the products, and a semi-mechanised production. The labour-intensive work such as beating the fibres and pressing and drying the sheets is done by machines, thus greatly enhancing the production capacity. The production processes are described below for both the traditional rural household production as well as the semi-mechanised production:

Rural household production describing tsharsho process: (Imaeda, 1988, Dorji and Zangpo, 1999, Hadorn and Wangda, 1999, Dorji et al., 2000a, Sherub, 1999). See also Diagram I in Annex 2.

Harvesting, drying and transportation of bark to producer: The bark is harvested and usually the outer secondary fibrous cambium (the white inner bark being called bast or cuticle layer) is stripped off the branches and cut into 40-50 cm long, 10-cm wide pieces of 5-7 mm thick. Then the bark is dried (naturally or hung in the smoke of a fire), packed in bundles and transported to producer.

Tearing and soaking the bark: The bark is torn with the help of a small dagger made of bone and/or plastic. The bark is then soaked in a wooden tank with water with figures ranging from two to four hours (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999) to 12 to 24 hours (Sherub 1999) in order to clean it from waste bark, soil and other dirt. Moreover the soaking reduces the pectin quantity in the bark which improves the paper quality. A recent innovation not used in all the household units and producing softer and smoother papers is the washing and filtering with a cher-gen to remove the residue and dirt.

Photo 2: Rural household production of deysho is largely a family business. Here the whole family assists in tearing the bark.

Cooking: The bark is cooked in a loara with alkali water for 3-4 hours (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999) in some cases, 5-10 hours (Imaeda, 1988, Dorji et al., 2000a, Sherub, 1999) or 7-8 hours (Dorji and Zangpo, 1999) in others, until it is soft. The standard size and volume of the loara can contain enough bark to obtain one hundred sheets of paper. Variation in size and volume occurs though. The bark is turned quite often. A jama of bark consumes 40 to 60 litres of filtrate water to completely cook the bark (Sherub, 1999).

The alkali water or khare is obtained by pouring water through a Phrokpa with fern leaves inside, filled with lye of wood ashes or the residue of burnt wood biomass and collected in a non-corrosive container. The wood ash is becoming scarce when production increases and Dorji et al., (2000a) report that often household items are traded for wood ash with other villagers. While mixing water with khare, caution must be taken since too much khare results in only the outer portion of the bark getting cooked and not the inner part, resulting in poor paper quality. The khare plays a vital role in the subduing of fungus growth on the sheets. The cooked bark is washed with clear water and cut into small pieces.

Sometimes, the cooking occurs in two steps, the first step taking 2 to 3 hours, then the bark is taken out and split, and again boiled for 5 hours (Sherub, 1999) in alkali water until it is well softened and can be easily broken.

Beating and churning: The now soft bark is beaten (with a wooden club, litong, mallet on a flat stone) until it is reduced to a fine pulp. The quality of this pulp determines the ultimate fineness and smoothness of the paper. The pulp is made into small balls for convenience and then smashed and churned thoroughly in a large through (suma), containing enough pulp to produce one thousand sheets. A circular perforated piston is moved in both upward and downward strokes and the efficient movement makes the pulp soft and sticky.

Laying the pulp on the screen: Small quantities of pulp are mixed with the right amount of water in a container. By immersing and withdrawing a fine, flexible mould (Sh., Dz. Tshar, Dzalakha: Parshing, bamboo or reed split screen with the desired paper size and shape) into the mixture of pulp and water a thin layer of fibres is collected. Shaking of the mould leads to leaking out of excess water and an even distribution and good binding of the fibres. For a thick quality of paper the pulp is poured on the mould to the level where the tsar is no longer visible. To make thinner sheets less pulp is poured onto the tsar.

Photo 3: Moulding the sheets on the screen is the most important step in the production process and needs a skilful and experienced hand.

Drying: The screens with the pulp on it are obliquely (in a 40 to 60 degree angle) rested on poles and dried in the wind and sun. Direct sunlight however causes the paper to wrinkle and under the influence of cool wind the drying process is much better. This weather condition is mostly found during winter days, when the drying takes around 20 minutes to half an hour. In summer it is too wet. Sometimes the drying takes place inside houses or huts near a wood fire. This way only small quantities can be produced however. The dried sheets are carefully separated from the screen by tussling each other with the hands covered in butter and placed on top of each other. The khare prevents the sheets from growing fungus even when kept like that for one month. Sometimes, mainly in unexpected unfavourable weather, the semi-dried sheets are piled up on top of a smooth wooden plank. When there are around 200 sheets, again a smooth plank is placed on top and big stones are placed on top of this for around a night to squeeze the water out. In some cases a modern jack is used for this purpose. When the layer of sheets becomes too thick and bulky a dum is kept at the edge of the sheets after twenty sheets are piled up for squeezing the water out. After five dum have been counted there are 100 sheets in the pile, and after 10 dum there are 200 sheets. This way the number of

sheets is counted. For the counting of the number of spoilt or torn sheets pebbles dew are used. After spoilt sheet taken out a dew is pulled aside, and in total there are twenty one dew.

Photo 4: The days' production drying in the open air.

Re-use of spoilt sheets: when a dry spoilt or poor quality sheet is detected it is soaked in khare, made into pieces and reprocessed. Wet spoilt sheets are directly pieced and processed. Thus the wastage is minimum (Dorji et al, 2000a)

Semi-mechanised production (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999), see also Diagram II in Annex 2:

Harvesting and drying of bark: The bark is harvested and usually the outer bark is stripped off. Then the bark is dried, packed in bundles and transported to producer.

Soaking: The bark is soaked in water for two to four hours in order to clean it from waste bark, soil and other dirt.

Cooking: The bark is cooked in a copper vessel with alkali water (imported soda ash being mixed with the water) for three to four hours until it is soft. The cooked bark is washed with clear water and cut into small pieces. Then again it is cooked in alkali water until it is well softened and can be easily broken.

Pulping: The now soft bark is broken into a fine pulp making use of a machine. The quality of this pulp determines the ultimate fineness and smoothness of the paper.

Moulding: Small quantities of pulp are mixed with the right amount of water in a container and sometimes artificial glue sticking the fibres together is added to obtain stronger paper. By immersing and withdrawing a fine mould into the mixture of pulp and water a thin layer of fibres is collected. Shaking of the mould leads to an even distribution and good binding of the fibres.

Photo 5: Semi-mechanised moulding in Jungshi, Thimphu.

Drying: The thin layer of fibres is put onto a fine cloth and piled up. This pile is put into a strong press in order to remove as much water as possible and to obtain smoother paper. The paper sheets are dried in the mould in the sun or separated from the mould using an electric drying oven. However the traditional way of drying the paper in the sun makes the sheets whiter.

Smoothering (optional): A machine is used to smoothen the surface of the paper.

In addition to the different production methods of the paper a distinction can also be made between two types of *dcysho*, known as *tsharsho* and *resho*. In the *tsharsho* type of production the pulp is poured on a bamboo screen. This is also known as the 'pouring method' (Hunter, 1947). This method is described under the household level production process above. The paper is thicker and darker in appearance and has greater strength than *resho*. This paper fetches a higher price and is mainly used for wrapping and the printing of religious texts like *Bum* and *Domang*. Bhutan is the only country in the Himalayas where this technique has been practised in the past using screens made of reed splints. The bamboo screens currently in use are very fine and thus difficult to make locally. Therefore they are imported from Japan. The cost of these screens in Japan is very high and so only the semi-mechanised units can afford to buy them. *Tsharsho* is further reported to be made in *Radhi*, *Yongphula* and *Khaling*, *Trashigang dzongkhag* (Sherub, 1999)

The household level units continue to use cloth screens, a method introduced from Tibet and common all over the Himalayas, resulting in a paper type called *resho*. The method is known as the 'dipping method' (Hunter 1947). The cotton cloth mould is kept floating on water and highly concentrated paper pulp is poured on the cloth. Then the mould is shaken and lifted till the sheet is formed. The mould is leaned against a stick till sun and wind have dried the paper, which takes around half a day. Thus per mould only two sheets per day can be made (Imacda, 1988).

4.2.2 Production and Supply of Deysho

Records from the Ministry of Trade and Industry show that in total Bhutan has 12 people across the country with a license for traditional paper making, although not all have established a unit. In 1995 the MTI decided that mini-scale or cottage industries in rural areas (i.e. T/Yangtse) do not require a trade license since it is a traditional craft. This explains the discrepancy between the number of licenses and the actual number of units estimated to be more than 30. This number is not exactly known however. Units exist at least in Thimphu, Samdrup Jongkhar, Trashigang, Mongar, Zhemgang and Trashi Yangtse dzongkhag. The uncertainty about the actual number of units disables the estimate the actual demand for the raw materials. A field survey conducted by Hadorn and Wangda (1999) revealed that there are at least 19 permanent and 26 temporary paper factories in Thimphu, Mongar, Trashigang and Trashi Yangtse Dzongkhag.

However, deysho production is a highly dynamic industry, and producers in one year might not be there the next year. An example of this is Dhewang in Dckiling, Bumthang. Hadorn and Wangda (1999) list this factory as one of the three semi-mechanical producers and the third largest producer in Bhutan. However, by the time of visit in June 2000 the factory had closed down, according to the other producers because the emphasis of production in the unit was on quantity instead of quality thus leading to inferior products. This is an example of a 'permanent' producer shutting down. In Trashi Yangtse the dynamics are even bigger especially among the temporary producers.

In contrast to Bumthang, Zhemgang saw the establishment of a new factory funded by the Integrated Sustainable Development Programme (ISDP). This factory was started in August 1999 and follows the traditional, handmade process of producing *sharsho*. With the funding of Nu. 100,000 the proprietor and an assistant were sent to Mangala Handmade Paper House in Thimphu for a 6-month training and some basic tools were bought as well. It is situated in Tingtibi and has currently 8 employees. In wintertime this increases when temporary labour is hired. Both *Daphne* as well as *Edgeworthia* is collected by the factory itself as well as on contract basis by farmers. Still the resource is abundantly available at a distance of around one-hour from Tingtibi. Unregulated harvesting might result in quick depletion of the resource though, as the Yangtse example shows. The boiler is fuelled by locally obtained wood. The production is on order basis, with an average production of 200 sheets of good quality per day. Main market is local although some small amount is sold in Thimphu. The factory produces deysho bags sold to Jichu Drake Bakery in Thimphu. The business is profitable, but marketing is a main constraint and currently the factory is looking for other markets like schools and institutions in the locality and Thimphu. Since the factory could not be visited and no detailed information on the current raw material consumption and production are available this unit has not been incorporated in the report.

The yearly and even monthly fluctuations in producers and production levels make estimations on total production and demand for raw materials extremely difficult. Following results are based on interviews with the proprietors Hadorn and Wangda (1999) managed to make a rough estimate on the raw material requirement (see paragraph 2.3) and the daily turn over. These amounts are however only valid for the year 1999. The total annual turn over of the traditional paper industry in Bhutan exceeds Nu. 6 million.

There are two semi-mechanised paper factories in Thimphu, Jungshi Paper Manufacturing Company and Mangala Handmade Paper House, both established with the assistance of Misumi town in Japan. Jungshi was established in the late eighties and re-opened

in 1996 after the factory caught fire in January 1995. Mangala opened in August 1995. These two semi-mechanised units remain the largest producers, accounting for over half of the total paper production in the country with 450,000 sheets per year.

In the East deysho is produced mainly in a traditional process. In Trashigang dzongkhag there are two paper manufacturing units, located at Yongphula and Khaling. The 2 units in Thimphu and two in Trashigang account for 63% of the annual production of handmade paper with an annual value of more than Nu. 5,223,000/-. Trashi Yangtse is traditionally the deysho producing dzongkhag and till date the household level production is concentrated there. There are altogether 34 units there.

Products: Paper made from Daphne species is tough, pliable, elastic and durable. The fibres are considerably longer (generally more than 7 mm) than those of other paper-producing species. Daphne gives strong, dark paper whereas paper from Edgeworthia is whiter, softer, more pliable and more fragile. The household level units mainly produce the ordinary deysho sheets of the reshho type using Daphne bark. Paper made from Daphne bark can be stored for a long time due to an aldehyde chemical that prevents fungal growth and insect attacks.

Photo 6: Unsold sheets stocked in the altar room.

The semi-mechanised units produce not only ordinary sheets (mainly tsharsho) but a wide range of other products such as design paper, books, photo albums, files and folders, envelopes and postcards as well. These value addition products are in great demand from handicraft shops, Banks, Corporations, Hotels, International Organisations and various private companies. Products from the household level units vary considerably in quality and size, depending on the amount of ash use, the skills of the producers, the size and shape of screens and the drying method. Proper grading according to quality, packing, branding and uniformisation of size and thickness would greatly enhance the sale of their products..

Price of products: the pricing of deysho for the household level producers is done as per demand. If demand is higher, the producers sell the sheets at a higher price. The price hardly ever exceeds Nu. 4.00/- per sheet (Dorji et al., 2000a). When producers are in need of money, they sell the sheets for as little as Nu. 2.00/- per sheet. When demand and thus price is low and the producers don't need money, they stock the sheets that can be kept for a long period of time without deteriorating paper quality. Another factor influencing the price per sheet is the cost of raw materials. When the producers collect the bark themselves the cost will consist of the paid royalty fee only. Most producers have to rely on agents though for the raw material, which increases the cost with transportation charge, labour charge and commission. The price of the products of the semi-mechanised producers in Thimphu depends on the type of product.

Employment and labour wages: there is no record of the exact number of people employed in the traditional paper production. However, for the semi-mechanised units an exact number of employees permanently active can be obtained. They have permanent staff working for the factory whereas the household production level has a constantly changing number of family members and sometimes hired staff. This is due to the seasonality of the production as well as the involvement of other people. The field study conducted by the RNR-RC Yusipang concluded that there are about 147 people directly (manufacturing) employed in the household level units and another 170 indirectly (raw material and fuel wood collection, transportation and retailers) involved. That puts the total employment in the industry over 300 people (Hadorn and Waugda, 1999).

For external labour the household level production units a daily labour wage of Nu. 50/- is paid per female and Nu. 60/- per male person, irrespective of the work they do in the production process (Sherub, 1999). Hired labour is used to beat or churn the pulp. The laying of pulp on the screen requires skill and is mostly done by the head of the unit. Family members, even children, are also employed in the production. These are not paid wage and therefore not counted as production cost, although they substantially contribute to the production.

Raw material is collected from the southern geogs of the dzongkhag to supplement the local collection from Taphel, Rigsum Goenpa and Lichen. For raw material collection a wage is paid to the bark collectors of Nu. 30/- to Nu. 45/- per jama of bark (one jama of bark producing around 40 to 60 sheets, depending on required thickness and thus quality of the sheet, Dorji et al., 2000b). For transportation of the bark from villages in Khamdang (Shaksiugma Goenpa, Brongla), Yalang and Toetsho geogs to Rangthangwoong and from villages in Tomazhaugtshen, Ramjar and Jamkhar geogs to Duksum a wage of Nu. 60/- per day is paid. For transportation from Rangthangwoong and Duksum to the road at Chorten Kora tractors are used which charge a transportation charge of Nu. 1000/- per load. From Chorten Kora the family members themselves mostly transport the barks. In case of large producers, mules or additional porters are hired at the rate of Nu. 100/- per mule and Nu. 30/- to Nu. 45/- per jama carried by the hired porter (Sherub, 1999, Dorji et al., 2000b). In total, harvesting and transportation charges and the royalty fee add up to around Nu. 35.90/- per kilogram of bark. With regard to the collection and transportation of bark from other dzongkhags, no information is available. In cases where the family members can not provide enough labour for the collection of firewood, labour is hired at the rate of Nu. 60/- per day for males and Nu. 50/- per day for females.

The semi-mechanised producers in Thimphu have labourers employed throughout the year at fixed wages. In times of extra production, additional labour is hired.

Table 2.16: Economic facts on annual paper production in Bhutan (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999, with updates from Dorji et al., 2000a).

Production unit and location	Raw material requirement per year (kg)	Production per year (sheets)	Total production cost ⁴	Gross return ⁵	Employment (number of people)
Sangay Wangdi	2,600	26,000	36,400	91,000	3
Tashi	2,860	23,400	40,040	81,900	3
Sonam Choeda	2,600	23,400	36,400	81,900	3
Pema	2,600	15,600	36,400	54,600	2
Kotangla	3,640	26,000	50,960	91,000	3
Gonpo Dorji	5,980	26,000	83,720	91,000	5
Manela	2,860	26,000	40,040	91,000	3
Shogpola	2,600	26,000	36,400	91,000	3
Subtotal permanent units T/ Yangtse	25,740	192,400	360,360	673,400	22
Temporary units in Bomdeling (14)	6,500	64,960	90,940	227,360	36
Temporary units in Yangtse (12)	5,570	55,680	77,950	252,000	32
Total household level production T/Yangtse	37,810	313,040	529,250	1,095,640	90
Ugyen Dorji (T/Gang)	7,800	39,000	54,600	331,500	9
Namgay (T/Gang)	5,720	39,000	40,040	331,500	7
Jungshi Handmade Paper Factory	30,000	300,000	392,000	3,000,000	30
Mangala Handmade Paper House	15,600	156,000	218,400	1,560,000	11
Grand total	96,930	847,040	1,234,290	6,318,640	147

⁴ for calculation of the total production cost a price of Nu. 14.00 per kg raw material is taken for the household level producers, Nu. 7.00 per kg for the Trashigang units, and Nu. 4.00 per kg for Jungshi and Mangala.

⁵ for calculation of the gross return Nu. 3.50 per sheet is taken for the household level producers, Nu. 8.50 per sheet for the Trashigang units, and Nu. 10.00 per sheet for Jungshi and Mangala.

Box 1: Deysho production in Mongar.

(United Nations Development Programme, 2000, National Women's Association of Bhutan, -/2000, Kucnsel, 2000a)

In Kurizampa, Mongar, a semi-mechanised deysho manufacturing plant was started in 1992. The premises, shed and second-hand machines (two dryers, one press, one shredder) were donated to the National Women's Association of Bhutan (NWAB) by Tashi Group of Companies. The production capacity amounted to 200 to 250 sheets per day and the plant had 10 employees. Both sheets as well as final products such as envelopes and bags were produced and exported to Thimphu and from there abroad. The raw materials used for producing the sheets were deykap, deynap and banana stems. The raw material was directly purchased from the local farmers who collected it in their free time. During the agricultural high season the farmers were too engaged in their farming activities and during these times contractors provided for the raw material. After deduction of the production cost including labour wage the profit that remained was enough for the manager to sustain his family. In 1999 the firm was closed down because the machines were no longer functioning properly. Although the press and shredder can be repaired, the necessary funding was not made available. The dryers are out of order since the outside became corrugated and whilst drying the sheets the rust stuck to the sheets making them unfit for sale. The employees were then fired and the owner and his family have been living in the shed. In March 2000 the NWAB, a Bhutanese NGO on non-profit basis working for women and rural women in particular established in 1980, received a Nu. 1,081,241/- (US\$ 24,942/-) grant under the Partners in Development Programme (PDP) of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) with which they will shift and rehabilitate the existing paper manufacturing unit to Gyelpozhing under Mongar Dzongkhag. This site was chosen because of its close location to the Kurichhu, which is important for access to electricity and water supply. Beside this the close location to the Gyelpozhing Junior High School could bring employment for the students during the holidays. The goal of the project is "to preserve and promote the age-old Bhutanese traditional art of papermaking and increase household income of the communities in Mongar district". The project objectives and intended results by the end of 2002 are (as far as related to deysho): 1. To preserve and promote the age-old Bhutanese art of paper-making. 2. To provide training to the local communities of Mongar district on sustainable harvesting and processing of raw materials. 3. To establish a community plantation to provide raw materials for the paper unit. 4. To build linkages within and outside the country for marketing of Bhutanese paper and its products. The rationale behind the establishment for the project is that the people of Mongar traditionally have expertise in the making of handmade paper and that the Daphne trees grow there in abundance. Due to lack of skill and knowledge on sustainable harvesting and the technical know-how as well as marketing problems of the products until now done by middlemen the continuity of the art is threatened. Practically, following steps will be undertaken after the unit is established: five local women will be trained on the job and employed in the factory, the present in-charge will be the general manager, two technical persons will be sent to Nepal for training, the paper products will be marketed through the Handicrafts Emporium in Thimphu, and other outlets in and outside the country will be established as well. To achieve this the production will be based on a standardised quality control and diversification of goods to capture a wide range of potential customers. The project involves active participation from local communities. Training workshops on sustainable harvesting will be set up for the local communities (about 100 households) gathering the raw materials. A weak point in the proposal is the following: it states that 'precisely by using only the Daphne bark the regeneration of the specie is expected within one year only whereas the regeneration of Edgeworthia requires much more time'. This is contradictory to the findings presented in 2.3. Moreover the estimated cost of Nu. 8/- per kg is an unrealistic estimate.

Box 2: Deysho production in Trashhi Yangtse

Trashhi Yangtse has traditionally been the main deysho-producing dzongkhag in Bhutan. According to some sources (Dorji et al., 2000a) it was started as recently as the early 1980s when Dungkara and his family moved to Yangtse from Yongphula where deysho was already produced at the time. There is evidence however that deysho was produced there considerably earlier. Sangay Wangdi, Gembo Dorji and Jampel Wangchuk state they started their businesses in 1974. Even till date the largest number of cottage or rural household production units can be found in this dzongkhag. Out of 3,516 households in the dzongkhag, 65 are directly involved in the production of deysho (Dorji et al., 2000a). Wangda and Hadorn (1999) counted a number of 34 units however. The discrepancy can be explained by the immense fluctuation in the number of households involved in the craft, which varies not only yearly but even per month.

The units are all located in the northern two geogs of Yangtse and Bumdeling, mainly in Bumdeling, Bertang, Tshogchen, Nyangteng, Dukzam, Tarpel, Baytsamang, Beling, Phantang, Raptey, Eichen, Chorten Kora and Womanang villages. Around 260 people are involved in the production directly with another 300 people involved in collecting, drying and transporting the bark (called 'trekpa' in Dzalakha) to the producers from the southern six geogs. Wangda and Hadorn further report that a majority of the households (26 units or 75%) engage in the production during the agricultural slack season (3-4 months, November to February) as a means for generating cash income. In addition to these seasonal producers there are about 8 households with a license from the MTI (in T/Yangtse, 12 in all of Bhutan) and which are fully engaged in the production during the year. Due to weather conditions their production almost comes to a halt in the months of June, July and August.

Photo 7: Screens piled up during the lean season.

Especially households with limited agricultural land are taking up this production on permanent basis as a means to raise income. These units account for a mere 16% of the total industry value. The monetary value in absolute terms of over Nu. 1.2 million is of great benefit to them. Being labour intensive and requiring little investment (which can be met by savings of the household itself or with an initial loan or mortgaging of their products to the distributors-cum-agents, Dorji et al., 2000a) and infrastructure it is attractive for farmers to take up the business (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999).

It seems that the additional income that deysho production (and another traditional craft mainly concentrated in Yangtse dzongkhag, the making of woodbowls, phop and dhapa) in the northern two geogs Yangtse and Bumdeling, is sufficient to make a proper living for the rural population. Unlike other villages in the east, such as in southern Yangtse, Trashigang, Mongar and Pemagatshel, from where there has been a large rural-urban migration over the past two decades, the people of Yangtse and Bumdeling are able to sustain themselves and their families through self sufficiency in most foodcrops (maize, paddy, millet, buckwheat and potato), the income earned from potato, mushrooms and other cash crop sales in Samdrup Jongkhar, and the additional income from deysho and woodturning crafts. This might explain why relatively few 'Dzalap', as people from these geogs are called, can be found in government service and other occupations in the rest of the

country. This is merely a hypothesis however, towards which further research has to be done. This observation is strengthened however by the narration of Memé Wangda of Womanang village: "This enterprise is really helping us villagers in adding reasonable money to our low rural income. I feel proud. People can now even afford to buy corrugated iron steel sheets for roofing of the houses. I always pray that the market for our laboriously produced paper will continue to exist and expand further. Then our self reliance will be one stride from the start" (Sherab, 1999).

For an average temporary deysho producer in Trashy Yangtse, a financial analysis making use of a Categorical Profit and Loss Account was constructed:

Table 2.17: Categorical Profit and Loss Account for Temporary Yangtsep Deysho Producer

Net turnover		Nu. 16,800
Total Revenues		Nu. 16,800
Costs of raw materials	Nu. 4,716	
Wages and salaries	Nu. 2,700	
Sum of operational Costs	Nu. 7,416	
Profit/Loss		Nu. 9,384

These figures were calculated as follows:

Net turnover/total revenues: assuming an average production of 40 sheets per day during the effective production season of 4 months (November, December, January, February), with the total production of $40 \times 120 = 4,800$ sheets sold (no stock) the same year at the rate of Nu. 3.50/- per sheet, the net turnover (total revenues) amount to $4,800 \times \text{Nu. } 3.50/- = \text{Nu. } 16,800/-$.

Costs of raw materials: assuming that one jama of bark (3 kgs) produces an average of 40 sheets, the average price of one jama of bark is Nu. 37.50/- the total cost of bark amounts to $\text{Nu. } 37.50/- \times (4,800/40) = \text{Nu. } 4,500/-$. The royalty fee paid over this amount of bark amounts to $120 \text{ jama} \times 3 \text{ kg/jama} = 360 \text{ kg} \times \text{Nu. } 0.60/\text{kg} = \text{Nu. } 216/-$. For the temporary producers it is assumed that they collect and transport the firewood themselves. Total raw material costs thus amount to Nu. 7,416/-.

Wages and salaries: assuming that the harvesting and transportation wages add up to Nu. 7.50/- per kilo of raw material, this amounts to $\text{Nu. } 7.50 \times 360 = \text{Nu. } 2,700$. Furthermore it is assumed that all labour used in the production process is provided by the family members and that no external labour is hired, and that the bark is transported from the nearest roadhead to the production unit by the producers themselves. This results in an annual cash income of Nu. 9,384/-.

The units in Trashy Yangtse currently face a number of problems threatening their very survival and existence. Firstly, there hardly exists a market for deysho in the east itself. Small quantities of deysho are sold to local shopkeepers (who sell it at a rate of Nu. 5/- per sheet) as well as in Trashigang town (where it fetches Nu. 8/- per sheet). Most producers therefore produce on order from Thimphu, or from abroad through an agent in Thimphu. They thus heavily depend on the middlemen-distributors who are actively involved in collecting the finished products and selling them outside the dzongkhag. Not only increases this the price because of transportation costs (trucks) and commission (having a profit margin of up to 50%) but also due to the unfavourable road conditions in the monsoon summer months (roadblocks on the main highway because of landslides due to rainfall) and winter (snow) the transportation is hampered. When a certain consignment does not reach the customer abroad or in Thimphu in time, further orders will be hampered thus resulting in an irregular and uncertain income for the producer.

Secondly, due to the heavy exploitation in Yangtse dzongkhag over the past 15 years the resource basis is very limited and good stands of Daphne only occur in very remote areas. The resource base has been seriously depleted. Collection in the southern geogs of the dzongkhag still takes place but prices have soared in recent years as collectors have to cover great distances to get the bark. Therefore, the raw materials are currently supplied from Wamrong, Thrimshing and Merak and Sakteng geog in Trashigang districts. The local people of Merak and Sakteng, mainly nomadic yakherders collect the bark and sell it to a middleman in Phongme village, the nearest roadhead. The price per jama is considerably lower there than in southern Yangtse, indicating an abundance of the resource there. From Phongme the middleman transports the bark to Trashy Yangtse. These middlemen, three in total at the moment, are the same as the distributors who sell the finished products outside the dzongkhag again. They arrange all formalities like acquiring the harvesting licenses and arrange for transportation as well. Their commissions result again in a relatively high price (Nu. 14.00/- per kilogram) for

the raw materials, a price rising per year as well. Irrespective of the source of the bark, its price might already be too much for the sustainability of the deysho craft in Yangtse. Some producers now have to get their raw materials from Korila, Mongar and even as far as Pemagatshel (Dorji et al., 2000a).

Thirdly, the paper is comparatively of low quality due to the use of cotton screens and rough, unsophisticated production method resulting in resho. The demand for resho is only national, within Bhutan, and has hardly any prospects of increasing in the coming years. Therefore they should attempt to shift to tsharsho production in order to profit from the growing export markets. Moreover the producers face problems with drying the sheets, especially in the rainy season. The viability of the Yangtse deysho production very much depends on the future developments of the market prospects and adoption of new innovations.

Box 3: Deysho production in Trashigang: Ap Namgay of Yongphula (Dorji and Zangpo, 1999).

In Yongphula, under Kanglung geog in Trashigang Dzongkhag, Ap Namgay owns a small deysho factory. Since his early teens he has been involved in deysho production, having been an apprentice of Ashi Tashi in Trashigang Yangtse for six years. After that the profession deteriorated in Trashigang until the early 1990s, when a kasho from His Majesty the King, there for the Seventh Five Year Plan meeting in Trashigang, commended the following: "If you are willingly ready to start the new project on deysho making, you begin the work immediately after taking Nu. one lakh from Dasho Jigme Thinley of Yongphula, and if you happen to face any problem in the future with your project, come to Thimphu and approach me without any hesitation". After this, Ap Namgay hired a piece of land from the Trashigang Rabdey paying an annual rent of Nu. 8,000/- and there he established his unit.

The raw material is bought from the people of Gomchu, Barshong, Jomtshang and Ozorong who collect and dry the bark. The price per jama of dried bark is Nu. 20.00/- which is enough to make twenty sheets of paper. A main improvement he made in his factory is the use of polythene between the roof of the huts on whose walls he dries the sheets. The black plastic absorbs the warmth and thus enhances and fastens the drying process.

Ap Namgay has his main market located in Thimphu, the Handicrafts Emporium buying most of his sheets. There it is mainly sold to tourists at a rate of Nu. 15/- per sheet. He sells the sheets for Nu. 700/- per bundle, or a price of Nu. 7.00/- per sheet. His annual earnings amount to over Nu. 100,000.00/-. This amount enables him to sustain himself and his family, providing all his twelve grandchildren with education as well. According to him, he is yet unable to meet the demand both in quantity as well as quality. Therefore he has the wish to make different colours of sheets with the help of new technologies, and increase the supply of raw material with is the main constraint to the production level.

When looking to the future, Ap Namgay is looking for someone with the true interest and ability to take over his unit, rather than to give it in lease to someone only looking to the economic benefits it might give.

Box 4: Deysho production in Thimphu

Jungshi Handmade Paper Factory (JHP) is one of the oldest and the largest semi-mechanised deysho producers in Bhutan. The factory is located in Thimphu, on the left bank of the Thimphu above Hotel Riverview. Jungshi was established in the late eighties with the assistance of Misumi town in Japan and reopened in 1996 after the factory caught fire in January 1995. In 1996, Jungshi produced 30,000 sheets per month. To meet the demand for lower priced sheets and a wider range of products the Jungshi PMP shifted its emphasis from small scale, labour intensive manual production to machine-aided large-scale commercial production. Until July 1999 about 2,000 sheets a day were produced. From July this would increase to 20,000 sheets daily. About 100 different products were launched with prices ranging from Nu. 5.00 to Nu. 12.00. To reduce prices, cheaper raw materials such as banana stems, rice straw and waste clothes and papers are used (Kuensel, 1999e). Its production accounts for 40% of the total or a value production of Nu. 3,000,000. In 2000 JHP produces 1000 sheets per day if in full operation, and around 800 sheets per day under normal conditions. The production however depends mainly on the orders it receives from abroad. Locally sheets are supplied to several art and souvenir shops. Main market however is the export market to Europe accounting for 90% of the total demand. The monthly total production cost amount to Nu. 150,000. This consists of labour wage for 26 people of around Nu. 6-7,000/- per month, per month the factory consumes two truckloads of firewood (30-40 kilo of bark being boiled per time) and 100 kilo of soda ash imported from India. Per day the water use amounts to 10,000 litres. Electricity charge is around Nu. 400/- per day. One kg of raw material fetches around 12 sheets depending on the quality with an average waste bark of 10% taken into account. The bark costs around Nu. 10/- to Nu. 15/- per kg. The raw materials are obtained from private land owners in Gedu, Chhukha

Dzongkhag, JHP uses 70% Edgeworthia and 30% Daphne. Beside the royalty paid to the government this avoids the requirement of harvest permits. JHP uses 6 sets of imported bamboo screens from Japan, which cost Nu. 60,000 each. Now, with Japanese assistance, these screens are manufactured in Bhutan itself as well. These screens are necessary to produce tsharsho, the high quality papers. As dye to make differently coloured papers natural (vegetable) dyes as well as chemical dyes are used. The amount of dye used depends on the required intensity of the colour. Sometimes the pulp is bleached with chlorine to get a whiter coloured paper. The raw sheets fetch between Nu. 8-10/- each depending on quality. In total over 50 different varieties are produced. JHP makes deysho bags of different quality. Some bags are sold in Thimphu itself but the bulk of bags (5-10,000 per order) is meant for Druk Air (Bhutan's National Airlines). The production cost per bag is Nu. 5/- whereas the printing of the logo amounts to Nu. 3/-. The bags are sold for Nu 9/- to Nu 11.50 depending on the quality and after deduction of transportation cost etc a profit of a mere Nu. 0.10 per bag remains. The local market for recycled paper is small due to the cheaply and readily available Indian and Bangkok machine made paper bags.

4.2.3 Demand for Deysho

The local market for deysho is mainly situated in Thimphu. A distinction can be made between the final products, such as envelopes, lamp shades, notepads, file-folders, photo frames and photo albums, decorated sheets etc which mainly find their way to souvenir shops in Thimphu, and the plain deysho sheets. These find a customer in artists using them to make cards and paintings, souvenir shops and private individuals using them as wrapping material for books, purchases and presents, the religious institutions using the sheets for printing prayer books and the making of religious masks, wall paintings, 'nangzung' for statues and finally government institutions using them as parchment for important documents. The production of the small-scale industries is purely for the domestic market since their paper quality is too low to be exported. According to Dorji et al.(2000a), 'an extensive market survey reveals that deysho has grown so important due to increase in demand from the local market as well as international market'. They do not refer to which market survey however, and local demand seems to be rather low and constant.

Traditionally the 'bum' and 'domang', Buddhist prayer books that are used in the religious institutions, schools and by private individuals are printed on deysho because the paper was readily available and lasted long. Previously printing was done manually by using carved wooden printing blocks. This is still common practice in the monasteries. For mass production however modern techniques are used.

Box 5: Printing of religious texts.

In a not so distant past, there was a yearly repeating caravan of people leaving from Bhutan to Tibet loaded with deysho sheets. Part of the sheets were traded there, another part was used for the printing of religious texts and returned to Bhutan, since in Bhutan not enough printing presses were available. After the Chinese invasion of Tibet this practice stopped and Bhutan improved its own printing facilities (Dorji and Zangpo, 1999). The common deysho sheets are used for the ordinary printing of the religious texts like Jatongpa, Kabum, Kanjur and Tenjur, the holy scriptures of Mahayana Buddhism. In case sheets have become affected by fungus, which could be due to an insufficient amount of kha-re or improper storage/drying, these black sheets are used for writing the mentioned scriptures in gold letters (Dz. ser-rig).

In January 2000 a private company in Thimphu ordered for 1,200 copies of 'domang', each having 1,512 pages, for sale to be printed on deysho. The order was taken up by the Survey of Bhutan. Deysho sheets were brought from Dowang in Dokyiling, Bumthang, at a cost of Nu. 15/- per sheet. One domang consists of 76 sheets, as 20 pages can be printed on one sheet. The sheets are cut straight. After that, 20 pages from the paper master copy are printed as negative on plastic and then onto an aluminium printing plate. From there a print is made on the deysho sheets. These are then cut into separate pages and sorted out. Leftover cuttings are sent to Jungshi PMP in Thimphu. About 300 KGs had been sent until the project finished. The leftover cuttings have however not been processed, because the sheets from which the leftovers came were of relatively poor quality (the bark not having been boiled long enough).

Photo 8: Sorting out the deysho pages for 'domane' at the Survey of Bhutan.

To achieve a better insight into the national demand for deysho and the forces that might influence it, the survey provided information to run multiple regression models. Firstly, the base model given by equation 3.15 was tested to establish a function for the demand for deysho by consumers:

$$Eq. 3.15: DDE = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INC + \beta_2 OPD + \beta_3 EDU + \beta_4 HHS + \beta_5 AGE + \beta_6 PDE + \beta_7 PLA + \varepsilon_0$$

In which:

DDE = demand for deysho per month in rough sheets, with as conversion factor: 1 rough sheet = 1 decorated sheet = 5 envelopes = 2 bags = 1 file/folder, as from question 12.

INC = average income per month, as from question 15.

OPD = opinion on deysho, 'very good' = 1, 'good' = 2, 'neutral' = 3, 'bad' = 4, as from question 11.

EDU = educational background, no education = 1, non-formal education = 2, class X = 3, class XII = 4, diploma course = 5, BSc = 6, MSc = 7, as from question 17.

HHS = household size, as from question 14.

AGE = age, as from question 16.

PDE = the average price per rough sheet of deysho, which amounts to about Nu. 6/- per sheet in the East, Nu. 12/- per sheet in Thimphu, and Nu. 15/- per sheet in Phuentsholing.

PLA = place, 1 = Phuentsholing, 2 = Thimphu, 3 = East.

As for the variables, following are the assumptions:

- The influence of *INC* will be positive. With rising income, consumers will be more enabled to buy the relatively expensive deysho products.
- When *OPD* is more positive, the amount of deysho bought will probably be higher. People who have a positive attitude towards are more likely to spend money on it as well.

- With higher EDU levels people might be more aware of the importance of the deysho craft for Bhutan, and the importance of the production mainly for the small-scale producers' livelihood. Moreover, higher education often goes together with higher income.
- As HHS increases, there will be more people in the household who might use deysho products. However, income constraints might prevent them from buying the products.
- With decreasing AGE, consumers might have less interest in deysho (and the traditional crafts in general). However, use of certain deysho products especially envelopes might be higher among the younger generation. Higher age could mean larger household size as well.
- Decreasing PDE will probably stimulate people to buy the products.
- Regarding PLA, consumers in the traditional deysho producing eastern dzongkhag will probably consume more deysho than consumers in the westernised towns.

The model was run in SPSS 9.0 as a linear regression model. After testing of 35 models the best fitting model was chosen to be the model in equation 3.16 (standard deviation of coefficient estimate between brackets):

$$\text{Eq. 3.16: } DDE = 2.431 + 0.0001906 * INC - 0.711 * OPD$$

(0.422) (0.000) (0.217)

with an R² of 0.337.

The mean of the dataset was 2.750 with a median of 2.000. Table 2.18 gives further characteristics of the regression:

Table 2.18: ANOVA Table of the model in equation 3.16.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24.793	2	12.396	10.158	.000 ^b
	Residual	48.812	40	1.220		
	Total	73.605	42			

a. Predictors: (Constant), OPD, INC

b. Dependent Variable: DDE

The low R² and the limited number of variables significant in explaining DDE are reason for concern over the viability of the model. Especially the fact that, against expectations, the price of deysho turned out not to be of influence on the demand was surprising. After substituting INC and OPD with their national means (INC = Nu. 5,783/-, ●PD = 1,539) a demand of 2.43 sheets of deysho per person per month results. Aggregation to a total national demand was done by multiplying this figure with the total number of households in the surveyed regions in Bhutan. The only figure available on this was the 1995 count of a total of 11,245 households (Policy and Planning Division, 1995). So the total national demand for deysho can be assumed to be around 27,325 sheets per month or 327,904 sheets per year. With a total production of 847,040 sheets this means that 519,136 sheets find their way to other demanders at the national market and the remainder is exported.

Bhutanese handmade paper enjoys a growing demand from abroad. Since the foreign market demands high-quality paper and added-value products such as envelopes, photo frames and photo albums, decorated sheets etc the main suppliers for these products are the two producers in Thimphu, Jungshi and Mangala. Their products have been exported in small quantities to countries like the United Kingdom, United States, Germany, The Netherlands, Nepal, Japan, Sweden and Austria. About 90% of Jungshi's produce is exported to Europe with only 10% sold in the local market. The United States and Australia have thus far been little explored (Kuensel, 1999e). Further developing the export market includes finding proper outlets and guaranteeing a regular supply and quality.

Products for the export market need to be of high quality. According to the producers, the export market is essential for the viability of the deysho production in Bhutan, since the local demand is too small to face the growing production. Bhutanese deysho products exported to Japan have to face competition from the local Japanese produce, which is generally of higher quality. In other export markets, the cheaper 'handmade' papers from Nepal and India (where production is mainly machine-aided) limit the demand for the products from Bhutan.

Considering the importance that the export market has for the producers of deysho even to the extent that without increased export opportunities the viability of the craft is questionable, steps have to be undertaken to promote deysho products abroad.

4.2.4 Attitudes towards Deysho

The survey resulted in some interesting insights in what the Bhutanese people think about deysho. Being one of the traditional crafts of Bhutan it could be expected that most people have a positive attitude towards it. However, the price of deysho as compared to other paper as well as the disregard and unfortunately deteriorating respect and interest of the younger generation for Bhutan's culture and traditions (mainly in Thimphu, Phuentsholing and other towns) influences this positive attitude.

49.4% of the surveyed people considered deysho as 'very good', 35.6% as 'good', 11.5% has a neutral attitude and 3.4% considers it 'bad'. An overwhelming majority of the population, 86% has a positive attitude towards deysho. The 3.4% of the people having a negative attitude clearly state the relatively high costs and the uselessness after it gets wet as the reasons for their negative opinion. Graph 3 shows the opinions on deysho.

Graph 3: Nation-wide average opinions on deysho.

Consumers generally have a slightly more positive attitude ('good' and 'very good', 92%) towards deysho than suppliers (81%). Consumers in Phuentsholing have a slightly more negative attitude (80%) whereas 90% of the suppliers there has a good or very good opinion on deysho. In Thimphu this is just the opposite, consumers 90% good and very good versus shopkeepers 80%. In the East, in the traditionally deysho producing dzongkhag of Trashigang, Trashi Yangtse and Bunthang, 100% of the consumers and 80% of the shopkeepers has a positive attitude towards the craft, with 16% of the suppliers having a neutral opinion and only 4% having a negative attitude.

4.2.5 Paper Recycling as Alternative

The paper recycling plant in Bjemina, near Thimphu, was originally started as machine-aided production of deysho. This shifting of emphasis from small scale, labour intensive manual production to machine-aided large scale commercial production was fuelled by the aspiration of the owner of Jungshi Handmade paper factory to meet the demand for lower priced sheets and a wider range of products. The initial investment was Nu. 4.50 million. The location on which the factory is situated in Bjemina is part of an industrial estate rented from the government at a rate of Nu. 0.50 per square feet. Total area is 25,000 square feet. Until July 1999 about 2,000 sheets a day were produced. From July this would increase to 20,000 sheets daily. About 100 different products were launched with prices ranging from Nu. 5.00 to Nu. 12.00. To reduce prices, cheaper raw materials such as banana stems, rice straw and waste clothes and papers are used (Kuensel, 1999e).

Making use of the existing equipment in this factory the process shifted to the recycling of waste paper as of October, 1999. The owner of JHP, after the suggestion of NEC, thought that considering the immense amounts of waste paper generated at schools, offices and other institutions in and around Thimphu this would be environmentally a good option and moreover hoped to increase his revenues (Tenzin, 2000). Instead of ending up burnt or disposed at the Mimalakha landfill, daily waste paper from schools and offices in Thimphu were recycled there. The offices provided it free of cost whereas other charges Nu. 18/- per kilo (Kuensel, 1999g) and to enhance the schools' income it was bought from them for Nu 3-4/- per kilo depending on the quantity (Tenzin, 2000). Until October 30th 1999, 9.5 tonnes of discarded paper had thus been collected and turned into sheets (Kuensel, 1999g). The plain recycled sheets and paper bags were priced at Nu. 1/- to Nu. 4/- each in the local market. This is at a profit margin of only 2%. The market for recycled paper is mainly local and production greatly exceeded demand. The lack of demand is mainly explicable by the competition from Indian made paper, which sells at a relatively much lower price of Nu. 15-16/- per kilo (Tenzin, 2000). Design sheets were made from recycled paper as well with bits of ferns or petals of marigold or seasonal flowers. They were priced at Nu. 12/- to Nu. 25/- depending on quality and their expected markets were mainly abroad (Kuensel, 1999g).

The lack of demand for recycled paper both inside Bhutan as well as abroad has led to a current situation in which the paper recycling plant no longer produces recycled paper. No recycled paper had been sold after the inception of production. The stock of recycled paper amounted to 78,000 sheets, of which 40-50,000 sheets have been mixed with bark and recycled to make deysho. At present, the factory uses raw bark and with the aid of the machines processes this into deysho sheets, mainly for orders from abroad. Around 2,000 sheets are produced per day in 4 shifts of 500 sheets each. The price per sheet comes to Nu. 5/- for the normal thickness to Nu. 10-15/- for thick quality ones. The number of employees is currently 8. Per month the electricity charge is Nu. 5-6,000/- per month, with a water use of over 50,000 litres per day. This water comes from an own source as well as from the government water supply. Most of the water in the process is being used for cleaning the roller band from remains of pulp. This water is however collected and recycled in the agitator (approximately waste water: clean water 2/3:1/3). Bleach is sometimes used to make the paper whiter, and soda-ash consumption is around 24 kilos per day. Per week one truckload of fuel wood is consumed, bought at a rate of between Nu. 2,700/- and Nu. 2,800/- per load. The factory doesn't make profit and even doesn't manage to break even. However production is still going on. The production cost are met from the profit made in the sister factory in Thimphu (Tenzin, 2000).

Production process (see also Diagram III in Annex 2): . In the plant machines imported from India are used in the production process. Following description is for the current process of making deysho with the aid of machines. However, for the waste paper recycling process, the cleaning and boiling is replaced by manual shredding, and 100 to 150 kilo's of shredded paper are ground in the bark grinder. After this the process is similar to that mentioned below. To make design sheets, the pulp is led from the agitator to a semi-automatic moulding machine, where it is led onto bamboo screens after which the design materials are added and the sheet is dried. Damaged sheets are reprocessed (Kuensel, 1999g, Tenzin, 2000).

Cleaning and boiling: the bark is washed and 80 to 100 kilo's are boiled for 3 to 4 hours in a cooking pot fuelled by softwood. Soda ash is added.

Grinding: in a bark grinder the boiled bark is ground to a fine pulp. Starch, washing detergent, dye and when necessary bleach are added.

Churning: the mashed pulp is lead to an agitator where the pulp is mixed with water and churned into a finer paste.

Vibrating: from the agitator the pulp is pumped to a vibrator which shakes the pulp and determines the amount of pulp and the thickness in which it is released onto the roller, eventually determining the thickness of the sheet. The vibrator also segregates the pulp from excess water, foam and dirt.

Forming of sheets: From the vibrator the pulp is released on the roller band of the paper-moulding machine in equal portions in a long strip. On a big round roller two sheets are formed at a time with new layers of pulp being pressed from the roller hand onto the roller. In between the sheets there is a 1/2-cm wide gap which enables the two separate sheets to be pulled off and dried.

Drying: The sheets are piled and naturally dried, sometimes after the water is pressed out in an automatic press. The dryers are hardly used. Drying takes places on the concrete floors in-and outside the factory.

Photo 9: The wet-rollers on which the sheets are formed.

Investment decisions: As compared to the semi-mechanical production in JHP the (former) paper recycling plant uses much larger amounts of water, firewood and soda ash. It is therefore less environmentally friendly than the household- and semi-mechanised production of deysho. In order to reduce fuel wood consumption the owner is currently looking for funds to replace the wood-fuelled oven by an electrical oven. The cost of this would amount to Nu. 230,000/- excluding transportation and installation charges (Tenzin, 2000). This decision is evaluated under 1.

From environmental point of view a water treatment plant is also needed to enhance the recycling of water within the production process. The water used for boiling can currently not be used for other purposes since it contains alkali ash, bark and dirt. Filtration can make it useful for recycling. After treatment the water can be used to mix with pulp in the agitator or to clean the roller bands of the mould machine. A water treatment installation would cost around Nu. 500,000/- (Tenzin, 2000). This decision is evaluated under 2.

Finally, the paper recycling process was stopped due to a lack of markets for the products. However, once higher quality paper is produced (thinner, smoother), price decreases to an acceptable level and proper marketing strategies are applied the products will most probably find their way in Thimphu, mainly in government offices and institutions. For that reason investment in new equipment is needed. With the aid of a fully automatic production process thinner and smoother sheets can be made from waste paper which can be used for printing and other purposes as well and might serve as a locally produced substitute for the Indian made papers. In total 6 new machines are required to make paper recycling an environmentally friendly and profitable operation: an auto-dryer with roller band ensuring continuous supply from the mould machine, an automatic boiler to reduce the consumption of fuel wood, a new agitator, a conveyor, a water treatment facility and an hydro-pulper guaranteeing a continuous supply of pulp. This investment of total Nu. 3,200,000/- would imply a monthly processing capacity of 4 to 5 tons of waste paper. However, the owner faces a serious financial constraint. The investment of Nu. 4,500,000/- made last year with the aid of bank loans has not been able to earn itself back and therefore new investments are not within the companies' financial reach. To see whether the investment would be worthwhile to undertake at all, this investment is evaluated under 3.

1. *Automatic (electric) boiler*: the initial investment I_0 amounts to Nu. 230,000/-, transportation and installation charges excluded. Assuming that these charges would amount to another Nu. 15,000/-, the total investment amounts to Nu. 245,000/-. The benefits of the investment are a reduction in the use of fuel wood. However the investment also implies increased electricity costs. Assuming a truckload of firewood to cost Nu. 2,750/- and a yearly productive period of 50 weeks, the total savings on fuel wood amount to: 1 truckload per week * 50 weeks * Nu. 2,750/- per truckload = Nu. 137,500/- per year. Current electricity consumption amounts to an average of Nu. 5,500/- per month. Assuming that the electric boiler increases this amount to Nu. 8,000/- per month⁶, the total costs of the increase in electricity consumption amount to (Nu. 8,000-Nu.5,500) * 12 = Nu. 30,000/-. Thus the total net benefits of the investment are Nu. 137,500-Nu. 30,000 = Nu. 107,500/- per year. Assuming these benefits to be constant over the total economic operating life, assuming this economic operating life to be 10 years, a 0 residual value, linear yearly depreciation (i.e. Nu. 245,000/10 years = Nu. 24,500/- per year) and an effective interest rate of 12% on industrial investments⁷, the investment selection criteria can be calculated as:

Payback-period: Nu. 245,000/Nu. 107,500 = 2 years, 3 ½ months.

Average Return on Investment: (Nu. 107,500-Nu. 24,500)/Nu. 122,500 = 67.8%.

Net Present Value: Nu. 107,500 * $a_{10|12}$ - Nu. 245,000 = Nu. 362,399/-.⁸

Internal Rate of Return: Nu. 245,000 - Nu. 107,500 * $a_{10|i}$ = 0 when $i = 42.5\%$.

Considering the relatively short payback-period, the high ARI (5 2/3 times the interest rate), the high positive NPV and the high IRR, it is recommendable that under the made assumptions the investment should be done.

⁶ In absence of information on real electricity use this is a realistic assumption, considering that there are currently already 5 other electrical machines in function in the factory and that electricity is relatively cheap in Bhutan due to the hydropower projects.

⁷ Official RGOB rate, 2000.

⁸ In which $a_{n|i}$ is equivalent to $[1 - 1/(1+i)^n]/i$, i being the discount rate and n the economic operating life of the investment, refer to Bruins and Pinke, 1996.

2. *Water Treatment Installation:* the initial investment of the water treatment installation amounts to Nu. 500,000/-. Let's assume this investment manages to reduce the water use by 30% since the water from the boiler can now be recycled in the agitator and the roller bands. If it is further assumed that 60% of the water is being bought from the government at a rate of Nu. 1.45/- per 1,000 litres⁹ and that the remaining 40% comes from the own water source. The effective days of production are assumed to be 280 days per year. The electricity use of the installation is assumed to be Nu. 1,000/- per month, or Nu. 12,000/- per year. The investment is again assumed to have a 0 residual value, linear yearly depreciation and the interest rate is assumed to be 12%. The reduced costs of water consumption are 50,000 litres per day * 0.30 * 0.60 * 280 days * Nu. 0.00145/- per litre = Nu. 3,654/-. The total net benefits of the investment are then Nu. 3,645 - Nu. 12,000 = -Nu. 8,346/- per year. Purely based on criteria of economic efficiency, a project with negative yearly net benefits should not be executed. Therefore, without considering benefits from the environmental point of view, this investment is not advisable.

3. *New production technology:* the total investment for a completely new production technology, including the wastewater treatment facility and electric boiler, would amount to Nu. 3,200,000/-. The net benefits of the wastewater treatment facility were estimated at -Nu. 8,346/-. The net benefits of the electric boiler were estimated at Nu. 107,550/-. Assuming that the new technologies result in an average monthly increase of Nu. 2,000/-, the total increase in electricity costs will amount to Nu. 24,000/- per year. The new technologies are expected to lead to an increase in production. This increase is estimated as follows: previously a daily average of 125 kilos of waste paper was made into 2,000 sheets. After the investment the capacity is expected to increase to 4,500 kilos per month, at an average of $(280/12 = 23\frac{1}{3})$ productive days per month this is 193 kilos per day which can be made into 3,085 sheets per day. Assuming that this increase of 1,085 sheets per day can be completely sold locally at a rate of Nu. 3/- per sheet, and an effective yearly production during 280 days, the increased production benefits amount to Nu. 3/- * 280 * 1085 = Nu. 911,400/- per year. Assuming further that the new investment requires the hiring of 3 additional employees at the rate of Nu. 175/- per day during 280 days, the increased labour costs are Nu. 175/- * 3 * 280 = Nu. 147,000/- yearly. Considering an average cost of Nu. 3.50/- per kilo of waste paper if bought from schools the yearly increase in cost of raw materials amounts to Nu. 3.50 * ((193-125) * 280) = 19,040 kilos = Nu. 66,640/-. The investment is again assumed to have a 0 residual value, linear yearly depreciation and the interest rate is assumed to be 12%. Thus the total net benefits of the investment amount to (Nu. 911,400 - Nu. 8,346 + Nu. 107,550) - (Nu. 147,000 + Nu. 66,640 + Nu. 24,000) = Nu. 772,964/- per year. The investment criteria now become:

Payback period: Nu. 3,200,000 / Nu. 772,964/- = 4 years, 1 $\frac{3}{4}$ month.

Average return on investment: (Nu. 772,964 - Nu. 320,000) / Nu. 1,600,000 = 28.3%.

Net Present Value: Nu. 772,964 * $a_{10|12}$ - Nu. 3,200,000 = Nu. 1,167,419/-.

Internal Rate of Return: Nu. 3,200,000 - Nu. 772,964 * $a_{10|i}$ = 0 when i = 20.5%.

Considering the relatively short payback-period, the high ARI (2.4 times the interest rate), the high positive NPV and the high IRR, it is recommendable that under the made assumptions the investment should be done.

⁹ Thimphu City Corporation

4.2.6 Environmental Impact of Deysho Production

4.2.6 Effects on the Raw Material Supply

There are several factors that influence the total supply of raw materials:

Total consumption: The total consumption of raw materials is currently estimated at 100 tons yearly with an increasing trend. This increasing trend means an increased pressure on the natural resource at the base of deysho production: *Daphne* and *Edgeworthia*. Without proper measures, the future supply could be seriously at risk.

Sites of harvesting: some sites are over-harvested whereas some are still unexploited. In Northern Trashi Yangtse it is almost impossible to get reasonable amounts of bark at accessible places, and the stock in Southern Yangtse is quickly getting depleted as well (see also Annex 1). The other locations still have reasonable stocks, but improper harvesting can quickly deplete them. Research into other possible sites has to take place to relieve the pressure on the traditional collection areas. Comparison of height and forest type from the maps provided by the Land Use Planning Section (1997) show that particularly the unexploited forests of Northern Dagana (Tseza), Southern Paro, Southern Wangdue Phodrang (Daga, Athang), Trongsa, Bunthang, Lhuentse, Samdrup Jougkhar (Martshala, Shingkar Lauri and Serthig), Trashigang (Kangpara), Mongar (Ngatshang, Saleng) might hold large stocks of *Daphne sureil*, *Daphne bholua* and *Edgeworthia gardneri*. Biggest problem will be accessibility of the harvest sites and transportation to the production units. The mentioned regions are remote, sparsely populated and poorly connected to the road network (which are exactly the reasons for their large forest cover).

Harvesting methods: According to Hadorn and Wangda (1999), March to June are considered the best harvesting time in Bhutan as the plants have not yet collected water in the stems which makes it easier to peel the bark off. Alternatively Dorji and Zangpo (1999) report spring till autumn or the second till eighth month of the Bhutanese calendar as harvesting time. Harvesting is carried out on an ad hoc basis with techniques varying from district to district. There are two different harvesting methods:

- Partially cutting through the stem of the plant at a height of one meter or more above the ground and then peeling off the bark down to the root collar. This method reduces the chances for regeneration but might encourage root suckering.
- Cutting the stem through at 2-15 cm above ground level and peeling off the bark afterwards. By leaving the stump intact this method seems the best way as it will allow regeneration to take place. This method should therefore be promoted and spread among the harvesters to sustain the resource.

In Bhutan most harvesting is done by the first method thus decreasing the chances of natural regeneration. In some parts however the stem is cut with a knife before stripping the bark off. In the southern geogs of Yangtse the depletion of the resource has led to an even more destructive harvesting method: uprooting the whole plant as root bark weighs more than stem bark (but is useless for production of deysho) and thus the collector earns more.

4.2.7 Fuel wood Consumption

Fuel wood is another important raw material in the paper making process as the barks of the *Daphne* and *Edgeworthia* need to be boiled for a long time. This fuel wood consumption has a direct impact on the surrounding forests. FAO (1991) estimates that 7 kg of fuel wood is consumed per kg of raw material. Since the total annual raw material requirement is estimated at almost 100,000 kilo this results in an annual fuel wood consumption for the paper production of 700 tons. Dorji et al. (2000a) come to an estimate for Yangtse alone, taking three back loads of 35 kg of firewood (wet, or 20 KGs dry) daily during the production season (three months effectively), which results in an annual consumption of 209.3 tons. However these figures are nothing more than rough estimates. The household level producers prefer hardwood to softwood, as ash alkali obtained from hard wood ash is of better quality for the softening of the bark. During the time of the paper production, the rural household units keep the oven burning for over 16 hours per day. It has to be stated however that in the smaller units the branches from which the bark has been stripped off are themselves used as firewood and for obtaining the alkali ashes. Firewood, having become scarce in the immediate surrounding of the units, now has to be bought from contractors. This makes firewood a considerable production cost.

The fuel wood use in the two semi-mechanised units amounts to three truckloads per week whereas the mechanised production of deysho in the former paper recycling plant consumes one truckload per week. The paper recycling process is relatively more environmentally friendly since the paper does not have to be boiled but is directly ground and mashed to pulp. The use of hardwood for the semi-mechanised units is not permitted and therefore they rely on softwood.

4.2.8 Water Consumption and Pollution

Water consumption in the deysho production processes is very high. Water is not only used for soaking, washing and boiling the bark, but also for the pulping, churning and moulding. Regarding total water consumption data are unavailable from most producers. Jungshi in Thimphu uses 10,000 litres of water per day in the semi-mechanised process, or 2,800,000 litres at an effective yearly production during 280 days. The mechanised deysho production as well as the paper recycling in Bjemina consumes 50,000 litres of water per day. One jama, equivalent to 3 kilos of bark consumes 40 to 60 litres of water for the boiling process alone (Sherub, 1999). For all the household level producers together this implies a water consumption of between 731,500 and 1,097,200 litres per year and for the two semi-mechanised producers of between 600,000 and 900,000 litres per year. The actual consumption of the semi-mechanised producers is with an estimated 2,800,000 litres annually for Jungshi considerably higher and it can thus be assumed that total water use is around 3 to 4½ the amount of water used for the boiling of the bark alone, thus putting total water consumption of the deysho production in Bhutan at an estimated 5,326,000 to 11,324,000 litres annually.

Water is a free and abundant resource in most places in Bhutan although seasonal fluctuations in rainfall patterns can lead to temporary droughts in certain areas. Most rural household deysho units are located near the streams (e.g. Kholong Chu in Trashi Yangtse) thus guaranteeing a continuous water supply for the production. The producers in Thimphu are charged Nu. 1.45/- per 1,000 litres by the Thimphu City Corporation. Bjemina currently has no water metres so the water is free there.

Water consumption, both at the rural household level as at the semi-mechanised level and in the paper recycling plant, can be reduced considerably by reusing waste water as indicated in Diagram I, II and III in Annex 2. For the rural household producers simple methods can be applied to clear the wastewater from the soaking, cooking, washing, churning and moulding steps. A sieve made of coarse bamboo (Phrokpa) can strain the dirt, soil and bark residues from the water that can then be reused. There is however no incentive for these producers to reuse the water, being a freely available resource, at the cost of extra manpower and time. The reduction of water consumption in the semi-mechanised processes and the paper recycling plant is a more complex issue due to the use of various chemicals that can affect the paper quality if they are not removed before reuse and therefore waste water treatment installations have to be installed.

In contrast to other paper production methods, especially the large-scale industrial methods in use in the West causing chemical and thermal pollution of waterways, the small-scale production of deysho in Bhutan hardly has any adverse environmental effects resulting from the waste water. The wastewater is not filtered but directly streams into the nearest waterway. Harmful components in the wastewater of the semi-mechanised units can result from the use of soda ash/alkali water, chemical dyes, gluc, and chlorine for bleaching. Secondly the water coming from the boiled bark has a higher temperature and can thus lead to thermal pollution. Thirdly, the remains of bark fibres and excess pulp can lead to clogging of drains.

For local units in Trashy Yangtse the wastewater ends up in the Kulong Chu or Bumdeling Chu. Compared to the enormous amounts of water flowing through these rivers the pollution caused by these small scale deysho units is negligible, both thermal as well as chemical pollution. Their ash filtrate has a pH ranging from 10 to 18, and though high this has negligible harmful environmental effects (Sherub, 1999).

For the Thimphu units located on a slope above the Thim Chu the location means that by the time the water reaches the river it has a normal temperature. The used alkali filtrate (having a pH ranging from 8.3 to 23.1) sediments in the soil over which the wastewater stream runs. Although the pH is very high, due to dilution the water is not considered harmful to the soil organisms in the quantities used. The National Environment Commission has checked the water and send water samples to Idaho, USA, where it was tested. No harmful compounds were found to exceed the US standards (Tenzin, 2000). However the pH discharge standards for most industries in Bhutan are supposed to be between the range of pH 6 to 9 according to the National Environment Commission (1999d/e). However since the NEC stated they had done water sampling and testing and had no complaints no further testing was done. The Thimphu City Corporation has also no complaints since the wastewater does not affect any water source but flows into the Thim Chu. Moreover no serious complaints have come thus far from the residents nearby (Phuntsho, 2000). Discharge standards of chlorine in Bhutan are recommended at 0.5 mg/litre and temperature increase has to be below 3 °C.

Own observation in the early morning showed a visible waste stream coming from Jungshi factory, containing red dye and smelling of chlorine. Beside that the wastewater contains pulp, which when it gets stuck behind branches or stones accumulates and thus can lead to clogging of the drain. On several visits especially during the rainy season it was observed that the wastewater could not go through the drain and had flooded the adjoining road.

5 Discussion

5.1 The Impact of Plastic Ban

The decrease of the plastic use has direct positive effects on the environment. The greatly reduced littering of streets and the landscape has contributed to less visible pollution as well as less clogging of water drains. Health risks to livestock and wildlife from the littered plastic have also decreased. The long-term effects will be even more important. Leakage of harmful substances such as heavy metals to soil and water, resulting from disposed plastics, will decrease over time as the stock does not increase. This in turn reduces the health risks on humans, livestock and wildlife. The substitutes that have taken the place of plastics are less harmful to the environment.

The Bhutanese public was more or less unprepared for the ban on the use of plastics and after it came into force in June 1999 people had to suddenly switch from the convenient, ever available plastics to other substitutes. The eradication of the plastic use therefore took time and only one year later it can be said that, although plastics have not completely disappeared from the streets, at least a good number of substitutes have taken the place of the bulk of plastics.

A Bhutanese proverb says:

འཇམ་རྗེ་འཇམ་ན་ཕྱི་གིས་ཡང་རྒྱ་ལུ་འཕྱར།

(Jam rā jān pcigi yā 'kän lu pchar), or: "Even flour will stick too the roof of the mouth if it is too fine". It means, that if rules and regulations imposed on people, or the implementation of these rules and regulations, are too lenient, even the commoners will revolt against them. This proverb very much counts for the plastic ban. With the MTI not releasing information regarding the fining of violators of the plastic ban it was difficult to say anything on the enforcement of the ban by MTI inspectors. However, from the survey that was conducted a clear thing regarding the fining of people not adhering to the plastic ban can be concluded. Despite the fact that almost 10% of the shopkeepers indicated they still distribute plastics, only one shopkeeper (in eastern Bhutan) had been fined twice for doing so. It is clear that the inspections by the MTI are not stringent enough and that the implementation of the ban is quite weak. Although the ban seems to have large positive impacts regarding the reduction in plastic use, this is mainly due to the peoples' own adherence to it, and not due to strict enforcement by the concerned authorities. Thus, although it is a direct government regulation, its practical working is more like an indirect government regulation in which the individuals themselves adjust their behaviour and the government only provides incentives. It is suggested that the MTI now steps up the inspection to apprehend the remaining perpetrators and ensure a full implementation of the ban.

Deysho bags, making up a mere % of the total substitute use, have yet to develop as a proper alternative for plastic bags. Their price is too high for either shopkeepers to provide or consumers to buy. Their production cost even when produced in bulk can not become much lower. Especially compared to the other alternatives like cheap single use plastic bags from India, it has little chance to develop as substitute. The initial hope the deysho producers expressed in Kuensel therefore has not become reality and most probably will not as well.

མ་ཀླབན་མི་ཤོག། མ་སྒྲབན་མི་གོ།

In Dzongkha, there is a saying: (Ma 'chân mi phô, ma 'lân mi go), or, if the bow is not drawn, the target will not be hit. It refers to things that are not explained and therefore will not be understood either. It applies to the plastic ban as well. The introduction of the plastic ban was most unfortunately not accompanied by an awareness campaign regarding the harmful consequences of the use of plastics and their indiscriminate disposal and littering. Although reasons for establishing the ban were given in Kucnscl, this message has not reached the larger part of the Bhutanese society. However, it is not too late and the littering behaviour of the Bhutanese people still leaves a lot of room for educational messages. Whether it is plastic, paper or another type of product that is being improperly disposed of, it is not the packaging that is at issue but rather the human behaviour behind the tossing of the trash that needs to be addressed (American Plastics Council, 1999).

5.2 Ensuring the Sustainability of Deysho Production

5.2.1 Decreasing Negative Environmental Impacts of Deysho Production

There is currently an annual demand for Daphne and Edgeworthia bark of about 100 tons per year with an increasing trend. To make sure the increasing demand can be met in the future and to protect growing areas from being overexploited the development of the resource basis as well as the demand have to be observed. In order to guarantee the sustainable use of the Daphne and Edgeworthia resources it is important to take the right management measures. Therefore, following recommendations have been put up:

Optimal harvest time and harvesting methods: the optimal harvest time for a timber species is that point in time where the mean annual increment culminates, considering only the wood production and no other features such as quality, market price, ecology, harvesting cost. If this would be adopted for Daphne and Edgeworthia species the bark should be harvested when the mean annual increment of the dry bark weight is culminating which seems to be the case far beyond 15 years for Edgeworthia and far beyond 30 years for Daphne. Most trees in the areas where harvest takes place never reach this age. Therefore other aspects of paper quality (bark from smaller trees is said to give better paper) and of harvesting (bark of bigger trees is more difficult to strip off, Hadorn and Wangda, 1999). According to the producers themselves, the trees are ready to be harvested after a period of three years. These young plants give a bark that can be used for the production of good quality paper in high demand in the market. The bark of old plants is too hard and difficult to cook, giving a poor paper quality. Therefore, one third of old bark is mixed with two thirds of young bark to make the paper (Dorji and Zangpo, 1999). According to Hadorn and Wangda (1999) a target diameter of 8cm seems to be adequate, which is reached at an age of about 7 years for Edgeworthia and 15 years for Daphne.

Resource depletion: At the national level, resource degradation at the moment seems not to be the case. The wide geographical distribution provides a natural supply positive against the current demand. At the local level however the depletion of the resource is obvious. In Trashy Yangtse the resource stock has been completely depleted near the factories and only isolated stands in remote places remain.

The Forest and Nature Conservation Rules (2000) give a clear directive aimed at preventing the depletion of *Daphne* and *Edgeworthia*. Section 67 page 51 states:

"(3) Commercial harvesting permits under this section (traditional uses of certain wild plants and other species) shall not be granted as to any species whose population is considered threatened as a result of the current level of harvesting"

Although the species population is not threatened at national level, this section should be implemented to prevent the depletion at local level as is the case in Trashi Yangtse at the moment and as might occur in various other harvesting areas as well.

Harvesting of Daphne and Edgeworthia: The harvesting of the bark of *Daphne* and *Edgeworthia* trees for the production of deysho can not be separated from the broader framework of forestry related activities in Bhutan. Although compared to commercial logging and other large-scale forestry activities the bark harvesting plays a minor role, the preceding paragraph makes clear that without proper management it can lead to depletion of the resource within a couple of decades.

To limit the impact on the environment the Forest and Nature Conservation Act of 1995 and the Forest and Nature Conservation Rules of 2000 provide a framework under which the harvesting of forest products should take place. Regarding deysho however there is no clear-cut and to the point policy. In fact, anyone who obtains a permit can harvest *Daphne* and *Edgeworthia* and as long as the royalty fee of Nu. 0.60 per kilo is paid there is no restriction on from where, in which way or how much is harvested.

An inventory on an area sampling is the only way that leads to a more or less appropriate estimate of the supply of the resource. A nation-wide inventory with information on the different regions would give an accurate result for *Daphne* and *Edgeworthia*. It is however too costly compared to the total income generated by the paper production. Only after establishment of a national forest inventory the inventory on the availability of *Daphne* and *Edgeworthia* can be established. The result of this inventory however will include areas where harvesting is not possible due to inaccessibility or remoteness. Therefore, the resource should be sustainably managed in the harvesting areas especially. Considering the target diameter of 8cm reached at an age of about 7 years for *Edgeworthia* and 15 years for *Daphne*, this is the time a harvested area should be allowed to regenerate until it is harvested again. Issuing harvesting permits for certain areas taking this into account will promote the sustainability of the resource in that area (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999).

The Forest and Nature Conservation Rules of 2000 will regulate commercial harvesting of NTFP including *Daphne* and *Edgeworthia* in Bhutan. The exact classification of the species is not well defined. Considering the age-old tradition of paper making in Bhutan and the promotion the craft deserves it would be logical to list the species as 'certain wild plants and other species for traditional use'. This category includes "those species listed as 'species for traditional use' and may be amended to include other species that are determined to be of important traditional use in Bhutan".

Section 67, "Traditional Uses of Certain Wild Plants and Other Species" page 51 states:

"(2) Commercial harvesting of wild plants shall be conducted only with a harvesting permit, issued by the Department (of Forestry); and such permits shall be required under Chapter V for the trade and transit of forest produce."

Furthermore, section 84 (7) (b) states clearly the penalty for offence of the previous section, namely:

"illegal harvesting and marketing of species having traditional uses, as described under section 67 of these Rules, shall be subject to a fine of not more than Nu. 5,000/- plus confiscation of all specimens, or forest produce so harvested"

The cottage industry entrepreneurs submit their quantified annual requirement of Daphne bark along with the specification of locality of collection, to the territorial range officer (TRO) of the district. The range personnel inspect and inventory the production probability of the identified sites. The requisition is put forward to the territorial division, with the report addressing the availability of the resource attached. The division issues the clearance to the territorial range officer, who only endorses the permit after having received the full royalty amount.

Regeneration and cultivation: Daphne spp. regenerate naturally through seeds and root-suckers. Artificial propagation through seeds is possible but seeds have an extremely short viability and they store badly. Vegetative propagation through semi-hardwood cuttings is considered the most successful method. Propagation through layering (bending over of long side branches, wounding them and covering them with soil) is also possible (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999).

The option of cultivation has been suggested by Jungshi and will allow demand to be met even when natural supply is too low. One of the main objectives of a plantation is constancy of the supply at a maximum productivity. Monitoring and management will hence be carried out much more careful than in natural growing areas. Choice of the best site and establishing of the optimal growing conditions will significantly increase the productivity per area. Modelling with the growth equation and assumptions on plantation age, Hadorn and Wangda, 1999 came up with the following results: if only Daphne bark was demanded a total cultivated area of 541 ha would be required. If only Edgeworthia bark was demanded a total area of only 206 ha would be sufficient. However, since the total demand in Bhutan consists of 70% for Daphne and 30% for Edgeworthia, a total plantation area of 440 ha would be requested. A reduction of this area could be expected if trees were harvested at a higher age and if paper producers could be encouraged to use a higher amount of Edgeworthia bark.

Jungshi's proposal, currently under consideration for approval by the MOA, would firstly imply a trial plantation of 3 to 4 acres planted with mulberry seeds imported from Japan. Mulberry is chosen because it is a faster growing tree, which can be harvested after one year as opposed to three years for Daphne and Edgeworthia. The native mulberry species does not produce good quality fibre. A UNDP grant has been given under the Partners in Development Programme, amounting to Nu. 1,000,000/-. Eventually 30 to 40 acres of plantation is the aim. The location that was chosen is private land (in the future expansion on government land if approved) in the Gedu/Makaibari/Takti area in Chukha Dzongkhag.

A major problem that might occur in the approval of the proposal lies in the fact that the import and commercial cultivation of a non-native species (Japanese mulberry or *Morus* spp.) will meet resistance from MOA. The import of this species can lead to uncontrollable spreading and disturbance of the native plant communities and before any proper study into the nature of the species, multiplication methods and ways to prevent its spreading beyond the cultivated area is done it is not recommendable to start the project. Import of thus far unknown plant diseases that might affect native species is another consideration. Examples in other parts of the world have shown what the introduction of a non-native species can do to the original flora and fauna.

Introduction of Japanese Mulberry should therefore be considered as second option only. The economical benefits derived from it (earlier harvesting time than the native Daphne and Edgeworthia plants and therefore faster and more continuous supply of bark) should be made subject to concerns over the environmental implications of the introduction.

It would be more worthwhile to consider plantation of the native Daphne and Edgeworthia species in the proposed area instead. Although Edgeworthia grows faster than Daphne, its bark is in lesser demand from the paper producers. A trial plantation of approximately 70% Daphne and 30% Edgeworthia, combined with other (commercially usable or non-usable) native species to maintain at least some degree of natural vegetation and variety, might be a good option. Harvesting of the bark should be done according to the best method described earlier and the harvesting should be done plot-wise, to guarantee a continuous yearly supply and allow for the plants to regenerate.

According to the Forest and Nature Conservation Rules of Bhutan (2000) there are several restrictions to the captive breeding of native species as well. Section 65 (3) page 50 states:

"(a) No wild animal or listed plant shall be taken from the wild for purposes of commercial breeding or cultivation in a private facility, except when the taking occurs with a permit from the Department under this Chapter;

(b) The holder of a permit under section 65 (3) (a) shall be required to prove or certify that any specimen possessed or sold by such person have been taken under the permit or are offspring produced in such facility;

(c) For purpose of this selection, the term 'commercial' shall refer to any activity or undertaking with the intent of the ultimate sale, barter, exhibition, or other activity obtaining financial benefit from the species, its offspring, or any parts, eggs, or fruits thereof."

Problem arises to what extent the term 'listed plant' applies to Daphne and Edgeworthia. Strictly speaking it refers to the Schedule I plants of the Forest and Nature Conservation Act (1995) in which neither species is listed.

In Yangtse, there are options for cultivation of Daphne as well. Open, fallow government reserved forests may be leased to the local community and become community forest to develop Daphne plantation areas. It would also protect the water sheds, prevent soil erosion and landslides. In combination with this Daphne cultivation, trees used as firewood can be planted. On privately owned oak forests (Dz. Shokshing), used to collect leaf-litter for animal sheds, Daphne growth and plantation can be encouraged as well since Daphne originally grows in these forest types (Sherub, 1999).

Fuel wood consumption: The use of fuel wood in the deysho production in Bhutan can not be separated from the overall fuel wood use in Bhutan. Around 90% of the total fuel consumption in the rural areas is met by fuel wood and even in the urban areas fuel wood is an important energy source. Despite the forest cover of 72% the forest cover in certain heavily exploited areas is dwindling and for the future demand for fuel wood to be sustained measures have to be taken to sustain the fuel wood sources. Sustainable forest management is thus of great importance. This is described by the National Environment Commission (1999c) and regulated in the Forest and Nature Conservation Act and Rules (1999, 2000). The new forest management unit at Dongdechu in Trashig Yangtse and the construction of another bridge over the Khulong Chu to increase the accessibility of the unit (Kuensel, 2001a) will provide sustainably managed fuel wood to the deysho producers as well and is a great step forward.

Even with the expected advent of electricity to the villages in Trashy Yangtse with the upcoming completion of the Kurichu Hydroelectric Project they can not afford to replace their boiling on fuel wood by electric boiling since the initial investment is too high. The amount of money they will save by no longer having to buy firewood and pay the collectors and transporters will be insufficient to cover the cost of an electric boiler. Also the long-term volatility of the rural household production makes such a high investment not worthwhile considering.

For the semi-mechanised producers the investment in electric boilers will probably be possible to undertake due to their greater yearly profits and easier access to money for the investment. Also electricity is already available at lower cost than fuel wood due to the hydropower energy generation. The price they pay for fuel wood is higher compared to the household level producers and therefore the reduced costs of fuel wood can outweigh the investment costs. They should therefore be encouraged to shift from fuel wood boiling to an electric boiling process.

Water consumption and pollution: Due to the still small-scale production even in the semi-mechanised units the negative environmental impact of the production is not alarming at the moment. The water consumption in the semi-mechanised units and the paper recycling plant can considerably decrease by installation of water treatment facilities so that waste water can be reused in the production process. This can also remove harmful substances before the water is released back into the environment. Thus far the National Environment Commission and the Thimphu City Corporation have not had any complaints against the semi-mechanised producers in Thimphu. But the pH is exceeding the NEC's own recommended standard, and the emissions of chlorine, chemical dye, thermal increases and suspended solids have apparently not been measured. It might therefore be wise to conduct water tests and set up discharge standards for the semi-mechanised deysho production and encourage the use of water treatment facilities. Furthermore it would be useful to clear the drains through which the wastewater flows from stones, sticks and plants on a regular basis to enable an unhindered flow of water.

5.2.2 Protection of Small Producers

It is obvious that the production methods used in the larger scale factories in Thimphu and Bumthang can never be applied to the small-scale cottage industries in other parts of the country due to financial restrictions. However the transfer of local knowledge and innovative production methods can improve the paper quality of these units considerably. The producers in Trashy Yangtse are facing serious problems with marketing of their products due to comparatively low paper quality. Resho is in much lower demand than the finer tsharsho. Looking at the scale of their production and earned income, the introduction of imported bamboo screens is no option. One option though could be to train a Bhutanese in Japan in making these screens. With Bhutan's bountiful bamboo resources the cost of the screens would considerably decrease thereby enabling the small-scale producers to start using them. Another problem they face is regarding drying the papers especially during the rainy season. The factories in Khaling and Yongphula are able to dry even during cloudy days and their production is not affected. This is a result of the use of black polythene between the roof of the drying shed to trap solar energy. The wet paper drying on the walls underneath thus dries faster and better and therefore Trashigang producers fetch higher prices for their products. This is a low-cost innovation and the transfer of this knowledge is thus of great importance. Thirdly, they should uniform their paper quality in size and thickness. Fourthly, they should adopt innovations regarding the use of other raw material species, dyes and decoration where

possible to increase their product range. Even when the scope for own experimenting with this is low, they could use the experience of the other producers. Lastly, regarding marketing of their products, a way should be found to decrease their dependency on middlemen who all take a piece of the profit. The irregularity of their production can not be avoided since it is a side business for them beside their main agricultural activities; neither can the natural conditions be changed. But direct marketing to paper consumers in Thimphu would certainly enhance their prospects.

In order to achieve all these goals and ensure that the deysho craft will remain of importance in Trashy Yangtse, the formation of the deysho producers association is a leap forward. Through this association the dependency on middlemen regarding raw materials and transport of final products can be decreased. Moreover, it will facilitate the transfer of local knowledge and innovative production techniques.

5.2.3 The Deysho Producers' Association

One of the recommendations from the report by Hadorn and Wangda (1999) was followed up by the MTI in 2000 will result in the establishment of the deysho makers' association of Bhutan. The proposal is still awaiting final approval given by the RGOB. It will initially operate under the MTI but in future supposed to become an autonomous body. Funding for the equipment comes from Japan (Jaica, total ¥30,000,000/-) and possibly from the Netherlands (SDA). It will set up a training centre, most probably in Bjemina, and fund research into the market prospects and export possibilities. An own office in Thimphu is to be established as well.

Another field in which the deysho producers' association can assist the producers is the transfer of knowledge among themselves. For example, in order to improve paper quality and increase the number of paper varieties the producers should go on experimenting with other raw material species for fibres, dyes and decorations. Although mainly the larger scale factories are currently carrying out these experiments, small manufacturers should be encouraged to do this as well. This could increase to a future decrease in the pressure on *Daphne* and *Edgeworthia*. Following products are known to be used as alternative already: morus, banana, vine, walnut, ficus, urtica, grasses, bamboo, rice, straw, betelnut peel fibres, waste paper, waste cloth, and as dyes and decoration: cannabis, indigo, flowers, chillies, leaves, ferns (Hadorn and Wangda, 1999). The use of *Morus* spp in the cast could revive the silk production culture as well which disappeared from the region about 100 years ago due to cheap imports (Sherub, 1999).

Dorji et al.(2000a) also suggest that a deysho producers' association in collaboration with Trashy Yangtse Dzongkhag Administration could greatly benefit the local producers by assisting them in proper grading, packing and branding of their product as well as taking over the role from the middlemen regarding the distribution and sale of the products outside the dzongkhag. Promotion of proper harvesting methods and efficient use of firewood are other fields of interest. Their paper is comparatively of low quality due to the use of cotton screens and rough, unsophisticated production method resulting in resho. The demand for resho is only national, within Bhutan, and has hardly any prospects of increasing in the coming years. Therefore they should attempt to shift to tsharsho production in order to profit from the growing export markets. Diversification of the products and use of other materials i.e. for decoration can be taught as well. Grass root level workshops could be used to discuss these subjects with the producers themselves and to instruct them. With the advent of electricity to Yangtse in 2000 some producers hope to increase their production by making use of electrical heaters and light enabling them to work during nighttime. This development should however

never be encouraged, since it would result in scale advantages for the larger producers who are able to make the investment, increase their production, reduce prices and thus monopolise the craft. The current small-scale production benefits a large number of households which is a situation that should be preserved. Moreover, large increases in the production are from the resource point of view not available or even not possible.

5.2.4 Increasing National and Foreign Demand

The local market for deysho is still very limited. Most Bhutanese can simply not afford to use the more expensive deysho products and therefore prefer the cheaper substitutes, mainly manufactured in India. Since prices for deysho can not be lowered that much, even when scale of production advantages occur, the only option lies in export.

Therefore, further development of the export market needs increased attention if the deysho craft is to sustain in Bhutan. The paper producers association, rather than individual firms, can play an important role in this. In August 2000 the proprietors of Jungsbi and Mangala, with assistance from the Export Promotion Centre under MTI were sent to the annual trade fair and autumn show in Binningham, United Kingdom, as part of a larger group of Bhutanese entrepreneurs. Goal was to promote Bhutanese handicrafts including deysho abroad. This was, according to the producers, the first initiative taken by MTI to seriously promote deysho in potential export markets. Increased awareness of the Bhutanese handmade paper, its production methods and diversity among importers in developed countries mainly in Europe, Northern America, Australia and Japan could provide a stimulus to the export. With competing producers in Nepal and India however increased promotion might not be enough to establish a consistent market share for deysho products abroad. Another instrument that could facilitate this is certification of the products.

5.2.5 Certification of Deysho Products

Market failure in production processes depending heavily on forest resources, such as the deysho production in Bhutan depending largely on the forest for raw materials such as bark and firewood, result from the fact that the markets for many benefits that the forest provides are absent or malfunctioning. This includes benefits such as conservation of genetic resources and biodiversity, protection of watersheds, provision of other non-timber forest products to the local population and esthetical values. These benefits may then be underprovided and the marketable forest products may be over-harvested since the non-market costs (lost benefits) of harvesting the forest products may not be considered in the harvesting decisions (Sikod, 1996).

Another market failure is information asymmetry. Consumers of traditionally produced paper might be Willing To Pay (WTP) more for products that originate from a sustainably managed forest. However, they may lack the information required to differentiate between products originating from sustainably and unsustainably managed forests.

These two types of market failure are connected in the case of certification of deysho. In purchasing traditional paper, the information that consumers lack relates to the degree to which forests are managed for non-market values. This information is provided by certification, so that consumers act as a regulator in attempting to internalise the non-market values into the producers' decisions (Haener and Luckert, 1998). With regards to deysho, certification might provide the means to stimulate the export demand for the product. National demand for deysho will probably not be affected by certification. The demand from abroad, where consumers are more sensitive to 'green' products, could be substantially increased if

the proper methods are applied. The benefits of certification of a forest-based product such as deysho can be distinguished in benefits for consumers, benefits for environmentalists and benefits for the producers.

For the consumers, certification allows them to make more informed purchasing decisions based on specific products attributes (Sikod 1996) and gives them the ability to contribute to environmental conservation through their purchasing decisions (Cabarle et al., 1995). The specific product attributes and environmental conservation in the case of deysho might be the environmentally friendly harvesting of the natural resource, a clean production process hardly involving chemicals and the sustenance and support of local communities. Consumers might be WTP more for certified deysho products if their utility derived from the product increases as a result of the fact that the product they purchase originates from a certified production process. Alternatively, if a consumer is given a choice between certified Bhutanese deysho and non-certified traditional paper from for example India or Nepal, they may opt for the Bhutanese product if they attain satisfaction from the believe that they contribute to environmental enhancement through their purchasing decision (Cabarle et al., 1995). Most demand for certified deysho is likely to originate from markets in Europe and North America, where the number of consumers WTP a green premium is highest (Sikod, 1996). Opinion polls throughout OECD countries have demonstrated that consumers are WTP a premium for environmentally friendly good (Mattoo and Singh, 1994), on average 5 to 10 percent more than for products which don't have this attribute (Lober and Eisen, 1995).

From the environmentalists perspective certification represents a mechanism for decreasing the environmental impacts of harvesting forest products (Rotherham, 1997) and promoting Sustainable Forest Management (Kiker and Putz, 1997).

Jungshi and Mangala, the two largest deysho producers in Bhutan, have been advertising their products abroad by stressing on the environmental friendliness of the product. Their reasoning follows the same logic that also provides producers with benefits of certification. Certification may represent a mechanism for advertising about the sustainability of the production. It may thus secure the producers' market share, which can lead to increased profits. Moreover it may lead to the company's and industry's stature in the market (Rotherham 1997). Certification may eliminate misperceptions and convince the public to accept the sustainability of the producers' production. It can add a 'green premium' to the products, an additional benefit to the producers which can manifest itself in either a higher price or an increased and more secure market share (Haener and Luckert, 1998). However, certification of deysho products has not yet taken place, and as may be concluded from the previous chapters, deysho production is not that environmentally friendly as Jungshi and Mangala pretend. The producers are sending as it were wrong information towards their clients, who however have little idea of the actual situation of deysho production in Bhutan. Official certification by the RGOB will work two-fold. Firstly, the Bhutanese deysho will get official international recognition as being environmentally friendly, with all the benefits for the producers included. Secondly, it will force the producers into adopting more environmentally friendly production. Producers will voluntarily pursue certification of their products if the benefits outweigh the costs. The direct benefits and costs of certification are listed in Table 3.1 (Haener and Luckert, 1998).

Table 3.1: Direct benefits and costs of certification to producers.

Benefits	Costs
Access to new markets and secured position in existing markets	Obtaining, learning and understanding the certification standard
Increased revenue if certified products sell at a higher price	Alteration of operations to comply with certification standards and requirements
Better public relations	Documentation and data collection requirements for certification
	Identifying and tracking the chain of custody
	Finding markets for certified products

More specifically, the costs of certification will include the adoption of sustainable harvesting methods, reduced fire wood and water consumption and cleaning of waste water through alterations in the production process, a detailed collection of data regarding in-and outputs to compare with the standards, and finding markets for the certified deysho. Moreover, the RGOB together with the producers has to define the certification standards.

The result of the certification process is the differentiation of the market for a product into certified and uncertified markets. The certified market is characterised by higher production costs and consumers with a higher WTP compared to the uncertified market segment. Sedjo, Swallow and Goetzl (1997) then predict that the demand for certified and uncertified products would not be independent, but conditional on the prices in the two markets. The final equilibrium will then occur at a point, where the price of the certified products is slightly higher than that of uncertified wood, and that production of the certified products could either decrease or increase, depending upon the differential effects of production side costs and demand side valuation related to certification.

Certification of deysho products can have a significantly positive impact on the demand for deysho products abroad. This would directly benefit the large-scale producers whose production is focussed on the export. It will have much less impact on the small-scale producers, and might even threaten their existence. Moreover, the implications and costs of starting deysho certification will be considerable. It will not be sufficient for the RGOB just to label Bhutanese deysho products as environmentally friendly. The production itself has to become more focussed on conserving the resource base and reducing waste streams and from that point of view the current semi-mechanised production needs to undergo significant changes, which might not be financially and technically possible. The benefits of introducing certification for deysho products might be severely outweighed by these costs. Therefore, other means of promoting the craft abroad seem to be more appropriate.

5.2.6 Paper recycling

The paper recycling plant in Bjemina is unfortunately not as big a success as hoped. In fact, several constraints have led to the shut down of the recycling process. First and foremost the total absence of a market for the recycled paper resulted in a stock of unsold paper and loss for the factory. This absence of a market can be explained by a number of factors. The paper quality was too low to obtain a secure market. Secondly compared to Indian paper the price was too high. Thirdly, inadequate marketing methods led to the absence of market, as people were not aware of the availability of recycled paper.

Recommendations regarding the paper recycling are that the government and other agencies should seriously consider a providing the financial means to restart the paper recycling process in a modified form, with cheaper and higher quality papers as a result. Moreover, the RGOB being the largest paper consumer in Bhutan by far, should stimulate and encourage the use of recycled paper made inside Bhutan over imported paper. Government offices and schools as well as the private sector should be encouraged to use the recycled paper. Without prior market prospects for the recycled paper, the investments will not be able to become profitable and should therefore not be executed.

6 Conclusions and Recommendations

6.1 Introduction

The Kingdom of Bhutan started its development in the 1960s with an intact natural environment and strongly preserved culture and traditions. Throughout the development process the policies of the Royal Government have been aimed at increasing the wellbeing of the people, not only in material sense but also by preserving the natural environment and the rich cultural heritage and traditional values for future generations. Thus it has been effectively promoting a sustainable path of development. It is in this light that the introduction of the ban on certain plastic items in 1999 and the promotion of deysho production should be considered.

6.2 The Effect of the Plastic Ban on the Environment

Evaluation of the ban: The plastic ban was aimed at preventing the negative consequences of uncontrolled plastic use and disposal on the natural environment. Paragraph 2.1 stated that reducing the amount of plastics generated is considered superior over initiatives to reuse or recycle plastics. This reduction can be achieved by various means institutionalised by the government, either command-and-control policies or market-oriented policy tools. More direct government intervention is deemed necessary in case of persistent stock pollutants like plastics due to their nature and high level of uncertainty regarding their impacts on the long term. The choice of the RGOB policy makers therefore fell on a total ban on plastic items. The multi-criteria analysis provided in Paragraph 4.1.1 calculated the effectiveness indices of a number of alternatives and supported the choice of this policy tool under a large number of assumptions regarding the criteria values and criteria weights. A more detailed study of the effects of the different criterion values and criteria weights as set by the policy makers might have resulted in a different outcome though. But it would not be feasible to allocate any further human and financial resources to establishing a better foundation to this decision since the ban is already in place.

Plastic demand and supply: One year after the introduction of the ban the use of plastics has significantly decreased. The results presented in Paragraph 4.1.2 show that in total 85% of the people is aware of the ban and that it is considered to be effective by 66% of the interviewed people, with 70% of the people having a positive attitude towards the ban. Although the ban was not accompanied by a proper awareness campaign among the general public, the small and transparent social structure made it rather well known in a relatively short time.

Not only observation in the field but also the results of the survey and subsequent estimation of total demand and supply for plastics, before and after the introduction of the ban, by means of regression analysis show that there has been a considerable decrease in plastic use. In the surveyed regions, 58% of the consumers no longer use plastics whereas 85% less shopkeepers provide plastics. Moreover, the total number of plastics that are still being used and supplied has decreased. Before the introduction of the ban, regression analysis shows that age, place and total income of shopkeepers determine their distribution of plastics, with an average estimated plastic supply in the surveyed locations of 12.8 bags per day or a total of 23,680 bags per day. Total income and place are considered quite logical explanatory variables but the importance of age is rather surprising. After the ban the determining factors to plastic distribution are environmental awareness and again total income, with an average estimated plastic supply of 0.1508 per day and a total supply of 279 plastics per day. This means a decrease of 99% on average.

Demand for plastics by consumers before the ban is found to be dependant on income only, with an average daily demand of 7.66 plastics per household and a total daily demand in the surveyed regions of 86,137 plastics per day. After the introduction of the ban only environmental awareness determines the demand for plastics which reduced to 1.20 plastics per household per day on average or a total of 13,494 plastics per day in the surveyed regions. This is a decrease of 84% as compared to the situation before the ban. Data inconsistency partly explains the difference between total supply and demand for plastics. Other factors influencing this are the fact that the plastics used by consumers not necessarily have the shops as their source, the models do not account for reuse of plastics, and not the whole of Bhutan was included in the survey.

It is interesting to see the shift from factors such as income to environmental awareness as explanatory variable. It shows that increased environmental awareness does have a positive impact on the reduction of environmentally unfriendly behaviour. Nation-wide 95% of the Bhutanese consider plastics as harmful to the environment, an increase of 50% as compared to before the ban.

Beside the indicators of decrease in number of plastics demanded and supplied there are several other conclusions that were derived from the data. Among the people still using plastics, the use of thin, single use plastics has decreased whereas the use of good quality, lasting, reusable plastics has increased. Furthermore the perceived business necessity of plastic distribution decreased and instead consumer demand has become a more important reason for plastic distribution. Lastly, an increase was noticed in products themselves as source of plastics, whereas India and the border towns and local agents saw a decrease as sources.

The decrease of the plastic use has direct positive effects on the environment: The reduced littering of streets and the landscape has contributed to less visible pollution as well as less clogging of water drains. Health risks to livestock and wildlife from the littered plastic have also decreased. The long-term effects will be even more important. Leakage of harmful substances such as heavy metals to soil and water, resulting from disposed plastics, will decrease over time as the stock does not increase. This in turn reduces the health risks on humans, livestock and wildlife. The substitutes that have taken the place of plastics are less harmful to the environment.

Plastic substitutes and impact on the use of deysho bags: The RGOB provided no information or other means of assistance to the shopkeepers and general public regarding substitutes. It was the inventiveness of the people that resulted in 10 substitutes for plastic finding their way into the market in Bhutan, as presented in Paragraph 4.1.4. These are mainly paper bags imported from India, bags glued from old paper and old paper. The position of the traditional woven bags has also strengthened. In contrast to the expectation of the traditional paper producers, the deysho bags constitute a mere 13% of the total substitute use according to the results of the survey. This still high percentage was however not supported by the general observation, and the data were thought to be biased towards the expected outcome. Regression analysis showed that income, the opinion on deysho and age were the main determinants of the Willingness to Pay for deysho bags. An average WTP of Nu. 8.29 per bag emerged for the households and shopkeepers together in the surveyed regions. This WTP was higher than the actual market price of deysho bags. Therefore, other reasons than price are thought to determine the demand for deysho. These reasons are the lack of marketing methods, difficult substitution between plastics and deysho due to the inherent utility

weaknesses of deysho, and the comparative advantages of other substitutes. It is doubtful whether these problems can be overcome to assure a higher use of deysho bags.

6.2 Environmental Effects of Deysho Production

In-output analysis: The in-output diagrams of the different production processes provided a handy tool in establishing the current use of raw materials- bark, fuel wood and water- and the disposal and possible reuse of waste water. They were used to discuss the environmental effects of deysho production regarding these three raw materials.

The effects on bark supply: Box 2 and Paragraph 4.2.6 bring a problem to the surface faced by all producers irrespective of location and production level: the increase in prices for raw materials. Uncontrolled and improper harvesting in the past decades has resulted in a depletion of the plants providing the main raw material, bark. With the decline in availability of bark the price is steadily increasing. This threatens the very survival and sustainability of deysho production in the future. The total demand for bark is estimated at nearly 100 tons yearly. The current total supply of *Daphne* and *Edgeworthia* in Bhutan is unknown. There has been no research into the actual prevalence of the plants at different locations, their age and expected bark yield. The estimations of growth functions of bark weight in relation to age are a step forward. Without forest inventarisation however no estimation of total supply can be made.

Fuel wood consumption: Fuel wood use in deysho production as described in Paragraph 4.2.7 is another factor of concern. Annual fuel wood consumption is estimated at 700 tons, mainly in the boiling process. The rural household producers have hardly any opportunities to reduce this. Even with the advent of electricity the investments in electric boilers would be too high for them. The semi-mechanised producers however could probably afford to make these investments.

Water consumption and pollution: Paragraph 4.2.8 shows that the amount of water that is being used in deysho production is high as well. The abundance of this resource in Bhutan makes the use for deysho production negligible. Water pollution is a reason for concern however. The pH of the alkali water used for boiling the bark is very high, between 8.3 to 23.1, and this can have negative impacts on the water quality. The water used for boiling the bark can also cause thermal pollution. In the rural household production the water is extremely diluted since it immediately reaches the river and thus causes little harm. In the semi-mechanised units however the water has to go a long way down to the river and may cause changes in the soil condition on the way. Moreover, the use of chemicals such as chlorine bleach, chemical dyes and glue might contaminate soil and water. The drains also get clogged due to remnants of bark and pulp.

Paper recycling: After introduction of the ban one of the owners of a semi-mechanised deysho production unit in Thimphu made an attempt to increase the use of deysho bags by lowering their price through machine-aided production lowering production costs. This large scale, machine-aided production in Bjemina was shifted to paper recycling in October, 1999, out of environmental concern and in order to increase revenues. A serious lack of demand for recycled paper forced the plant to shift back to machine-aided production of deysho again. The price of recycled paper was too high and its use too limited as quality was insufficient. The current process is consuming very large amounts of fuel wood and water. To make the production more environmentally friendly as well as open up the possibilities of a restart of

the paper recycling process by producing cheaper and better quality recycled paper several investments were proposed.

Under certain assumptions mentioned in Paragraph 4.2.5, the investment in an automatic (electric) boiler is considered worthwhile undertaking as it would radically reduce fuel wood use and thus reduce production cost as well. The investment in a water treatment installation is not recommended separately since costs will outweigh benefits. In combination with the introduction of completely new production technology, a total of 6 new machines, it becomes profitable.

6.4 Economic Viability and Sustainability of Deysho Production

Supply and demand of deysho: Deysho production is one of the traditional arts and crafts in Bhutan and therefore has a considerable historical and cultural significance, which is a very strong point in advocating its existence and survival. Around 40 producers produce yearly nearly 850,000 sheets with an annual turnover exceeding Nu. 6,000,000. By means of regression analysis the average monthly consumption of deysho per household in the surveyed regions was estimated to be 2.75 sheets. The demand was found to be dependent on the income and the opinion on deysho. The low R^2 of the model was again thought to be caused by data inconsistency and bias. However total demand in the surveyed regions was estimated at nearly 328,000 sheets per year. This means that 522,000 sheets find their way to other national consumers with the remainder being exported. Attitudes for deysho were found to be very positive, with 86% of the population having a positive attitude.

The deysho production is a very volatile business and this makes estimations regarding economical data difficult. Paragraph 4.2.1 states that there is a distinction in two production levels: the semi-mechanised production concentrated in Thimphu and the rural household production concentrated in Trashigang. There are several constraints to deysho production that are steadily starting to affect the viability of the craft. Both production levels face a number of common as well as specific problems.

Rural household production: Box 2 shows that the rural household level production provides the producers and their families with considerable cash addition to their income from agriculture, which might prevent them from migrating and leaving the rural areas. On average a yearly profit of Nu. 9,500/- is made. The wages paid to raw material collectors, middlemen and hired labour significantly increases the benefits of the production beyond the producers themselves. The specific problem they face is mainly a weak market for their products. This is mainly due to the lack of uniformity in size, quality and price, improper packaging and grading and difficult transportation. This results in unstable and irregular production benefits that could undermine the viability of their craft, even to the extent that future continuation of the production becomes doubtful.

Export: From Paragraph 4.2.3 it can be concluded that the semi-mechanised producers are faced with another problem. Their value added diversified products hardly find a local market in Bhutan itself because the prices are too high and use is limited. They heavily rely on the export market. This market is however little explored.

6.5 Recommendations

Policy decision support: The MCA analysis in Paragraph 4.1.1 concluded that a total plastic ban would, under the given assumptions, be the most effective alternative. It would not harm the RGOB to use Cost Benefit Analysis (if monetary values can be assigned to all the criteria effects) or Multi Criteria Analysis for further decisions regarding the implementation of policies, especially when related to environmental preservation.

Data collection for research and policy use: In all the regression models presented in Paragraph 4.1.2 and 4.2.3, the R^2 is very low due to which doubts over the validity of the models arise. The models in Paragraph 4.1.4 have a higher but still not convincing R^2 . The low explanatory strength of the models is probably caused by inconsistent and biased data that are the result of the methods of data collection. The lack of data available in Bhutan seriously hampered this research as well as limits informed decision making at higher levels. It resulted in the need to collect data with the help of inexperienced interviewers, which might have led to interviewer bias in the data, in turn causing various problems in their analysis. Allocation of sufficient human and financial resources to data collection in Bhutan is therefore strongly advocated to overcome these problems.

Increased enforcement of the ban: A total prohibition has to combine with effective monitoring and large penalties for non-compliance. The fine of complete withdrawal of the shop license after two offences of the ban is strict enough and should enable compliance. Paragraph 5.1 discusses that currently weak enforcement of the law by inspectors of the Ministry of Trade and Industry is considered to be the main reason of the fact that banned plastics are still being provided and used and the observation that this happens in increasing numbers. Increased vigilance in the enforcement of the law by introducing more manpower is therefore recommended to increase its effectiveness and prevent the old situation from reoccurring.

Reducing the pressure on the stock of Daphne and Edgeworthia trees: In face of uncertainty since no accurate supply estimations can be carried out, measures have to be taken to preserve the current resource stock and increase it in whatever way possible. These options are discussed in Paragraph 5.2.1. Firstly, harvesters should be educated on the best harvesting method: cutting the stem at 2-15 cm above ground level and peeling of the bark thus encouraging regeneration. Secondly, they should be encouraged to harvest trees with an age of about 7 years for Edgeworthia and 15 years for Daphne (corresponding to a target diameter of 8 cms) since this takes different aspects besides mean annual increment culmination into account. Thirdly, a survey of heavily harvested areas as well as surveys for new, unexploited areas where harvest can take place to decrease the pressure on certain areas. Harvesting licenses should be withheld for heavily exploited areas and instead issued for unexploited areas, and regeneration time should also be taken into account when issuing the permits. Fourthly, the possibilities of cultivation on plantations should be encouraged. The current initiative to plant Japanese Mulberry should be carefully examined since it carries a lot of possibly negative environmental impacts. Instead, possibilities for (re-) plantation of Daphne and Edgeworthia in overexploited areas, on fallow government forests and on sokshing, privately owned oak forests, should be explored and trial plantations should be started.

Reducing fuel wood consumption: The semi-mechanised producers will be financially more enabled to reduce their fuel wood consumption by making investments in new technologies. They should therefore be encouraged or even legally committed to this, for as far as they haven't done it as yet. Sustainable collection of fuel wood should also be encouraged but this is an issue that plays in the general environmental spectrum in Bhutan with most of the population being dependent on wood for energy provision.

Reducing water pollution: Further research into water pollution by the semi-mechanised units has to be executed and appropriate measures have to be taken. Water treatment facilities should be made compulsory if the wastewater is proven to contaminate the environment.

Sustaining rural household deysho production: The problems that the rural household producers face threaten the survival of the craft as an important cash income generator. According to Paragraph 4.2.2 and 5.2.3 the recently established Deysho Producers' Association can address this issue. This can be done through facilitating the transfer of local knowledge, the introduction of innovative production methods, the uniformisation of the paper quality, price deals to reduce unfair competition and decreasing the dependence on the middlemen.

Increasing foreign demand: The semi-mechanised producers heavily rely on the foreign demand. Paragraph 5.2.4 states that future exploitation of the export markets should be promoted by the RGOB. The role of the Deysho Producers' Association in this should be limited since it will only benefit the larger producers who have the funds to do this on their own. Paragraph 5.2.5 concluded that certification of deysho products on the international market is, for the time being, considered as undesirable due to high costs associated with its introduction which will outweigh the possible benefits.

Paper recycling: The owner of the paper recycling plant has a lack of funds to execute the proposed investment in a completely new production technology, which would result in the production of recycled paper of higher quality and lower price. In Paragraph 5.2.6 it is therefore recommended that the RGOB and various national and international organisations consider supporting this investment to give the paper-recycling project a new life. It has to combine with serious marketing though in which government institutions, private companies, schools and international organisations in Bhutan have to be stimulated to use the recycled paper instead of imported Indian paper.

6.4 Concluding Thought

The positive impact of the plastic ban on the environment is unquestionable. Plastic use has considerably decreased and many substitutes have found their way into the market. Deysho bags have not been able to secure the expected market position. Not price, but factors like user-friendliness appear to be the cause of this. The deysho production is of great importance to the local producers, who earn most of their cash income from the business. The newly established Deysho Producers' Association is expected to address specific issues that threaten their survival, as well as institutionalising measures to prevent the overexploitation of the natural resources that form the basis of production: Daphne and Edgeworthia. This threatens the survival of the business as a whole. The semi-mechanised producers have to try to open the export market further. The paper recycling plant can become a profitable and environmentally friendly business again when certain investments are made. In all, this report hopes to provide policy makers and deysho producers with some views, support and advice to enable to continuation along the "Middle Path" towards the national goal of "Gross National Happiness".

Glossary and Acronyms

- Arish- traditional Bhutanese distilled wine made from rice or maize
Ashi- title of a woman belonging to the nobility
Betang- Tibetan silver coins used as medium of exchange in Bhutan before the introduction of a monetary system
B'la-shye- Dzalakha term for alkali water
Bumthabikha- language of Bumthang Dzongkhag
Ch.- Choekey, classical Tibetan language in which the Buddhist scriptures in Bhutan are written
Cher-gen (Dz. gSig-pa)- a sieve made from cane
Dasho (Dz. Drag-sho)- official rank accompanied by a red kamney
Dzo (Dz. rDal-dzo)- traditional paper maker
Dew (Dz. De'u)- pebbles used for counting
Deysho (or Druksho, Dz. rDal-sho, aBrug-sho)- traditional Bhutanese paper
Dzo (Dz. rDal-bzo)- art of traditional paper making
DFO- Dzongkhag Forest Officer
DFEO- Dzongkhag Forest Extension Officer
Doma- traditional Bhutanese condiment consisting of betelnut (doma), betelleaf (pancy) and lime (suney).
Dum (Dz. mZer)- small stick with the size and length of a forefinger
Dungkhag- sub-division of a dzongkhag
Dz.- Dzongkha or Zhungkha, national language of Bhutan, belonging to the Tibeto-Mongol language group and written in Tibetan script
Dzalakha- 'money's language', language of Trashig Yangtse Dzongkhag and parts of Lhuentse and Arunachal Pradesh
Dzong (rDzong)- fortress where the civil and religious power in a district is located
Dzongkhag- district. Bhutan has a total of 20 districts.
Phrok-pa (rTshow)- bamboo or cane basket
FSD- Forestry Services Division
Gcog- block of villages within a dzongkhag
Gung (Dz. Gung)- household
Guru (Dz. Gu-tu)- teacher
Jama (Dz. Bya-ma)- local unit of measurement equal to three kilograms
Jatongpa (Ch. BiGya-stong-pa)- religious text
Kabum (Ch. BKa'-bum)- religious text
Kamney (Sh. Sari)- ceremonial scarf
Kanjur (Ch. BKa'-'Gyur)- religious text containing the exact teachings of Lord Buddha
Kasho (bKa'-shog)- Royal edict or command
Khakap- Dzalakha term for cane or bamboo strainer
Kharo (Dz. mThalku)- alkali water
Lhakang (Dz. Lha-khang)- monastery
Litong- Dzalakha term for heavy wooden pulp beater
Loa-ri (Dz. Zangs)- very thick, non-corrosive copper vessel
Lyonpo- minister.
MoA- Ministry of Agriculture
MTI- Ministry of Trade and Industry
NEC- National Environment Commission
NTEP- Non Timber Forest Product, also NWFP, Non Wood Forest Product.
Parshing- wooden framed cloth screen measuring 20" by 30" used to produce resho
Rabdey (Dz. Rab-sDe)- monastic body
Resho- deysho made with cloth screens
RGOB- Royal Government Of Bhutan
Rinpoche (Dz. Rin-po-che)- precious religious teacher
RNR-RC-Renewable Natural Resources- Research Center
RSPN- Royal Society for the Protection of Nature
Salang- Dzalakha term for losra
Sh.- Sharchop, Sharohopkha, Sharchobikba or Tshangla, main language of Eastern Bhutan, belonging to the Tibeto-Burman language group
Shogu-shing (or deyshing, Dz. Sho-gu-shing, rDal-shing)- Daphne or Edge worthia tree
Sokshing- privately owned oak forest
Suma- wooden barrel (mainly from Betula spp. and Taxus buccata) used for churning butter tea or wood pulp

Tenjur (Ch. BsTan-'Gyur)- later commentaries of the teachings of Lord Buddha
Thomkhang- Court of Justice.
Thrimpon- Judge
Thrompon- mayor of a major town.
T'rb.- Tibetan
Trekpa- Dzalakha term for Daphne bark
Tsar (Dz. mTshar)- bamboo sieve
Tsharsho- deyshe made with bamboo screens
Tseri- registered land where previously shifting cultivation was allowed (now prohibited)

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Annex 2, Diagram I: Production Process in Rural Household

Diagram II: Production Process in Semi Mechanised Unit

Reprocessing of spoilt sheets
Use of wood ash

Input flow
Output flow

Through flow
Potential reuse of water

Diagram III: Production Process in Paper Recycling Plant

Annex 3: Questions from the Survey on Plastic Ban and Deysho

Since June 2nd 1999 the use and sale of plastic bags, plastic dome wrappers and home made ice cream (Pepsi) pouches has been banned. In response to this ban the dcysho (traditional Bhutanese paper) producers expected an increase in the demand for their products. This survey is aimed at determining the extent of this increase and related aspects.

Consumer survey

Plastic.

1. Do you think plastic is bad for the environment?

- (a) Yes
- (b) No

2. Do you know about the plastic ban?

- (a) Yes
- (b) No (→ explain them about the ban before continuing)

3. Do you think the ban is effective although other things are still sold packed in plastic?

- (a) Yes
- (b) No

4. What do you think about this ban?

- (a) Very good
- (b) Good
- (c) Neutral
- (d) Bad
- (e) Very bad

5. Before the ban, how many plastics did your households get (from shops etc) per day?

- (a) <5
- (b) 5-10
- (c) 10-20
- (d) >20

6. Do you still use plastics yourself? If no, why? If yes, how many per week does your household use? And why?

- (a) No;
 - i. Concern for environment
 - ii. Chance of being fined
 - iii. Not available
 - iv. Expensive
 - v. Other, namely.....

→ continue with question 10.

- (b) Yes;
 - i. <5
 - ii. 5-10
 - iii. 10-20
 - iv. >20

Because.....

- I. necessary for shopping
- II. getting them free
- III. cheaply available
- IV. other, namely.....

→ continue with question 7.

7. If you use plastics, what kind of plastics do you use?

- (a) Thin, single use plastics
- (b) Thicker plastics
- (c) Good quality, lasting, re-usable plastics
- (d) Combination, namely.....

8. If you use plastics, from which kinds of shops do you get them (more than one answer possible)?

- (a) Groceries
- (b) Clothing
- (c) Hardware
- (d) Restaurant, bar, hotel
- (e) Stationary
- (f) Electronics
- (g) Pan shop
- (h) General

9. Have you ever been caught by police or city corporation for using plastics, if yes, how many times?

- (a) No
- (b) Yes;
 - i. Once
 - ii. Twice
 - iii. Thrice

Substitution.

10. Out of the following list of substitutes for plastics, which do you use as substitute and in which order of importance? (more than one answer possible)

- (a) Traditional woven bags
- (b) Imported nylon bags
- (c) Indian-made paper bags
- (d) Hand woven plastic-string baskets
- (e) Glued paper bags
- (f) Old paper
- (g) Re-stitched cement bags
- (h) Re-used plastic bags
- (i) Jute bags
- (j) Deysho bags

Deysho

11. What do you think about deysho, the traditional Bhutanese paper?

- (a) Very good
- (b) Good
- (c) Neutral
- (d) Bad
- (e) Very bad

12. Which of the following deysho products do you use, and how many per month (indicate with number, more than one answer possible)?

- (a) Rough sheets (e.g. for wrapping of gifts)
- (b) Decorated sheets
- (c) Envelopes
- (d) Photo albums, photo frames
- (e) Files and folders
- (f) Postcards
- (g) Bags

13. If the price of deysho bags would be how many Ngultrum (maximum price you would pay between Nu. 1/- and Nu. 50/-), would you start to use these bags instead of plastic bags, thinking about things such as eco-friendliness, reusability, promotion of traditional craft and industry and the price of other substitutes?

Background information

14. How many people does your household have?

.....

15. What is your average monthly income?

Nu.....

16. What is your age?

.....

17. Village, gcog, dzongkhag name

.....

18. What job do you have?

.....

19. What education did you have?

- (a) No education
- (b) Non-formal education
- (c) Primary education
- (d) Class 10
- (e) Class 12
- (f) Diploma course
- (g) Bachelors Degree
- (h) Masters Degree
- (i) Professional Masters

Supplier survey

Plastic

1. Do you think plastic is bad for the environment?

- (a) Yes
- (b) No

2. Do you know about the plastic ban?

- (a) Yes
- (b) No (→ explain about the ban before continuing)

3. Do you think the ban is effective although other things are still sold packed in plastic?

- (a) Yes
- (b) No

4. What do you think about this ban?

- (a) Very good
- (b) Good
- (c) Neutral
- (d) Bad
- (e) Very bad

5. Before the ban, how many plastics did you give to customers per day?

- (a) <5
- (b) 5-10
- (c) 10-20
- (d) 20-30
- (e) 30-50

(f) >50

6. Do you still give plastics to customers? If no, why? If yes, how many times per day? And why?

(a) No;

- i. Concern for environment
- ii. Chance of being fined
- iii. Not available
- iv. Expensive
- v. Other, namely.....

→ continue with question 11.

(b) Yes;

- i. <5
- ii. 5-10
- iii. 10-20
- iv. 20-30
- v. 30-50
- vi. >50

Because.....

- I. necessary for business
- II. getting them free
- III. cheaply available
- IV. customers want them and ask for them
- V. other, namely.....

→ continue with question 7.

7. Have you ever been caught by police or city corporation for giving plastics, if yes, how many times?

(a) No

(b) Yes;

- i. Once
- ii. Twice
- iii. Thrice

8. If you give plastics, what kind of plastics do you give?

- (a) Thin, single use plastics
- (b) Thicker plastics
- (c) Good quality, lasting, re-usable plastics
- (d) Combination, namely.....

9. If you give plastics, from where do you get them?

- (a) Free with products
- (b) Local agent
- (c) India/border towns
- (d) Elsewhere, namely.....

Substitution.

10. Out of the following list of substitutes, which do you give as substitute and in which order of importance (more than one answer possible)?

- (a) Traditional woven bags
- (b) Imported nylon bags
- (c) Indian-made paper bags
- (d) Hand woven plastic-string baskets
- (e) Glued paper bags
- (f) Old paper
- (g) Re-stitched cement bags
- (h) Re-used plastic bags
- (i) Jute bags
- (j) Deysho bags

Deysho

11. What do you think about deysho, the traditional Bhutanese paper?

- (a) Very good
- (b) Good
- (c) Neutral
- (d) Bad
- (e) Very bad

12. Do you give deysho bags to customers, if yes, how much do you pay for them and how much do you ask from the customer?

- (a) No
- (b) Yes;

I pay Nu.....

I ask Nu.....

13. If the price of deysho bags would be how many Ngultrum (maximum price you would pay between Nu. 1/- and Nu. 50/-), would you give these bags instead of plastic bags, thinking about things such as eco-friendliness, reusability, promotion of traditional craft and industry and the price of other substitutes?

Background information

14. What is your average monthly income from your shop?

Nu.....

15. What is your total average monthly income?

Nu.....

16. What is your age?

.....

17. Shop number, village, geog, dzongkhag name

.....

18. What is your type of shop?

- (a) Groceries
- (b) Clothing
- (c) Hardware
- (d) Restatrant, bar, hotel
- (e) Stationary
- (f) Electronics
- (g) Pan shop
- (h) General

19. What education did you complete?

- (a) No education
- (b) Non-formal education
- (c) Primary education
- (d) Class 10
- (e) Class 12
- (f) Diploma course
- (g) Bachelors Degree
- (h) Masters Degree
- (i) Professional Masters

